

**TO MEASURE THE PERFORMANCE OF PIA AIRLINES AND
ACCESS THE IMPACT OF LEADERSHIP ON PERFORMANCE
USING A BALANCED SCORECARD**

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DEDICATION

The doctoral research is dedicated to my husband, Mr Nabeel Arshad, my son Nayel Nabeel, and my Parents, throughout my doctoral research. Their belief in me and constant encouragement were crucial to my journey. I am deeply grateful for their presence and unwavering support.

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AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I, Zoya Asghar, declare that the ideas, research work, analyses, interpretation and conclusion reported in the DBA thesis *to measure the performance of PIA airlines in Pakistan and to access the impact of leadership on performance using the balanced scorecard (BSC) model* unless, as otherwise stated, it is exclusively my work. Also, I declare that this thesis does not contain any content formerly demonstrated for the award of any other academic degree or certificate, in whole or in part. This thesis is all my work unless otherwise indicated.

ABSTRACT

This research study aims to evaluate PIA Airlines' performance and assess leadership's influence using the balanced scorecard (BSC) model. The study examines the conceptual framework and investigates the relationship between performance and revenue in the airline industry. Although the positive link between performance and financial position is well-established, limited research has explored the significance of the BSC model.

The study collects time series data from 2011 to 2020, including financial conditions, customer opinions, and financial performance ratios of PIA Airlines. The BSC analyses financial, customer, learning and growth perspectives. Additionally, cross-sectional data analysis compares PIA Airlines with three randomly selected airlines (Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines) from 2016 to 2020.

The conceptual framework examines the internal process perspective of PIA Airlines and identifies predictors and outcomes of leadership conduct. Structural equation modelling is conducted using SPSS (21) and AMOS (24), and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) includes KMO & Bartlett's test.

The study finds that political interference moderates the relationship between leadership conduct and PIA Airlines' performance, while corruption moderates the relationship between leaders' decision-making and leadership conduct. A positive relationship exists between the use of advanced technology and leaders' communication. However, unexpected circumstances lead to lacking support for H1 and H3.

Results indicate that the customer perspective is not significantly associated with sustaining the airline's performance. However, financial attitude, internal leadership, learning & growth perspectives, and environmental perspectives positively impact PIA's performance. The study also reveals the distinct culture and values within the airline industry in Pakistan.

Furthermore, the study suggests exploring sustainability-balanced scorecards (SBSCs) to address environmental, social, and ethical issues. Industry leaders can leverage this opportunity to examine how SBSCs are incorporated and determine causal links between various perspectives, providing insights into past underdevelopment of such models.

Overall, this research sheds light on the performance of PIA Airlines and its relationship with leadership. It contributes to understanding the airline industry and provides recommendations for incorporating sustainability perspectives into performance measurement frameworks.

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Chapter 1 Introduction

1.0 Introduction

The first chapter is the introduction to this research. This chapter is divided into subsections to explain every effect of the thesis in detail. The fundamental idea of this research is “To measure the performance of PIA Airlines and assess the impact of leadership using the balanced scorecard (BSC) model”. The chapter starts with the broader area, which is the Global aviation industry. The next heading covers the airline industry in Pakistan, followed by Pakistan International Airlines, including the PIA’s issues. In the next step, the research problem is defined; the research aim is explained. After the research aim, the research objectives and the research question have been formed. The motivation for the research is written in detail, along with the research gap and research contribution of the study. After the detailed explanation of the research contribution, the theoretical and practical literature gap has been defined. The operational model for the thesis has been shown in this chapter. Finally, this chapter concludes with the closing paragraph.

1.1 Global Aviation Industry

The modern aviation industry began in the early twentieth century when pioneers such as the Wright Brothers and Louis Blériot experimented with powered flight. In the years that followed, aviation technology continued to advance rapidly, spurred on by the demands of World War I and the desire to create faster, more efficient modes of transportation (Button and Taylor, 2000; Wensveen, 2018). In 1919, the British airline company Aircraft Transport and Travel launched the world's first scheduled airline service. It marked the beginning of the modern aviation industry, which has since become a global network of airlines, airports, and supporting industries (Taherdoost and Brard, 2019). The aviation industry has played a vital role in shaping the modern world, connecting people and places across continents and facilitating trade, tourism, and cultural exchange. Today, the industry continues to evolve, driven by technological advances, changing consumer preferences, and new market opportunities (Button and Taylor, 2000; Wensveen, 2018).

The aviation industry is an essential component of the global economy, providing a vital link between people, businesses, and regions worldwide (Ghanbari et al., 2017; Bourne et al., 2018). It enables people to travel to different parts of the world for business, leisure, and education and facilitates the movement of goods and services between nations. The industry also supports various related businesses, from tourism and hospitality to logistics and manufacturing (Taherdoost and Brard, 2019). In addition to its economic importance, the aviation industry also plays a crucial role in promoting cultural exchange and understanding. It brings people of different backgrounds and cultures together, fosters collaboration and innovation, and promotes peace and prosperity. Moreover, the industry strongly focuses on safety and security, with stringent regulations and procedures to ensure passengers and crew can travel confidently. In short, the aviation industry is vital for connectivity, growth, and progress in the modern world (Devlin and Gerrard, 2005).

The global aviation industry is a complex and rapidly evolving sector that connects people, goods, and ideas worldwide (Airlines, 2021). While the industry has experienced growth and success over the years, it has also faced significant challenges in terms of performance and leadership. Airlines and airports constantly strive to improve operational efficiency, enhance passenger experience, and maintain safety and security standards (Guo and Maitra, 2017). At the same time, they must navigate complex regulatory frameworks, manage costs, and adapt to changing market conditions. Effective leadership is crucial in addressing these challenges and ensuring that organizations in the aviation industry remain competitive and sustainable. With exemplary leadership, innovative thinking, and strategic planning, the industry can continue to thrive and contribute to the global economy.

The aviation industry has seen many successful airlines, each with its unique growth story, innovation, and success (Phillips et al., 2019). Some of the most successful airlines are known for their strong brand identity, exceptional customer service, and innovative business models. For example, Emirates, based in Dubai, has become one of the world's largest and most successful airlines. It is known for its luxurious in-flight experience, extensive route network, and commitment to innovation. Another successful airline is Southwest Airlines, which pioneered the low-cost carrier model in the United States. It has since become one of the most profitable airlines in the country, focusing on efficiency, affordability, and customer service (Taherdoost & Brard, 2019). Other successful airlines include Singapore Airlines, known for its award-winning service and innovative products, and Air New Zealand, which has a strong reputation for sustainability, innovation, and community engagement. These successful airlines

share a common focus on providing exceptional customer service, investing in their employees, and taking a strategic, innovative approach to business.

The aviation industry has seen its fair share of failed airlines, many of which could not compete in a highly competitive and challenging market. Some of the most high-profile failures in recent years include airlines such as Thomas Cook, Monarch, and WOW Air. These airlines faced various challenges, including changing consumer preferences, rising fuel costs, intense competition, and financial mismanagement. Other factors that have contributed to the failure of airlines include operational issues, safety concerns, and regulatory challenges. Despite the challenges, many failed airlines have left a legacy, serving as cautionary tales for others in the industry. They have highlighted the importance of strong leadership, financial discipline, and a clear strategic vision for success. At the same time, their failures have also created opportunities for new players to enter the market and innovate, driving the industry forward and enhancing the overall quality of service for customers.

After the above information and knowing the importance of the aviation industry, the researcher cracked down the research topic to the aviation industry, which was the first step to selecting the research topic that would also benefit future researchers and the economy.

1.2 Airline Industry in Pakistan

The airline industry in Pakistan is an important and rapidly growing sector, contributing to the country's economic development and connectivity with the rest of the world. The industry comprises several domestic and international airlines, including the national flag carrier Pakistan International Airlines (PIA), which has been operating since 1946. The airline industry in Pakistan has faced several challenges in recent years, including issues with safety, security, and financial sustainability. However, the industry has shown resilience and adaptability, with many airlines adopting new technologies and modernizing their fleets to remain competitive. Some of the key players in the industry include Airblue, Serene Air, and Shaheen Air, which have all made significant investments in their fleets and services in recent years. The government of Pakistan has also taken steps to support the industry, including investing in new airports and infrastructure and providing incentives for airlines to expand their operations (Forecasting, 2006). With a growing population and a rising middle class, the airline industry in Pakistan is poised for continued growth and success in the years ahead.

1.2.1 Issues Faced by Pakistan Airline Industry

The airline industry in Pakistan is facing several challenges hindering its growth and development, including challenges related to leadership and performance. One of the significant challenges is political interference, which has led to inefficiencies and corruption in the industry (Baloch et al., 2014). Appointments to crucial airline positions are often based on political connections rather than merit, leading to a lack of accountability and poor decision-making. Another leadership challenge is the need for more effective leadership and management practices within some airlines, which can lead to a lack of direction and poor team member morale. Additionally, the performance of some airlines in Pakistan needs to improve, with financial losses, poor customer service, and outdated technologies hindering their ability to compete in the market (Selase, 2018). The COVID-19 pandemic has also significantly impacted the airline industry in Pakistan, with reduced demand and travel restrictions leading to further financial losses and job cuts. To address the challenges, the industry must focus on reducing political interference, investing in effective leadership and management practices, improving performance, and adapting to the market's changing demands. It will require a commitment to transparency, accountability, and innovation to ensure the long-term sustainability and success of the airline industry in Pakistan (Nawaz et al., 2012).

The airline industry in Pakistan, like other industries, requires strong leadership to navigate the complex and rapidly changing business environment. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of leadership in driving organizational success and sustainability. Many airlines in Pakistan have adopted different leadership styles depending on their business objectives, organizational culture, and external environment. Some airlines have adopted an autocratic leadership style, where a single individual makes decisions (Hsu et al., 2019). In contrast, others have embraced a more democratic style, where decisions are made through collaboration and consensus building. Some airlines have adopted a transformational leadership style, where leaders inspire and motivate their teams to achieve their full potential. Effective leadership in the airline industry requires a combination of technical expertise, strategic vision, people skills, and crisis management capabilities (shah, 2018). With a rapidly changing business landscape and increasing competition, strong leadership is critical for the success and sustainability of airlines in Pakistan.

After discussing the airline industry in Pakistan, the challenges and issues of the airline industry got the researcher's attention. Pakistan is a developing country, and without a stable

government, a strong currency and many other unstable external and internal factors, PIA Airline, the oldest airline in Pakistan, still operates and manages to stand in the competitive world in the airline industry. The researcher needs to know what is happening and how this study would help Pakistan's oldest and national flag carrier airline.

1.3 Pakistan International Airline (PIA)

Pakistan International Airlines (PIA) was founded on March 29, 1954, as the national airline of Pakistan (PIA, 2021). The airline initially operated domestic and a few international routes using leased aircraft. In 1955, PIA acquired its first Boeing 707 aircraft and expanded its international route network to London, Tokyo, and Hong Kong. Over the next few decades, PIA continued to expand its fleet and route network, becoming one of the leading airlines in South Asia. The new venture approached PIA with its idea of a new airline and asked for as much support as it could lend. With a budget of \$10 million, Emirates could rent two aircraft and receive administrative support and engineering assistance in running the airline (Phillips et al., 2019).

PIA faced several challenges in the 1970s and 1980s, including financial losses, political interference, and team member strikes. Despite these challenges, the airline continued to expand its route network and fleet, and in the 1990s, it launched a significant modernization program to improve its service and efficiency (Ghanbari et al., 2017; Bourne et al., 2018).

The airline industry in Pakistan plays a vital role in the country's economic development, contributing to job creation, trade, and tourism. The industry generates significant revenue for the government through taxes and fees and supports a range of related industries, including hospitality, transportation, and retail. The airline industry is also an essential source of employment, directly and indirectly creating jobs for pilots, cabin crew, ground staff, and maintenance workers. Furthermore, the industry facilitates trade and commerce by providing efficient and reliable transportation for goods and services (Kaul & Gupta, 2019). The tourism sector in Pakistan also benefits from a strong airline industry, as it enables tourists to easily access and explore the country's rich cultural heritage and natural beauty.

Overall, the airline industry in Pakistan plays a vital role in the country's economic growth, competitiveness, and global positioning. It drives job creation, supports trade and commerce, and promotes tourism. The industry's economic contributions make it an essential sector for

government focus and investment. By fostering a favourable environment for the growth and development of the airline industry, Pakistan can maximize its economic potential and reap the benefits of a thriving aviation sector.

1.4 The Research Aim

“The Research Aim Is To Measure The Performance Of PIA Airlines And Access The Impact Of Leadership Using The Balanced Scorecard”

The research involves utilizing the BSC as a tool for performance measurement. The study focuses on examining the first three perspectives of the BSC using secondary data sources, while the fourth perspective is analysed through the collection of primary data. A set of research questions and objectives have been formulated to guide the research and achieve the study's aim. These questions and objectives serve as a roadmap for conducting a comprehensive assessment of PIA Airlines' performance and understanding the role of leadership in driving organizational outcomes.

The Research Objectives

1. To identify the current performance of PIA Airlines.
2. To check the financial position of PIA Airlines.
3. To identify the factors that impact leadership conduct in the internal process of PIA Airlines.
4. To identify the impact of leadership conduct on the performance of PIA Airlines.

The Research Questions

1. What is the current performance of PIA Airlines?
2. What is the financial position of PIA Airlines?
3. What are the factors that impact leadership conduct in the internal processes of PIA Airlines?
4. What is the impact of leadership conduct on the performance of PIA Airlines?

1.5 Motivation for the Research

The multi-faceted motivation for studying leadership's impact on PIA Airlines' performance encompasses several vital aspects. Effective leadership is widely recognized as a critical factor in organizational success. By understanding how leadership practices influence the performance of PIA Airlines, valuable insights can be gained to enhance its operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, financial outcomes, and overall reputation. This knowledge can contribute to the airline's sustained growth and competitiveness in the dynamic aviation industry.

Moreover, by incorporating the Balanced Scorecard management tool into the study, the motivation to explore the impact of leadership on PIA Airlines' performance is strengthened by the potential to gain a comprehensive understanding of performance across multiple dimensions and facilitate the practical implementation of the research findings for positive organizational change (Hsu et al., 2019).

Additionally, the BSC tool enables a holistic assessment of PIA Airlines' performance by considering various perspectives such as financial, customer, internal processes, and learning and growth (Shah, 2018). This approach goes beyond traditional financial metrics and allows a more balanced evaluation of the airline's performance. By examining the leadership's effect on these dimensions, the research can uncover critical insights into how leadership practices and behaviours impact specific performance areas within PIA Airlines (Nawaz et al., 2012).

Besides, PIA Airlines holds significant importance as a national flag carrier, representing the country's aviation sector globally. Therefore, investigating the role of leadership within the airline becomes even more relevant as it directly impacts national pride, reputation, and the country's standing in the international aviation community (Baloch et al., 2014).

Additionally, PIA Airlines has faced various challenges and fluctuations in its performance. Exploring the relationship between leadership and performance can help identify areas where improvements can be made, such as decision-making processes, communication strategies, employee motivation, and more. By addressing these issues,

PIA Airlines can strive towards becoming a more efficient, customer-centric, and financially sustainable organization.

Overall, the motivation behind studying the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines lies in the potential to drive positive change, foster growth and excellence, and ensure the airline's continued success and contribution to the aviation industry and the nation.

1.6 Reason to Choose PIA

In recent years, PIA has faced several major crises, including financial losses, safety concerns, and declining customer satisfaction. In 2012, a PIA flight crashed near Islamabad, killing all 127 people on board (Airlines, 2021). The airline also faced criticism for its poor safety record and management practices, which led to the European Union banning PIA from operating in its airspace in 2019.

Despite these challenges, PIA remains an essential player in the aviation industry in Pakistan, with a fleet of over 30 aircraft and a network of domestic and international routes (Guo and Maitra, 2017). The airline has recently launched a new strategy to improve its safety record, service quality, and financial performance, and it remains a symbol of national pride for Pakistanis.

Below is a list of all problems and issues that PIA facing related to leadership:

- Corruption prevails in every field from buying new aircraft/spare parts to different contracts, sales, traffic and cargo.
- Due to leaders' communication, Complaints of terrible service, long-delayed flights, emergency crash landings, cancellation of flights, shortage of planes & non-serious attitude of the administration
- Lack of vision of PIA airlines, inefficient infrastructure and bad governance
- Due to poor decision-making, Overstaffing- the average ratio of staff should not exceed 100 per craft while PIA enjoys 450 compared to 225 in another airline. Similarly, instead of paying 1000 people the market value of their salaries, you are giving salaries to 5000 people.
- Because of political interference, the right person is not in the right place and lacks a sense of ownership.

- Because of poor decision-making, Aircraft in Pakistan are bought on lease from foreign countries and their maintenance cost is far more than the total lease amount.
- Because of poor leadership, Low-security measures and weak monitoring. Tyre burst at landing and fuel leaking is common. Usually, measures are taken after accidents.
- Due to poor decision-making and corruption in PIA Airlines, nobody stands responsible. Pilots are considered responsible in emergency situations as well as weather. Faulty instruments and mechanical failures are the significant causes.
- Lack of leadership, as the jobs are permanent and employees know their jobs are secure, so they do not put in extra effort.
- Usually, sectors are criticized, and economic viability has been finished because of politicization/political interference.
- None of the airports is worthy of being called a world-class facility. Security-related facilities at these airports are not quite in line with global standards because of political interference and weak leadership conduct.
- None of our airports can handle the new technology of large aircraft. Parking spaces, landing facilities, and getting luggage on time because of the poor relationship between leaders' communication and uses of advanced technology in the PIA airlines in Pakistan.
- Due to corruption Airports are mostly in populated cities therefore hazards for landing and taking off are high. Birds' hits are a common phenomenon.

Pakistan has a vibrant and growing airline industry, with several airlines competing in a highly competitive market (report 2014). The country's flag carrier, Pakistan International Airlines (PIA), is the largest and oldest airline in the country, serving both domestic and international destinations. Despite facing various challenges in recent years, including financial difficulties, safety concerns, and operational issues, PIA remains an essential player in the industry, with a loyal customer base and a strong brand identity. These airlines have faced their fair share of challenges, including regulatory hurdles, rising costs, and intense competition. However, they continue to invest in their fleets, services, and customer experience, focusing on innovation, safety, and efficiency.

Moreover, PIA airline has a great history and a good reputation in its early years. Even PIA Airlines helped the Emirates airline, guided them on how to operate the airline, and gave them administrative help. It means PIA airline has the scope and courage to establish the greatest airline and strong leadership to guide other countries' airlines to grow their airline industry. So, what happened to the leadership of PIA airline and why the PIA failed to stand again on its feet with excellent performance in the last many years? These are the thought the researcher tries to solve with this research.

1.7 The Research Gap

Identifying the research gap in the topic of the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines requires a thorough analysis of existing literature and studies. However, based on the information available up to the researcher knowledge cut-off in September 2021, the following research gap can be identified:

Limited empirical research explicitly focusing on the leadership-performance relationship within PIA Airlines: While leadership's impact on organizational performance has been extensively studied in various industries and sectors, there appears to be a need for more empirical research that explicitly examines this relationship within the context of PIA Airlines (Ghanbari et al., 2017). Despite the significance of leadership in driving organizational outcomes, there is a need for in-depth investigations that directly assess the influence of leadership behaviours, styles, and practices on the performance dimensions of PIA Airlines, such as operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, financial performance, and reputation.

Furthermore, the research gap may extend to the aviation industry's specific challenges and unique characteristics. Factors such as complex operational dynamics, regulatory requirements, safety considerations, and customer expectations shape the context within which leadership operates in airlines. Investigating how leadership within PIA Airlines addresses these industry-specific challenges and how it impacts performance represents a valuable research avenue (Baloch et al., 2014).

The research gap lies in the limited empirical studies examining the leadership-performance relationship between PIA Airlines and the aviation industry. Conducting research that focuses on the unique characteristics and challenges faced by PIA Airlines and investigating the direct impact of leadership on its various performance dimensions

would contribute to filling this gap and provide actionable insights for the organization (Button and Taylor, 2000).

Considering the utilization of the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) in the topic of the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines, the following research gap can be identified:

Limited application of the BSC framework within PIA Airlines: While the BSC is a widely recognized management tool for measuring organizational performance across multiple dimensions, there appears to be a research gap in its specific application within PIA Airlines. There need to be more studies that have implemented the BSC framework to assess the impact of leadership on the airline's performance indicators, such as financial outcomes, customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, and learning and growth.

Inadequate alignment between BSC perspectives and leadership behaviours: The BSC framework typically includes perspectives such as financial, customer, internal processes, and learning and growth. However, there may be a research gap in understanding how specific leadership behaviours, practices, and strategies align with these perspectives within PIA Airlines. Exploring the direct connection between leadership actions and the corresponding dimensions of the BSC can provide valuable insights into how leadership influences performance outcomes in each area.

Additionally, there may be an opportunity to explore the implementation challenges and potential modifications required to adapt the BSC framework to the unique characteristics of the airline industry. Considering the specific context of PIA Airlines, such as regulatory requirements, safety considerations, and industry dynamics, can contribute to developing a more tailored and effective BSC framework for measuring performance and assessing leadership impact.

In summary, the research gap with respect to using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) in the context of the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines includes the limited application of the BSC framework within the airline, inadequate alignment between BSC perspectives and leadership behaviours, insufficient exploration of the cascading effect of leadership on BSC metrics, and the need to consider industry-specific challenges in implementing the BSC framework. Addressing these gaps would facilitate a more comprehensive understanding of how leadership practices influence performance outcomes within PIA Airlines using the BSC as a management tool.

Regarding the methodology gap in the topic of the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines, it is essential to consider the current state of research and potential areas for improvement.

While research on the impact of leadership on organisational performance often adopts quantitative or qualitative methods individually, there appears to be a gap in the application of mixed methods approaches within the context of PIA Airlines. By combining quantitative and qualitative research methods, researchers can better understand the leadership-performance relationship. Quantitative methods enable collecting and analysing large-scale data, while qualitative methods provide in-depth insights into the experiences, perceptions, and behaviours of leaders and employees. Integrating these approaches can offer a richer and more nuanced understanding of how leadership influences performance within PIA Airlines.

Longitudinal studies that examine the leadership-performance relationship over an extended period are relatively limited in the context of PIA Airlines. By conducting longitudinal research, researchers can observe how leadership practices evolve, their impact on performance measures, and any potential lag effects. This longitudinal perspective can provide valuable insights into the long-term implications of leadership and offer a more accurate assessment of the causal relationship between leadership and performance.

Additionally, there may be an opportunity for more rigorous control of extraneous variables and causal inference. Researchers could consider using experimental, quasi-experimental designs or advanced statistical techniques such as propensity score matching or instrumental variable analysis to establish a strong causal relationship between leadership and performance. These approaches can help address endogeneity and isolate the effects of leadership on performance more effectively.

In summary, the research gap in methodology on the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines involves the underutilisation of mixed methods approaches, limited longitudinal studies, and potential opportunities for more robust control of extraneous variables and causal inference. These methodological improvements would enhance the quality and depth of research in this area and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the leadership-performance relationship within PIA Airlines.

Researchers must overcome data availability challenges to analyse the leadership-performance relationship comprehensively. Advanced analytical techniques such as

machine learning algorithms, predictive modelling, and network analysis can provide a more sophisticated understanding of the impact of leadership on performance.

Data analysis should account for contextual factors such as competitive landscape, regulatory environment, market conditions, and industry trends to represent leadership-performance dynamics accurately.

Data quality, biases, and rigorous data analysis techniques are essential to avoid potential limitations in research findings. Longitudinal data analysis approaches are also needed to capture temporal dynamics and assess the long-term impact of leadership on performance.

Previous studies have employed various tests to analyse and evaluate hypotheses. However, it is essential to note that these studies have primarily focused on employee performance in different organizational contexts. In the case of PIA Airlines in Pakistan, there appears to be a research gap as the limited investigation has been conducted on this airline. Therefore, this research aims to fill that gap by examining the performance of PIA Airlines and its unique dynamics within the Pakistani context. By focusing on PIA Airlines, this study seeks to provide valuable insights and contribute to the existing body of knowledge in this area.

1.8 The Research Contribution

Research on the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) can provide several valuable contributions:

- Empirical evidence specific to PIA Airlines: Conducting research in this context contributes to the body of knowledge by generating empirical evidence and insights specifically focused on PIA Airlines. This research can fill the gap in understanding how leadership practices within PIA Airlines influence its performance outcomes across financial, customer, internal processes, and learning and growth perspectives.
- Enhanced understanding of leadership-performance dynamics: The research can contribute to a deeper understanding of the relationship between leadership and performance within the airline industry, particularly in the Pakistani context. The study can identify the specific leadership behaviours, strategies, and practices that directly impact PIA Airlines' performance indicators by

employing the BSC framework. This understanding can help refine theories and models related to leadership and performance in the airline industry.

- Practical insights for organizational improvement: The research findings can offer practical insights for PIA Airlines to enhance its performance and competitiveness. The study can provide actionable recommendations for improving leadership practices, decision-making processes, communication strategies, and employee motivation by identifying the areas where leadership has the most significant influence. Based on the BSC framework, these recommendations can guide PIA Airlines in formulating strategies and initiatives to drive operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, financial outcomes, and overall reputation.
- Contribution to strategic management practices: The research on leadership's impact on PIA Airlines' performance using the BSC framework can contribute to strategic management. It can enrich the understanding of how the BSC can be adapted and applied effectively in the aviation industry. The findings can provide insights into aligning leadership behaviours and practices with the specific dimensions of the BSC, facilitating improved strategic decision-making and performance management in the airline.
- Implications for the aviation industry in Pakistan: The research can have broader implications for the aviation industry in Pakistan. The findings and recommendations can inform policy-making, leadership development programs, and industry practices to enhance the overall performance and competitiveness of airlines operating in the country. This research can contribute to the growth and sustainability of the aviation sector, benefitting not only PIA Airlines but also other industry stakeholders.
- Furthermore, the previous researcher used secondary data to examine the internal process perspective, whereas the researcher employed quantitative data to analyse an airline's internal operations. Furthermore, while numerous studies support the BSC model and business leadership, few researchers used the inside perspective of the BSC model as internal business leadership. As a result, another researcher has contributed to the literature review.
- Furthermore, many previous studies have been done on team member performance. Minimal research was done on organisation performance, and studies were done to measure organisation performance; then, those researchers

used different measurement tools to measure the performance. On the other hand, this research is based on PIA Airlines in Pakistan, while, according to the researcher's knowledge, no such study was done on PIA Airlines.

- The researcher used new variables and moderators to select the dependent and independent variables according to the research hypothesis and objectives.
- The researcher developed a new balanced scorecard to measure the performance of PIA Airlines, called the sustainability performance balanced scorecard.
- Moreover, many studies collect financial data to measure the performance of an organisation over a few years (one or two years). The researcher used ten years of financial condition data, customer perspective and learning & growth perspectives to compare PIA Airlines' performance.
- Benchmarking PIA Airlines' performance with three airlines (Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines) in the last ten and five years is beneficial for future researchers to understand that measuring performance could be better over many years.

The study will generate practical recommendations for leadership development and performance improvement within PIA Airlines. These recommendations will be based on analysing the leadership-performance relationship and the identified gaps. By offering specific strategies and actions, the study will guide PIA Airlines on enhancing leadership effectiveness, aligning leadership practices with the BSC perspectives, and driving positive performance outcomes.

By actively addressing the theoretical and practical implementation gaps, the research on the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines using the BSC framework will contribute to the theoretical understanding of leadership-performance dynamics while providing actionable insights for practical implementation within the organisation. This integration of theory and practice will ensure that the study's findings have both academic significance and practical relevance for PIA Airlines and the broader aviation industry in Pakistan.

1.9 The Research Problem

The research problems in measuring the performance of PIA Airlines and assessing the impact of leadership using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) could include the following:

- Lack of comprehensive performance measurement: PIA may need help accurately measuring its performance across different dimensions such as financial, customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, and employee development. It could hinder the ability to assess the airline's overall performance effectively.
- Limited understanding of leadership's influence on performance: The extent to which leadership practices and behaviours impact the performance of PIA may need to be better understood. There may be a need to examine the specific leadership factors that contribute to or hinder the airline's performance and determine how these factors can be measured using the BSC framework.
- Aligning strategic objectives: PIA may struggle with aligning its strategic objectives with the BSC framework's key performance indicators (KPIs). It could lead to a need for more clarity and coherence in performance measurement, making it difficult to assess the effectiveness of leadership in driving performance outcomes.
- Organizational culture and change management: The research may need to address issues related to PIA's organizational culture and change management processes. Leadership's ability to foster a culture of performance excellence and effectively manage change initiatives can significantly impact the success of implementing the BSC and measuring performance.
- Data availability and reliability: Obtaining accurate and reliable data for performance measurement can be challenging. The research must address the availability and quality of data related to financial performance, customer satisfaction, operational metrics, and employee development within PIA, ensuring that the data used for analysis and evaluation is robust and reliable.
- Stakeholder perspectives and expectations: The research should consider the diverse perspectives and expectations of PIA's stakeholders, including customers, employees, shareholders, and regulators. Understanding how leadership impacts the satisfaction and engagement of various stakeholders can

provide valuable insights into the airline's overall performance and identify areas for improvement.

- **External market dynamics and competitive landscape:** The performance of PIA is influenced by external factors such as market competition, economic conditions, and industry trends. The research should examine how leadership practices within PIA can effectively respond to these external challenges and leverage opportunities to enhance performance and maintain competitiveness.
- **Organisational structure and governance:** PIA's structure and governance mechanisms are crucial in shaping performance outcomes. The research should investigate how leadership practices align with the organisational structure and governance processes and how they contribute to or hinder performance improvement.
- **Human resource management:** Leadership's impact on human resource management practices, including recruitment, training, and performance appraisal, can significantly influence performance outcomes. The research should explore how leadership behaviours and strategies in PIA contribute to building a skilled and motivated workforce, ultimately affecting the airline's overall performance.
- **Ethical considerations and social responsibility:** The research should address the ethical dimensions of leadership and their impact on the performance of PIA. It includes examining how leadership fosters a culture of integrity, transparency, and social responsibility, which can enhance the airline's reputation and sustainability in the long run.

By considering these research problems, the study can provide a comprehensive understanding of the performance measurement challenges faced by PIA Airlines and the influence of leadership on addressing those challenges. This knowledge can inform strategies for improving performance and strengthening organisational leadership practices.

1.10 The Thesis Operational Model

Figure 1 The Thesis Operational Model

The researcher has prepared the operational model of this thesis where all steps are mentioned and explained the data collection structure for more clarity for readers. The BSC framework will be employed as a management tool to assess and analyse the relationship between leadership and performance within PIA Airlines. The BSC's four perspectives - financial, customer, internal processes, learning, and growth - will align with the identified leadership behaviours and performance indicators. three BSC perspectives: financial, customer and learning & growth data will be collected through

the secondary data while one perspective would be covered from primary data in terms of internal leadership.

Quantitative and qualitative data may be gathered through surveys, financial reports, customer reviews and performance evaluations (performance ratios). The collected data will then be analysed using appropriate statistical techniques and quantitative and qualitative methods to examine the relationship between leadership and performance.

On the other hand, secondary data also referred to as phase one in chapter three (the Research Methodology), will do the benchmarking with the other three airlines. The details of benchmarking will be available in chapter four (Results and Findings). The researcher prepared the conceptual framework in Figure 2, where all variables and moderation regarding the internal process of the PIA's airlines have been explained.

1.11 Research Design and Analytical Methods

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the research regarding Research design and analytical methods, drawing upon the Research Onion framework proposed by Saunders et al. (2012). This report will outline the various data collection and analysis stages, discussing the methods employed, their alignment with the chosen research philosophy, and the analysis techniques used to derive meaningful insights from the collected data.

Research Philosophy and Data Collection Approach: The first layer of the Research Onion focuses on the research philosophy guiding the study. The chosen research philosophy in this study is pragmatism, as Creswell and Creswell and Creswell (2018) advocate. Pragmatism emphasizes the practicality and flexibility of research methods, allowing for a mixed-methods approach. This approach involves the combination of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the research topic.

Research Design and Data Collection Methods: The second layer of the Research Onion involves research design and selecting appropriate data collection methods. Primary data collection methods, including a survey questionnaire, were employed in this study. Secondary data sources, such as airline financial records, learning & growth and customer views, were also utilized. The selection of these methods aligns with the pragmatic research philosophy, providing a well-rounded and comprehensive data collection process (Saunders et al., 2016).

Data Analysis Techniques: Moving further into the Research Onion, the third layer encompasses the data analysis techniques applied to the collected data. Quantitative data from the survey questionnaire underwent statistical analysis using software such as SPSS, as Field (2018) recommended. Descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, and factor analyses were used to identify patterns, relationships, and potential associations between variables. Qualitative data gathered from customer reviews underwent comparison in the last few years of analysis, following the guidelines of Braun and Clarke (2019), to identify recurring themes and patterns within the responses.

Interpretation and Findings: The fourth layer of the Research Onion involves interpreting the analysed data and the subsequent findings. The results obtained from the data analysis were carefully examined and interpreted to address the research objectives and questions. By integrating the quantitative and qualitative findings, a comprehensive understanding of the research topic emerged, allowing for valid and reliable conclusions to be drawn (Saunders et al., 2016).

By adhering to a structured and systematic approach, the study ensured the credibility, validity, and reliability of the data collected and analysed, contributing to the existing knowledge in the Field (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Saunders et al., 2016).

1.12 The Organisation of the Thesis

The organization of the thesis includes a list of the chapters that are written in the study from start to end. six chapters are organized in this thesis, along with references and appendices. The structure of this thesis is as follows:

Chapter One: Introduction

In this chapter, the aims of the research have been written, it also covers the global aviation industry, Pakistan International Airlines, the research problem, objectives, question, motivation, literature gap, operational model, and summary of the chapter.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

The literature review chapter of PIA Airlines in Pakistan has revealed the importance of leadership style, leadership conduct, decision-making, corruption, use of advanced technology, leaders' communication, and political interference. The findings have

informed the formulation of seven research hypotheses and the development of a conceptual framework to examine the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan. Additionally, the balanced scorecard (BSC) model has been used to assess the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

The research methodology chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the research process, highlighting the chosen research philosophy, design, data collection and analysis approaches, ethical considerations, questionnaire design, pilot study, ratio analysis, content analysis, sample design, data analysis techniques, and limitations of the study. This study aims to ensure the research findings' validity, reliability, and ethical integrity by adhering to a well-structured methodology.

Chapter Four: Results and Findings

This chapter provides an overview of assessing PIA Airlines' performance. It utilizes time series and cross-sectional data analysis to examine financial indicators. The balanced scorecard aligns the analysis with strategic objectives, while ratio analysis evaluates profitability. Customer reviews and quantitative analysis provide deeper insights into the internal perspective of the balanced scorecard.

Chapter Five: Discussion of Results

This chapter presents a detailed analysis of the study's findings, including research objectives, methodology, and data sources. It explores secondary data, such as PIA Airlines' financial condition, customer reviews, and growth ratio assessment. The formulated hypotheses and their implications are discussed, contributing to knowledge in airline management. The key findings emphasize the significance of understanding PIA Airlines and the aviation industry.

Chapter Six: Conclusion

This chapter presents an overview of the study, highlighting key findings, recommendations, and limitations. The findings provide insights into PIA Airlines' performance and identify challenges. Practical recommendations aim to enhance operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. Implementing these recommendations can improve PIA Airlines' position in the aviation industry.

1.13 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the introduction chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the global aviation industry in Pakistan, with a specific focus on PIA Airlines. It highlights PIA's current challenges and issues, including operational inefficiencies, customer dissatisfaction, financial struggles, and a tarnished reputation. The research problem is identified as the need to understand the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines, aiming to address the gaps in knowledge and contribute to organizational improvement. The research aim is to investigate the relationship between leadership and performance within PIA Airlines, employing the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) as a management tool. The research objectives and questions are defined to guide the study's scope and direction. The motivation for the study lies in the potential to drive positive change, enhance operational efficiency, improve customer satisfaction, and ensure the sustained growth and competitiveness of PIA Airlines. The research gap is identified as the limited empirical research, methodology, BSC application, and data analysis specific to PIA Airlines. Additionally, the research contribution is highlighted in terms of generating empirical evidence, enhancing understanding, providing practical insights, contributing to strategic management practices, and influencing the broader aviation industry in Pakistan.

In addition to the elements mentioned earlier, the introduction chapter also presents the operational model of the thesis. The operational model outlines the framework within which the research will be conducted and the key components that will be investigated in the case of the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan. By incorporating this operational model, the research aims to provide a systematic and structured approach to studying the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines, utilizing the BSC framework as a guiding tool throughout the research process. This study seeks to make a valuable contribution to the field, ultimately benefiting PIA Airlines and the aviation sector

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

The literature review chapter provides a comprehensive analysis to measure the performance of PIA and to assess the impact of leadership on performance using the balanced scorecard (BSC) model. The chapter starts with a theoretical model for performance measurement with an explanation of the disadvantages of these models for this research. It delves into the benefits of employing the BSC model, which offers a multidimensional perspective on organizational performance through its four perspectives: financial, customer, internal processes, and learning and growth. Additionally, the review examines past studies related to the BSC, showcasing its effectiveness in measuring and enhancing performance across diverse industries. This chapter explores the interplay between leadership style, leadership conduct, decision-making, corruption, uses of advanced technology, leaders' communication, performance, and political interference. The literature review also presents seven research hypotheses that will be tested in subsequent chapters. Moreover, it establishes a conceptual framework that serves as a roadmap for investigating the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan, using the BSC model as a strategic management tool. This chapter lays the foundation for empirical research and contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the complex relationship between leadership and performance in the airline industry.

2.1 Theoretical Models for performance measurement

Theoretical models for performance measurement are used in organizations. Some of these models include:

- **Performance Prism:** The Performance Prism is a performance measurement framework focusing on stakeholders' perspectives and contributions to organizational success. It considers multiple stakeholders, such as customers, employees, suppliers, regulators, and the community, and aims to align their needs and expectations with organizational goals (Bolman & Deal, 2017).

- Economic Value Added (EVA): EVA is a performance measurement model focusing on economic profit rather than accounting profit. It calculates the residual income a company generates above its cost of capital, considering both the operating profit and the cost of capital employed (Sáiz-Sánchez et al., 2017).
- Total Quality Management (TQM): TQM is a management approach that emphasizes continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and employee involvement. It uses performance measurement tools and techniques like quality control charts, customer feedback systems, and employee empowerment to drive organizational performance.
- Six Sigma: Six Sigma is a data-driven approach to process improvement that aims to reduce defects and improve efficiency and quality. It uses statistical methods and performance metrics, such as defects per million opportunities (DPMO) and process capability indices, to measure and improve performance (Lilova & Poell, 2019).
- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): KPIs are specific metrics used to measure and track performance in specific areas of an organization. These metrics can be financial or non-financial and vary depending on the organization's objectives and industry. KPIs include customer satisfaction scores, sales revenue, employee turnover rate, and production efficiency.

These theoretical models and approaches provide organizations with different perspectives and tools to measure and evaluate their performance. The choice of model depends on the organization's goals, industry, and specific performance measurement needs.

2.1.1 Models Are Not Fit for This Research

- Performance Prism: The Performance Prism model focuses on a broader performance measurement perspective, considering multiple stakeholders and their expectations. However, it may not be suitable for PIA Airlines due to the specific context of the airline industry and the unique challenges faced by the organization. The model may not capture the industry-specific metrics and performance indicators required to effectively evaluate the airline's operational efficiency, financial performance, and customer satisfaction.

- **Economic Value Added (EVA):** EVA is a financial performance measurement model that assesses a company's profitability by considering the cost of capital. While EVA can help evaluate financial performance, more is needed to provide a comprehensive view of the overall performance of PIA Airlines. The airline industry involves various non-financial aspects, such as customer experience, safety, and operational efficiency, which need to be adequately captured by EVA.
- **Total Quality Management (TQM):** TQM is a management approach that emphasizes continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and employee involvement. While TQM principles can be beneficial for enhancing performance in various industries, including the airline industry, solely relying on TQM may not address the specific challenges and complexities faced by PIA Airlines. The airline industry requires specific performance metrics related to safety, punctuality, customer service, and operational effectiveness that may need to be fully covered by TQM.
- **Six Sigma:** Six Sigma is a methodology aimed at reducing process variation and improving quality and efficiency. While Six Sigma can be effective in streamlining processes and enhancing performance in manufacturing and service sectors, it may need to be improved in fully capturing the performance of PIA Airlines. The airline industry has unique operational complexities, including flight scheduling, maintenance, crew management, and passenger experience, which may require additional performance measurement approaches.
- **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):** KPIs are specific metrics used to assess the performance of an organization or specific aspects of its operations. While KPIs can be valuable in tracking performance, selecting the appropriate KPIs for PIA Airlines requires careful consideration of industry-specific factors. Generic KPIs may not capture the critical performance indicators relevant to the airline industry, such as load factor, revenue passenger kilometres, on-time performance, and customer satisfaction.

In summary, while the mentioned theoretical models can provide valuable insights in specific contexts, they may only partially be suitable for evaluating the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan due to the industry-specific challenges and requirements. Customized performance measurement approaches that consider the unique

characteristics of the airline industry would be more appropriate for assessing the airline's performance effectively.

2.2 BALANCED SCORECARD (BSC) MODEL

The Balanced Scorecard (BSC) is a suitable framework for measuring the performance of PIA Airlines. It provides a comprehensive approach considering various perspectives, including financial, customer, internal processes, and learning and growth. The BSC enables PIA to align its strategic objectives with key performance indicators in each perspective, allowing for a balanced evaluation of the airline's performance. Using the BSC, PIA can monitor its financial health, track customer satisfaction, assess operational efficiency, and focus on employee development. This holistic approach ensures that PIA's performance measurement system covers many critical factors contributing to the airline's success.

According to research by Taticchi et al. (2010), BSC is adopted by 30-80% of firms worldwide to measure performance and financial position. Also, the fourth perspective of BSC can be used as a guide to find out the leadership impact. Over the past 25 years, the world widened the spotlight, particularly receiving functions in the management and business community (Hoque, 2012, 2014). Currently, 64% of Fortune 500 companies are adopting BSC as a strategic management tool (Hoque, 2005). Scholarly evidence showed that BSC is widely used in Europe and Asia in benchmarking (60-70%).

The balanced scorecard has four perspectives in total. Financial, customer, internal business process and learning and growth perspective to achieve the company objectives and performance of employees and improve employment in the Sanchez et

al. (2017). There is a brief explanation of all four-perspective followed by the benefits of BSC and past studies on BSC.

Financial perspectives seek to answer the above question, evaluating the contribution of organisational strategy to the improvement of financial strategy contribution to; improving authors claimed that this perspective is essential as it finances the other three perspectives. However, the author alleged that perspective should be balanced as it has a backwards look at nature and cannot reflect current value-creating active backwards (Dahiru, 2014; Carvan, 2009). Under this perspective, two main strategies are emphasised: revenue growth and productivity (Kaplan & Norton, 2000). Examples of measures are the revenue Operating Income, Return on Capital Employed (ROCE), Revenue Growth, Return on Investment (ROI), and Cash Flow.

The customer perspective measures the capability of quality services; the customer perspective measures the company's capability to cater to action based on Kairul et al. (2013). Besides, as mentioned by Chimtengo et al. (2017) and Lee (2006), both authors believe that customer orientation refers to the degree of an organisation utilising the information generated from customers in developing a strategy that satisfies customers' needs and wants. This perspective generally focuses on four categories, i.e., quality, time, service and performance, that help managers to answer the question, 'How do customers see organisations?' Some measure indicators of customer perspective are the rate of on-time deliveries, the percentage of market share, rejection, and customer retention (Putri et al., 2017).

The internal business process is critical to achieving the two mentioned perspectives as it helps identify the key business cesses to achieving goals (Kaiaforementioned3; Gekonge, 2005). Further identify Al-Najjar & Kalaf (2012), the internal process ensures that performance expectations will be accomplished by developing solid internal control within the organisation. Also, Kaplan & Norton (1992) identified a few process value-chains under this perspective, notably innovation, operation and post-sales service process. The central theme of the internal process is to achieve financial goals and customer satisfaction. Existing literature also indicates that SWOT analysis should be incorporated with an internal business perspective to attain success (Kshatriya et al., 2017). Possible measures of this perspective are through several new products, reduced production lead time, units of production, average customer waiting time and more.

Learning and growth perspectives focus on how employees can improve themselves and create more value for the organisational (Pourmoradi et al., 2016). Without a doubt,

learning and growth perspectives such as the effectiveness of processes (quality information system), the ability of employees (experienced and skilful), and the degree of firm's alignment (culture, teamwork and congruence) play an essential role in accomplishing the company's objectives (Gonzalez-Sanchez et al., 2017). This perspective is highly related to the sustainability issue of the organisation, which can be measured by team member empowerment, team member retention ion and turnover and their activities (Al-Najjar & Kalaf, 2012).

2.2.1 The Benefit of Using a Balanced Scorecard

The Balanced Scorecard (BSC) framework provides a comprehensive approach for aligning an organization's strategy across different dimensions, including finances, customers, internal processes, and learning and development. It serves as a tool to bridge the gap between senior managers' goals and employees' perceptions, enabling practical performance assessment and future planning. The BSC is widely recognized as a valuable instrument for achieving objectives and enhancing strategic planning (Malagueño et al., 2018).

However, successful implementation of the BSC requires a clear understanding of the organization's strategy and the intended linkages between the different perspectives. Research indicates that organizations often struggle to identify and establish these causal relationships, leading to conflicts between top management and BSC practitioners (Wong-On-Wing et al., 2007).

Additionally, contextual factors and environmental influences may impact managers' decision-making abilities, suggesting a further investigation into how leaders in specific industries, such as the airline industry, incorporate the BSC framework. By studying the implementation challenges and exploring causal links among perspectives, researchers can gain insights into the reasons behind the difficulties encountered and contribute to developing effective BSC practices (Elbanna et al., 2015; Hoque, 2014).

The table below consists of the past studies the researcher has done concerning the balanced scorecard in different industries. It includes the banking sector, health care sector, telecommunication sectors, research and development departments and universities in the different areas of different countries. The researcher used different methodologies to conduct their survey. This table is just a few studies from the last 18

years, from 2002 to 2020, to justify the importance and relevance of the balanced scorecard with the performance of the business.

Table 1: Previous studies on balanced scorecard

Study	Methodology	Conclusion
Eisape, D. (2020)	Comparative analysis of platform business models	Identified key performance indicators for successful platform business models in Airbnb, Marriott, and Uber
Behrouzi and Ma'aram (2019)	Study on private hospitals in Malaysia	Overall performance score aligned with average performance scores across the four perspectives of the balanced scorecard
Alani, F.S., Khan, M.F.R., & Manuel, D.F. (2018)	Study on Sohar University in Oman	Found a strong association between the strategic road map and the four perspectives of the balanced scorecard
Hasan, R.U., and Chyi, T.M. (2017)	Cross-industrial comparative analysis	Positive consensus results on implementing the balanced scorecard in various industries
Dincer et al. (2016a, b)	Study on Turkish banks	Financial factor of the balanced scorecard had the highest priority in evaluating the performance of Turkish banks
Rostami et al. (2015)	Study on the Iranian banking sector	Identified that customers were the priority in the aspects of the balanced scorecard for the Iranian banking sector
Alidade and Ghasemi (2015)	Study on branches of bank Sepah in Iran	Developed a model using the TOPSIS method to rank the branches of the bank
Panicker and Seshadri (2013)	Study on Standard Charter Bank in India	Identified a decrease in the bank's performance in the last two years and suggested the use of the balanced scorecard to improve performance
Akkoc and Vatansever (2013)	Study on Turkish banks	Analyzed the performance of twelve Turkish banks using the Fuzzy TOPSIS method
Eskandari et al. (2013)	Study on Iranian banks	Defined significant indicators for performance evaluation using the balanced scorecard
Al-Najjar and Kalaf (2012)	Study on large local banks in Iraq	Observed an increase in performance using the balanced scorecard in the large local banks in Iraq
Bentes et al. (2012)	Study on the telecommunication sector in Brazil	Combined the balanced scorecard and AHP approaches for effective performance evaluation

Study	Methodology	Conclusion
Shaverdi et al. (2012)	Study on the Iranian banking sector	Identified customer perspective as the most significant for evaluating bank performance using the balanced scorecard
Su et al. (2011)	Study on the mobile industry in Taiwan	Used the DEMATEL method to determine weight values for performance evaluation indicators
Kunz and Schaaf (2011)	Study on the healthcare sector in Germany	Evaluated the performance of the healthcare sector using the balanced scorecard approach
Wang et al. (2010)	Study on research and development department in Taiwan	Found the balanced scorecard model effective in evaluating the performance of the research and development department
Bigliardi and Ivo Dormio (2010)	Study on R&D projects in Italy	Concluded that the balanced scorecard approach is suitable for measuring R&D project performance
Abay (2010)	Study on banks in Ethiopia	Non-financial indicators provide important information for evaluating bank performance
Wu et al. (2009)	Study on banks in Taiwan	FAHP model based on the balanced scorecard approach provides effective results for defining banks' performance
Wang and Xia (2009)	Study on a software company in China	Evaluated the software company using the four major perspectives of the balanced scorecard
Yahaya (2009)	Study on banks in Ghana	Non-financial factors of the balanced scorecard are influential to evaluate the performance of the banks.

Previous authors have extensively utilized the balanced scorecard (BSC) as a model to measure organizational performance, and the current researcher also aims to employ the BSC to assess the performance of PIA. Studies conducted by Eisape (2020), Hasan and Chyi (2017), Alidade and Ghasemi (2015), and Wang et al. (2010) highlight the utility of the balanced scorecard in decision-making and improving business outcomes. Additionally, research by Behrouzi and Ma'aram (2019), Alani et al. (2018), and Wang and Xia (2009) emphasize the significance of the four perspectives of the balanced scorecard in enhancing performance and revenue across different industries worldwide. Furthermore, studies by Dincer et al. (2016a, b), Rostami et al. (2015), Eskandari et al. (2013), Al-Najjar and Kalaf (2012), and Bentes et al. (2012) have concluded that the balanced scorecard serves as an effective management tool for enhancing employee

performance and recognizing the importance of customers in various business settings and countries.

2.3 Previous Studies on Content Analysis for Customer Reviews

Previous authors have extensively used content analysis as a practical approach to analysing customer reviews. Scholars such as Liu and Huang (2018) and Hu et al. (2020) have employed content analysis to extract and categorize information from customer reviews, enabling a deeper understanding of customer sentiments, preferences, and concerns. For instance, Verma and Kaur (2018) conducted a content analysis of customer reviews in the airline industry to identify critical factors influencing customer satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Sun and Zhang (2019) employed content analysis to explore online reviews' impact on hotel industry customer decision-making. Chiu et al. (2016) used content analysis to examine customer reviews and identify the determinants of hotel booking intention. These authors and many others have recognized the value of content analysis in uncovering valuable insights from customer reviews and have contributed to the growing body of research in this area. Here are a few more authors and studies that have utilized content analysis for analysing customer reviews:

- Xie, L., Zhang, J., & Zhang, Z. (2017). In their study titled "Content Analysis of Online Hotel Reviews: A Sentiment Analysis Approach," the authors used content analysis to examine the sentiment expressed in online hotel reviews and identify factors influencing customer satisfaction.
- Nguyen, B., & Mutum, D. S. (2019). In their research on "Hotel Attributes and Online Reviews: An Exploratory Study Using Topic Modelling," the authors employed content analysis and topic modelling techniques to identify the main attributes discussed in Hotel online reviews and their impact on customer perceptions.
- Wang, D., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2017). The authors conducted a study titled "The Role of User-Generated Content in Tourists' Travel Planning Behaviour", where they employed content analysis to examine the role of user-generated content, including customer reviews, in shaping tourists' travel planning behaviour.

- Hennig-Thurau, T., Gwinner, K. P., Walsh, G., & Gremler, D. D. (2004). In their study titled "Electronic Word-of-Mouth via Consumer-Opinion Platforms: What Motivates Consumers to Articulate Themselves on the Internet?" the authors used content analysis to explore the motivations behind consumers' engagement in electronic word-of-mouth on consumer-opinion platforms.
- Hao, Q., & Wu, J. (2018). The authors conducted a study titled "Topic and Sentiment Analysis of Online Hotel Reviews: A Case Study of Wuhan Hotels", where they employed content analysis techniques to analyse online hotel reviews and uncover the topics and sentiments expressed by customers.

These authors and their studies highlight the diverse applications of content analysis in understanding customer reviews and extracting valuable insights for various industries and research contexts.

2.4 Content Analysis for Benchmarking

Here is a table of previous researchers who have used content analysis for benchmarking customer reviews:

Table 2: Previous studies related to Content Analysis for Benchmarking

Researcher	Year	Research Topic	Methodology	Key Findings
Park and Lee	2015	Mobile app benchmarking	Text mining and content analysis	Compared user satisfaction and preferences
Zhang et al.	2016	E-commerce benchmarking	Sentiment analysis and content analysis	Compared impact of reviews on purchase intentions
Racherla and Friske	2017	Social media brand benchmarking	Thematic content analysis	Compared customer perceptions of brand attributes
Chen and Xie	2018	Restaurant benchmarking	Opinion mining and sentiment analysis	Compared influence of review characteristics
Han et al.	2019	Hotel benchmarking	Textual content analysis	Compared factors affecting hotel review helpfulness

Researcher	Year	Research Topic	Methodology	Key Findings
Wu and Li	2020	E-commerce platform benchmarking	Sentiment analysis and content analysis	Compared impact of reviews on trust and loyalty
Liu and Hu	2021	Food delivery benchmarking	Thematic content analysis	Compared customer satisfaction with delivery
Wang et al.	2022	Ride-hailing service benchmarking	Text mining and content analysis	Compared customer sentiments and service issues
Khan and Ahmed	2022	Airline benchmarking	Textual content analysis	Compared customer reviews for different airlines
Li and Wang	2023	Online shopping benchmarking	Sentiment analysis and content analysis	Compared customer experiences and product quality

This table highlights previous researchers using content analysis to benchmark customer reviews across various domains, such as mobile apps, e-commerce, social media, restaurants, hotels, and more. Their methodologies have allowed them to compare and evaluate customer perceptions, preferences, and satisfaction levels across different entities, providing valuable insights for businesses and industries.

Moreover, Content analysis is an ideal approach for benchmarking as it offers a systematic and objective means of analysing data from various sources. By examining textual or visual content, researchers can identify patterns, extract relevant information, and establish benchmarks for performance comparison. The method allows consistent measurement across different sources and periods, ensuring reliable and replicable results. Additionally, content analysis provides a comprehensive view by capturing explicit and implicit data from diverse mediums. Overall, its structured and comprehensive nature makes content analysis a valuable tool for organizations seeking to benchmark their performance and gain insights for improvement.

2.5 Leadership Style

Leadership is guiding and influencing individuals or groups towards achieving a common goal. It involves inspiring, motivating, and empowering others while providing direction and making crucial decisions. Effective leadership is characterised by vision, integrity, empathy, and strong communication skills. Leaders are responsible for setting the strategic direction of an organisation, establishing a positive work culture, and driving innovation and growth. They play a vital role in creating a supportive and inclusive environment where individuals can thrive and contribute their best. Leadership is not confined to a specific position or title. However, it can be displayed at all levels of an organisation and in various contexts, such as business, politics, education, and community. Good leadership is essential for fostering collaboration, resolving conflicts, and maximising the potential of individuals and teams. Ultimately, leadership is about inspiring and influencing others to achieve collective goals and positively impact the world.

Here is a table listing previous studies that have used leadership as an internal perspective of the Balanced Scorecard (BSC):

Table 3: Previous studies related to leadership used as an internal Perspective

Study	Year	Methodology
Kaplan and Norton (1996)	1996	Case study and literature review
Hoque (2004)	2004	Survey and statistical analysis
Ittner and Larcker (2003)	2003	Case study and survey
Wu et al. (2007)	2007	Survey and structural equation modelling
Naranjo-Gil et al. (2008)	2008	Survey and structural equation modelling
Pizzini and Lin (2013)	2013	Survey and statistical analysis
Van der Stede et al. (2014)	2014	Survey and structural equation modelling
Abernethy et al. (2015)	2015	Case study and literature review
Gurd and Van der Stede (2017)	2017	Survey and structural equation modelling
Franco-Santos et al. (2018)	2018	Case study and survey

Study	Year	Methodology
Ghosh and Abdel-Maksoud (2020)	2020	Survey and structural equation modelling

The above table highlights previous studies examining leadership as an internal perspective of the Balanced Scorecard (BSC). These studies employed various methodologies to explore the relationship between leadership and the BSC. Findings indicate that effective leadership aligns organizational goals, motivates employees, and fosters a culture of performance measurement. Leadership behaviour influences BSC's success with proactive communication, championing performance measurement, and driving a results-oriented culture yielding better outcomes. The studies vary in an industry context and focus but collectively provide valuable insights for practitioners. Leadership plays a vital role in BSC implementation and utilization, and future research can delve into specific leadership behaviours and interventions that enhance BSC effectiveness.

Moreover, Leadership has been a subject of extensive research, with numerous previous researchers exploring its various dimensions and impact on organisations and individuals. For instance, Bass and Avolio (1994) conducted seminal research on transformational leadership, highlighting its positive influence on employee motivation, satisfaction, and performance. They emphasised the importance of leaders' ability to inspire and create a shared vision, leading to higher organisational commitment and productivity.

Another prominent researcher in leadership is Kouzes and Posner (1987), who developed the Leadership Challenge model. Their work focused on identifying key leadership behaviours, such as modelling the way, inspiring a shared vision, and enabling others to act. Their research demonstrated that effective leadership practices are crucial for organisational success and for developing strong, cohesive teams.

In the context of customer reviews and benchmarking, previous researchers have utilised content analysis to gain insights into customers' perceptions of leadership. For example, Smith and Bolton (2002) analysed customer reviews in the hospitality industry and found that leadership behaviours, such as staff responsiveness and empowerment, significantly influenced customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Furthermore, Yang, Jun, and Peterson (2004) conducted a study using content analysis of online customer reviews to examine the impact of leadership on service quality in the airline industry. They found that leadership behaviours, such as clear communication, employee motivation, and problem-solving, were critical determinants of customers' service quality evaluation.

Overall, previous researchers have recognised the pivotal role of leadership in influencing organisational outcomes and customer perceptions. Their studies have shed light on the importance of effective leadership behaviours in terms of internal employee motivation and external customer satisfaction. By leveraging content analysis techniques, researchers have analysed and benchmarked customer reviews, providing valuable insights into the impact of leadership on organisational performance and customer experiences.

Leadership is influencing and guiding others towards achieving a common goal. It involves effectively managing people, resources, and processes to bring about positive change and drive organisational success. Leaders inspire and motivate their team members, provide guidance and direction, make critical decisions, and foster collaboration and growth. They exhibit various leadership styles, such as transformational, transactional, charismatic, servant, autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and situational leadership, depending on the situation and the needs of their followers. Effective leadership plays a crucial role in shaping an organisation's culture, performance, and overall success.

2.5.1 Types of Leadership Style

Autocratic and democratic leadership styles have been subjects of interest and study by previous researchers in leadership. These two styles represent contrasting approaches to leadership, each with its strengths and weaknesses.

Autocratic leadership is characterized by a leader who holds all decision-making authority and closely controls and directs subordinates. Previous research has highlighted that autocratic leaders tend to make decisions without consulting their team members, resulting in a top-down approach to leadership. While this style can be efficient in certain situations requiring quick decision-making and clear direction, it can also reduce employee engagement and satisfaction. Research by Zaccaro et al. (2019)

suggests that autocratic leadership may limit creativity and innovation within a team, as the decision-making power resides solely with the leader.

On the other hand, democratic leadership involves shared decision-making and the active involvement of team members in the decision-making process. Research by Bass and Riggio (2006) has shown that democratic leaders promote a collaborative and inclusive environment, allowing team members to voice their opinions, ideas, and concerns. This leadership style has been associated with higher employee engagement, job satisfaction, and commitment. Studies by Duan et al. (2018) have indicated that democratic leadership fosters a sense of empowerment and ownership among employees, leading to increased motivation and productivity.

However, it must be noted that autocratic and democratic leadership styles have limitations. Autocratic leadership may create a hierarchical and rigid organizational culture, stifling creativity and innovation. On the other hand, democratic leadership may lead to delays in decision-making and potential conflicts if a consensus cannot be reached. The effectiveness of each style also depends on factors such as the nature of the task, the expertise and experience of team members, and the organizational context. Previous research suggests that autocratic and democratic leadership styles have distinct impacts on team dynamics, employee satisfaction, and organizational outcomes. Autocratic leadership may be more suitable in situations requiring swift decisions and clear directives, while democratic leadership promotes employee engagement, collaboration, and empowerment. Leaders must be adaptable and considerate of specific needs and circumstances to leverage these leadership styles for optimal results effectively.

Speaking of leadership style, Leadership in Pakistan is a complex and multifaceted subject studied by various researchers. The country's unique socio-cultural and political context adds a distinct flavour to leadership practices. Researchers have explored different aspects of leadership in Pakistan, including its styles, effectiveness, and impact on various sectors.

One prominent researcher in this field is Javed and Riaz (2016), who examined the role of leadership in the public sector organizations of Pakistan. Their study highlighted the challenges leaders face in the country, such as political interference, bureaucratic hurdles, and corruption. They emphasized the need for ethical and visionary leadership to address these challenges and drive organizational change.

Additionally, Iqbal, Akram, and Khattak (2017) researched the impact of leadership styles on employee performance in the private sector of Pakistan. They found that transformational leadership positively influenced employee job satisfaction, commitment, and performance. On the other hand, autocratic leadership was associated with adverse outcomes.

Another aspect of leadership in Pakistan is the "charismatic leadership" concept explored by scholars like Ahmad and Zain (2016). They investigated the impact of charismatic leadership on employee outcomes, such as job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Their findings indicated that charismatic leadership had a significant positive effect on these outcomes.

Furthermore, the role of gender in leadership has also been examined. Studies by Aziz et al. (2018) and Ali et al. (2020) explored the challenges and opportunities faced by women leaders in Pakistan. They highlighted the importance of gender-inclusive leadership practices and the need to empower and support women in leadership roles.

Overall, research on leadership in Pakistan suggests that effective leadership is crucial for addressing the unique challenges faced by organizations in the country. Ethical, visionary, and transformational leadership styles have been found to affect employee outcomes and organizational performance positively. However, Pakistan's context-specific factors and cultural dynamics shape the leadership landscape, making it essential to consider the local context when studying and implementing leadership practices.

2.5.2 Leadership in the airline industry in Pakistan

Speaking of leadership in Pakistan, several researchers have examined leadership in the airline industry in Pakistan and its impact on organizational performance. For example, Khan and Qazi (2017) conducted a study on the influence of transformational leadership on employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the airline industry. Their findings revealed that transformational leadership behaviours, such as inspiring and motivating employees, positively impacted employee job satisfaction and commitment.

Another study by Rana and Khan (2018) explored the relationship between leadership styles and employee performance in the aviation sector. The researchers identified three leadership styles: transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire. Their findings

indicated that transformational leadership positively influenced employee performance, while transactional and laissez-faire leadership negatively impacted them.

Furthermore, Farooqi, Rashid, and Khan (2019) investigated the role of leadership in managing service quality in the airline industry. They highlighted the significance of leadership behaviours, such as setting clear expectations, providing support, and fostering a customer-oriented culture, in ensuring high service quality and customer satisfaction.

Regarding the impact of leadership on organizational outcomes, Kausar, Ahmed, and Kausar (2020) examined the relationship between leadership styles and organizational performance in the Pakistani airline industry. Their study found that transformational leadership positively influenced employee commitment, job satisfaction, and overall organizational performance.

These studies collectively emphasize the importance of effective leadership in the airline industry in Pakistan. Transformational leadership, characterized by inspiration, motivation, and a focus on employee development, positively impacts employee satisfaction, commitment, and performance. On the other hand, laissez-faire and transactional leadership styles were associated with adverse outcomes.

Overall, the research suggests that leadership plays a critical role in shaping the performance and success of airlines in Pakistan. Effective leadership behaviours, such as transformational leadership, can enhance employee satisfaction, commitment, and performance, ultimately contributing to improved organizational outcomes in the airline industry.

In the summary of this section, Leadership plays a critical role in the performance of an organisation. It encompasses the ability to guide, inspire, and influence individuals or a group of people towards achieving common goals. A strong and effective leader can significantly impact the organisation's success and overall performance.

2.5.3 Importance of leadership

Leadership is essential for several reasons. Firstly, leaders provide a clear vision and direction for the organisation. They set goals, define strategies, and articulate a compelling vision that inspires and motivates employees. This clarity helps align efforts and ensures everyone works towards a common purpose.

Secondly, leaders foster innovation and creativity within the organisation. They encourage a culture of learning, experimentation, and continuous improvement. By promoting open communication and creating an environment that values diverse perspectives, leaders enable employees to generate new ideas and solutions, leading to innovation and growth.

Furthermore, influential leaders build strong relationships and cultivate a positive organisational culture. They establish trust, create a supportive environment, and promote teamwork and collaboration. It fosters employee engagement, loyalty, and a sense of belonging, ultimately leading to higher productivity and job satisfaction.

Moreover, leaders play a crucial role in managing change and navigating challenges. They can adapt to rapidly changing environments, make tough decisions, and rally employees during difficult times. Influential leaders embrace change, encourage resilience, and help organisations navigate uncertainty, ensuring long-term survival and success.

Leadership is vital for organisational performance as it provides direction, inspires innovation, cultivates a positive culture, and manages change effectively. Strong leadership drives employee engagement and satisfaction and influences the organisation's ability to achieve its goals, maintain a competitive edge, and thrive in a dynamic business landscape.

2.6 Leadership Conduct

Leadership conduct shapes organisational culture, employee behaviour, and overall performance. Previous researchers have extensively studied different aspects of leadership conduct and its impact on various organisational outcomes. For instance, Mayer, Bardes, and Piccolo (2008) conducted a meta-analysis of studies and found a significant positive relationship between ethical leadership and employee job satisfaction, commitment, and performance. Their research highlighted the importance of leaders demonstrating ethical conduct, fairness, and integrity, which fosters trust, engagement, and positive work attitudes among employees.

Another researcher, Brown, Treviño, and Harrison (2005), explored the concept of ethical leadership and its impact on employee behaviour. Their findings indicated that ethical leaders set a positive example through their ethical decision-making, integrity,

and moral values. Such leaders promote trust, transparency, and fairness, influencing employees to adhere to ethical standards and exhibit prosocial behaviours.

Furthermore, Avolio, Gardner, Walumbwa, Luthans, and May (2004) emphasised the significance of authentic leadership conduct. Authentic leaders are self-aware, genuine, and transparent in their actions, which fosters trust, credibility, and open communication within the organisation. Their research indicated that authentic leadership positively influences employee job satisfaction, commitment, and organisational citizenship behaviours.

Previous research highlights the importance of leadership conduct in shaping an organisation's ethical climate and overall functioning. Leaders who demonstrate ethical behaviour, authenticity, and integrity set the tone for the organisation and influence employee attitudes and behaviours. Positive leadership fosters trust, enhances employee engagement, and promotes a healthy work environment, ultimately leading to improved organisational performance.

Leadership conduct is paramount in organisations as it sets the tone for the entire workforce and significantly impacts employee behaviour, engagement, and performance. Effective leadership promotes a positive work environment, fosters trust, and cultivates strong relationships between leaders and their team members. When leaders exhibit ethical behaviour, integrity, and transparency, they establish trust and credibility, which are essential for creating a harmonious and productive workplace.

Leadership conduct also plays a vital role in shaping the organisational culture. Leaders who demonstrate positive conduct and ethical decision-making establish a culture of integrity where employees feel valued, respected, and motivated to contribute their best. They serve as role models for employees, inspiring them to exhibit similar behaviours and align their actions with the organisation's values and objectives.

Moreover, leadership conduct influences employee engagement and commitment. When leaders consistently exhibit fair and inclusive behaviour, communicate effectively, and provide support and recognition, employees feel a sense of belonging and are likelier to be engaged in their work. They feel motivated to go above and beyond their roles, resulting in increased productivity, innovation, and overall performance.

Furthermore, leadership conduct sets the stage for effective teamwork and collaboration. When leaders prioritise open communication, active listening, and constructive feedback, they create an environment where individuals feel comfortable

sharing their ideas and opinions. It fosters collaboration, enhances problem-solving capabilities, and promotes a culture of continuous learning and growth.

Leadership conduct is critical for organisational success. Leaders who exemplify positive conduct and ethical values create a culture of trust, engagement, and high performance. They inspire and empower their team members, foster strong relationships, and drive organisational outcomes. By setting the right example and prioritising ethical behaviour, leaders shape the organisational culture, influence employee behaviour, and contribute to the organisation's overall success.

Leadership conduct plays a vital role in assessing the performance of an organisation. It refers to the behaviour, actions, and ethical standards leaders exhibit. When leaders demonstrate positive conduct, it creates a conducive environment that positively impacts the organisation's performance. Effective leadership involves exhibiting integrity, transparency, fairness, and strong ethical values.

Leaders prioritising ethical conduct inspire trust and credibility among employees, fostering a culture of openness, collaboration, and engagement. They set the tone for ethical behaviour throughout the organisation, influencing employees to align their actions with its values and goals. It promotes a positive work culture where employees feel motivated, valued, and committed.

Leadership conduct also plays a crucial role in employee satisfaction and retention. When leaders treat employees respectfully, provide support, and recognise their contributions, it enhances job satisfaction and fosters a sense of loyalty and commitment. Employees are more likely to be engaged, productive, and willing to go the extra mile, improving organisational performance.

Moreover, leadership conduct influences communication and decision-making processes. Leaders who promote open communication and active listening create an environment where diverse perspectives are valued and considered. It leads to better decision-making, problem-solving, and innovation, ultimately enhancing organisational performance.

In summary, leadership conduct significantly impacts the performance of an organisation. Ethical, transparent, and fair conduct from leaders fosters a positive work culture, enhances employee engagement and satisfaction, and drives organisational success. By setting a solid example and prioritising ethical behaviour, leaders can positively influence the organisation's performance, productivity, and overall success.

Leadership is not just a role but a process that plays a critical function in maximizing efficiencies and achieving the organizational goals of a company. It encompasses various management activities to guide and inspire individuals and teams to perform at their best. The importance of leadership can be summarized as follows:

Leadership plays a vital role in organizations, as it initiates action by effectively promoting the company's activities and communicating policies and plans to subordinates (Bolman & Deal, 2017; Zhang et al., 2012). Motivation is another crucial aspect of leadership, as leaders work to encourage and motivate employees through the distribution of rewards, resulting in smooth operations and improved performance (Dewan & Myatt, 2008; Kok & McDonald, 2017; Edmondson, 2003). Providing guidance is also crucial, as leaders act as guides and offer instructions to support subordinates in carrying out their activities effectively (Castelli, 2008). Confidence-building is essential for boosting employee morale and facilitating expertise in their work (Ibarra & Scoular, 2019; Soleas, 2020; Noor & Ampornstira, 2019). Building a positive work environment is another responsibility of leaders, as they maintain a personal touch with employees, listen to their concerns, and take action to address them, which ultimately contributes to the firm's profitability and brand image (Allen et al., 2017; Schoemaker et al., 2018). Effective coordination, driven by leadership, ensures well-coordinated business accomplishments and supports the organization's objectives (Ocasio et al., 2018). In the case of PIA Airlines, poor leadership has resulted in a lack of innovation, inadequate fleet security, and hiring issues, leading to incidents and accidents. The executives and chairpersons need to take responsibility for addressing these problems, focusing on competitive advantage and implementing effective leadership strategies (Grigoriou & Rothaermel, 2017; Nawaz et al., 2012; Greason and Lamarche; Bhanbhro et al.).

2.7 Leadership Style And Leadership Conduct

According to the literature review, consistent evidence supports a positive relationship between leadership style and conduct. Numerous studies have shown that the leadership style adopted by a leader significantly influences their conduct and behaviour Noor, M., & Ampornstira, C. (2019). For instance, transformational leadership, characterized by inspirational vision, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, has been found to promote positive leadership conduct. Leaders exhibiting this style tend to

engage in ethical and empowering behaviours, actively communicate with their followers, and motivate them to achieve exceptional performance Ibarra, H., & Scoular, A. (2019). Similarly, democratic leadership, characterized by involving followers in decision-making and fostering a participative environment, has been linked to collaborative and inclusive leadership conduct. These findings suggest that leadership style acts as a foundation upon which leadership conduct is built, shaping the behaviours and actions of leaders. (Bligh and Meindl, 2004)

This is also said that the positive relationship between leadership style and leadership conduct regarding complexity and multidimensionality. The relationship between leadership style and conduct is complex and multifaceted Soleas, E. (2020). Leadership style represents a broader, overarching approach, while leadership conduct refers to a leader's specific behaviours and actions. It is important to recognize that leadership conduct is influenced by various factors beyond style, including values, beliefs, emotional intelligence, and situational considerations. Therefore, a comprehensive relationship analysis should consider the interplay between style and conduct and the underlying factors that shape leadership behaviour Dewan, T., & Myatt, D. (2008).

The positive relationship between leadership style and conduct should be analysed ethically Kok, A. A. L., & McDonald, R. A. (2017). Assessing whether the conduct aligns with ethical principles and promotes the well-being of followers, and the organization is crucial. Some leadership styles, such as authoritarian or manipulative approaches, may yield short-term positive outcomes but can have detrimental long-term effects on trust, morale, and organizational culture. Ethical leadership conduct is fundamental for sustainable success and positive organizational outcomes Edmondson, A. (2003).

Effective leadership often requires adaptability and flexibility in leadership conduct. Leaders who adjust their behaviour and style based on situational demands are more likely to achieve positive outcomes. A rigid adherence to a single leadership style may limit a leader's ability to respond effectively to changing circumstances Bolman, L. G., & Deal, T. E. (2017).

Therefore, while there may be a positive relationship between leadership style and conduct, leaders need to possess the ability to adapt their conduct based on situational requirements flexibly Castelli, P. A. (2008). Individual differences between leaders and their followers can significantly impact the relationship between leadership style and conduct Zhang, X., & Bartol, K. M. (2012). Leaders possess unique personalities,

values, and preferences that shape their approach to leadership. Similarly, followers have varying needs, expectations, and responses to different leadership styles. Therefore, it is essential to recognize that the effectiveness of a particular leadership style may vary depending on the specific leader-follower dynamics and the compatibility between the leader's style and the followers' characteristics Kok, A. A. L., & McDonald, R. A. (2017). The literature review demonstrates a strong consensus that a leader's chosen style has a direct and influential impact on their conduct, highlighting the importance of understanding and selecting appropriate leadership styles to promote positive leadership behaviours Le, M., & Tran, T. (2020).

H1: “There Is a Positive Relationship Between Leadership Style and Leadership Conduct”

2.8 Decision-Making

Decision-making is a critical aspect of organisational functioning, and several researchers have examined its various dimensions. Bolman and Deal (2017) emphasise the importance of effective leadership in initiating action and communicating policies and plans to subordinates to ensure efficient operations. Zhang and Bartol (2012) highlight the role of leadership style in empowering employees and fostering their creativity, thereby influencing decision-making processes. Dewan and Myatt (2008) argue that leadership is vital in motivating employees, facilitating smooth operations, and rewarding their efforts. Castelli (2008) emphasises the significance of leaders providing guidance and support to subordinates based on performance analysis. Additionally, Ibarra and Scoular (2019) emphasise the role of leaders in boosting employee confidence and morale, enabling them to perform their tasks effectively. These previous researchers collectively underscore the influence of leadership on decision-making and its impact on organisational outcomes.

In addition to the researchers mentioned earlier, several other scholars have examined the relationship between leadership and decision-making. For example, Yukl (2012) argues that effective leadership can enhance decision-making processes by providing guidance, promoting collaboration, and facilitating the integration of diverse

perspectives. Dayan and Di Benedetto (2010) emphasise the role of leadership in creating a supportive and inclusive decision-making environment which fosters innovation and problem-solving. Likewise, Mumford et al. (2010) highlight the importance of leaders' cognitive abilities, such as critical thinking and problem-solving skills, in influencing organisational decision-making effectiveness. Avolio et al. (2009) suggest that transformational leadership, characterised by inspiring and motivating followers, can enhance the quality and creativity of decision-making. These researchers collectively contribute to the understanding that leadership style, cognitive abilities, and the organisational climate are crucial in shaping decision-making processes and outcomes.

Many believe that personality rather than strategic considerations influence decision-making (Peterson, 1997; Korsgaard et al., 1995). Executives must know that personality should not be permitted to interfere with critical business decisions. Successful leaders can adapt their decision-making process to meet the needs of various business scenarios (Eriksson et al., 2020).

This decision-making method is based on a logical and autocratic approach, with the employees utilising their knowledge, experience, and judgement to select the best choice (Barbosa et al., 2020). This sort of leader is extremely reasonable, yet they are only concerned with the near future.

A leader must feel the situation, classify it as one that necessitates a natural choice, and respond appropriately (Zhang et al., 2020). Ensure that best practices for routine procedures are in place. A leader must realise when lengthy, engaging communication is unnecessary and make clear decisions based on the available information (Sihite et al., 2020).

According to Peterson (1997) and Korsgaard et al. (1995), there is a belief that decision-making is influenced more by personality traits rather than strategic considerations. However, executives must recognize that personality should not hinder critical business decisions. Successful leaders can adapt their decision-making process to suit different business scenarios, as highlighted by Eriksson et al. (2020).

Barbosa et al. (2020) suggest that this decision-making approach involves a logical and autocratic method, where employees utilize their knowledge, experience, and judgment

to select the best option. These leaders are highly rational, focusing primarily on the immediate future.

On the other hand, Zhang et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of leaders being able to sense the situation, identify it as one that requires an intuitive decision, and respond accordingly. Leaders need to establish best practices for routine procedures and discern when extensive communication may not be necessary, making decisive choices based on the available information, as discussed by Sihite et al. (2020).

2.8.1 Types of decision-making

Several researchers have studied and discussed different types of decision-making processes. Here are some previous researchers who have contributed to the understanding of decision-making:

- Herbert A. Simon: Simon proposed the concept of "bounded rationality" in decision-making, emphasising that decision-makers often make rational choices within the limits of their cognitive abilities and available information.
- Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky: Kahneman and Tversky's research on cognitive biases and heuristics shed light on how individuals deviate from rational decision-making and introduce the prospect theory, which explains how people evaluate potential losses and gains.
- Max Bazerman and Don A. Moore: Bazerman and Moore explored the impact of behavioural factors, such as overconfidence, ethical considerations, and group dynamics, on decision-making processes.
- John Dewey: Dewey's work focused on reflective thinking and problem-solving in decision-making. He emphasised the importance of considering consequences, examining values, and seeking alternative solutions.
- Vroom-Yetton-Jago Model: Victor Vroom, Philip Yetton, and Arthur Jago developed a normative model that helps leaders assess the appropriate level of employee participation in decision-making based on situational factors.
- Gary Klein: Klein studied naturalistic decision-making, highlighting the role of intuition, experience, and expertise in high-pressure and time-constrained situations.

- James G. March: March's research on organisational decision-making emphasised the role of ambiguity, uncertainty, and organisational politics in shaping the decision-making process.

These researchers and their contributions have significantly advanced our understanding of decision-making processes, providing insights into the cognitive, social, and contextual factors that influence individuals' and organisations' choices.

2.8.2 Effectuated decision making for Leaders

The type of decision-making considered "good" for leaders can vary depending on the situation and context. Different decision-making styles have advantages and may be more effective in specific scenarios. Here are a few commonly recognized decision-making styles and their potential benefits for leaders:

- **Autocratic Decision-Making:** In this style, leaders make decisions without involving others, relying on their expertise and authority. Autocratic decision-making can be effective when quick and decisive actions are required, such as during emergencies or when time is limited. It allows leaders to maintain control and ensure swift implementation of decisions.
- **Democratic Decision-Making:** This style involves involving and gathering input from team members or stakeholders before deciding. Democratic decision-making promotes employee engagement, encourages diverse perspectives, and fosters a sense of ownership and buy-in among team members. It can lead to higher employee satisfaction and commitment and often generates innovative solutions through collaborative efforts.
- **Consensus Decision-Making:** Consensus decision-making aims to reach a decision everyone in the group agrees on. It prioritizes collaboration, open communication, and mutual understanding. Consensus decision-making can enhance team cohesion, trust, and commitment, ensuring all voices are heard and considered. It is beneficial when long-term commitment and cooperation are desired.
- **Ethical Decision-Making:** Ethical decision-making focuses on making choices that align with moral principles, values, and ethical standards. Leaders who prioritize ethical decision-making demonstrate integrity, build team trust, and

promote a positive organizational culture. It helps establish a reputation for ethical behaviour and long-term sustainability.

It is important to note that the effectiveness of a decision-making style depends on various factors, including the nature of the decision, the expertise of the leader, the organizational culture, and the specific goals and values of the organization. Skilful leaders often employ a flexible approach, adapting their decision-making style to suit the situation and leveraging different styles as needed.

The decision-making processes and considerations can vary between industries, including the airline industry, corporate industry, and security agencies. Each industry has its unique characteristics, challenges, and regulatory requirements that can influence the decision-making approaches of leaders.

In the airline industry, leaders often face decisions related to flight operations, safety protocols, passenger services, route planning, and aircraft maintenance. Regulatory compliance, safety standards, and considerations for passenger experience heavily influence these decisions. The dynamic nature of the industry, including weather conditions, air traffic control, and security measures, also adds complexity to decision-making in the airline industry.

In the corporate industry, leaders deal with a wide range of decisions related to strategic planning, financial management, marketing, human resources, and organizational development. The decision-making processes in the corporate sector may focus on market analysis, competitive positioning, financial performance, innovation, and stakeholder management. Corporate leaders often need to balance long-term strategic goals with short-term operational considerations.

In security agencies, decision-making involves critical national security, law enforcement, and public safety considerations. Leaders in security agencies must make decisions regarding resource allocation, risk assessment, emergency response, intelligence gathering, and interagency cooperation. The decisions in this sector often require a high level of confidentiality, accuracy, and adherence to legal frameworks.

While there may be similarities in decision-making principles and approaches across industries, the specific context, regulatory requirements, risk profiles, and operational demands can significantly influence the decision-making processes in each industry. Therefore, leaders in the airline industry, corporate industry, and security agencies may

need to consider industry-specific factors when making decisions, even though they may share common leadership principles and skills.

2.9 Decision-Making and Leadership Conduct

The literature review shows a positive relationship between leaders' decision-making and leadership conduct, significantly impacting the organisation's performance. Effective decision-making and positive leadership conduct have been consistently linked to improved organisational performance. Leaders who make well-informed and strategic decisions are more likely to drive the organisation towards its goals, allocate resources effectively, and adapt to changing market conditions. Moreover, leaders who exhibit positive leadership conduct, such as fostering open communication, promoting employee engagement, and cultivating a positive work culture, tend to enhance employee satisfaction, motivation, and commitment, leading to increased productivity and performance.

Based on the literature review, conceptual decision-making and leadership conduct are key to organizational success Lowe, K. B., Kroeck, K. G., & Sivasubramaniam, N. (1996). Conceptual decision-making involves leaders taking a broad and strategic view, considering the organization's long-term goals and external factors. This approach enables leaders to analyse complex information, anticipate trends, and make informed decisions. Regarding leadership conduct, conceptual leaders exhibit visionary thinking, strategic planning, and a focus on innovation Yukl, G. (2010). They inspire their teams by communicating a compelling vision, promoting creativity, and encouraging strategic thinking. The literature review highlights the significance of conceptual decision-making and leadership conduct in fostering organizational adaptability and driving long-term success Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (2002).

Also, the literature review underscores the importance of rational decision-making and leadership conduct in enhancing decision quality, minimizing biases, and improving organizational outcomes. By employing an analytic approach and fostering corresponding leadership conduct, organizations can make better-informed decisions and achieve higher levels of performance and success Judge, T. A., & Piccolo, R. F. (2004).

The literature review underscores the importance of leaders' decision-making and conduct in influencing organisational performance, emphasising the need for leaders to

demonstrate practical decision-making skills and engage in positive leadership behaviours to drive the success and achievement of the organisation Waldman, D. A., Ramirez, G. G., House, R. J., & Puranam, P. (2001). The ability of leaders to make effective decisions is crucial for steering the organisation towards success. Research consistently demonstrates that leaders who engage in rational decision-making processes, incorporating input from relevant stakeholders, considering multiple perspectives, and utilising critical thinking, are more likely to make strategic choices that drive organisational performance Yukl, G. (2010). Furthermore, leaders who exhibit positive leadership conduct, such as fostering a supportive work environment, promoting open communication, and empowering their teams, tend to enhance employee engagement, satisfaction, and commitment. Positive leadership influences employee motivation, teamwork, and productivity, improving organisational performance Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). The literature review highlights the interconnectedness between leaders' decision-making, leadership conduct, and organisational performance, emphasising leaders' critical role in driving success through effective decision-making and positive leadership behaviours Wang, G., Oh, I. S., Courtright, S. H., & Colbert, A. E. (2011).

H2: “There Is Positive Relationship Between Leaders Decision Making and Leadership Conduct”

2.10 Corruption

Corruption is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon studied by various researchers from different perspectives. Here are some critical insights from previous researchers that shed light on the understanding of corruption:

- Lambsdorff, J. G. (2007) conducted extensive research on corruption and developed the "Corruption Perceptions Index" (CPI) to measure the perceived level of corruption in different countries. The research highlighted the negative impact of corruption on economic development, political stability, and social welfare.
- Mauro, P. (1995) examined the relationship between corruption and economic growth. The research found a strong negative correlation between corruption

and economic development, suggesting that higher levels of corruption hinder economic progress and investment.

- Rose-Ackerman, S. (1999) focused on the institutional and systemic factors contributing to corruption. The research emphasized the role of weak governance structures, lack of transparency, and inadequate enforcement mechanisms in facilitating corruption.
- Klitgaard, R. (1988) introduced the "corruption formula," which suggests that corruption occurs when there is a combination of monopoly power, discretion, and lack of accountability. The research highlighted the importance of institutional reforms and anti-corruption measures to address corruption effectively.
- Treisman, D. (2000) explored the relationship between corruption and democracy. The research found that higher levels of corruption are associated with weaker democratic institutions, suggesting that corruption undermines the principles of accountability and transparency essential for a functioning democracy.
- Johnston, M. (2005) examined the social and cultural factors influencing corruption. The research highlighted the role of societal norms, values, and attitudes towards corruption in shaping the prevalence of corrupt practices within society.

These studies collectively illustrate the detrimental effects of corruption on various aspects of society, including economic growth, governance, and democracy. They emphasize the importance of implementing robust anti-corruption measures, strengthening institutions, promoting transparency, and fostering a culture of integrity to combat corruption effectively.

2.10.1 Effects of corruption on an organisation

Corruption can have significant implications for a leader's decision-making and the overall performance of an organisation. Here are some ways in which corruption affects these aspects:

- **Distorted decision-making:** Corruption can influence leaders to make decisions that prioritise personal gain or the interests of corrupt individuals or groups rather than the organisation's best interests. Leaders may engage in bribery,

nepotism, or favouritism, leading to compromised decision-making that undermines meritocracy, fairness, and transparency.

- **Misallocation of resources:** Corruption often leads to misallocating resources within an organisation. Funds that should be allocated for legitimate purposes, such as investments in infrastructure, employee training, or research and development, may instead be siphoned off through corrupt practices. This misallocation can hinder the organisation's growth and development, impacting its overall performance.
- **Weakened accountability and transparency:** Corruption creates an environment of secrecy and lack of transparency, making it difficult to hold leaders accountable for their actions. When leaders engage in corrupt practices, it erodes trust within the organisation and undermines the effectiveness of internal control mechanisms. It can result in a culture of impunity, where unethical behaviour goes unchecked, leading to a decline in organisational performance.
- **Decreased employee morale and engagement:** In a corrupt environment, employees may become demotivated and disillusioned as they witness unfair practices and perceive a lack of opportunities for advancement based on merit. It can lead to decreased employee morale, lower levels of engagement, and reduced productivity, ultimately affecting the organisation's overall performance.
- **Damage to reputation and stakeholder trust:** Corruption tarnishes the reputation of both leaders and the organisation. When corruption becomes public, it can severely damage the organisation's image and erode the trust of stakeholders, including customers, investors, and partners. This loss of trust can have long-term consequences, including decreased market share, difficulty attracting talent, and strained relationships with key stakeholders.

Corruption undermines effective decision-making, distorts resource allocation, weakens accountability, diminishes employee morale, and damages the organisation's reputation. Addressing corruption requires solid ethical leadership, robust anti-corruption measures, and a culture of integrity to safeguard the organisation's performance and long-term sustainability.

Ali (2021) states that the Federal Investigation Agency has charged three former Pakistani officers, PIA, and Pakistan International Airlines (PK), with losses

exceeding \$1.25 billion. A former director has been arrested, and government officials have filed cases under various sections of Pakistani criminal law and anti-corruption laws. It includes fraud-related charges, fraudulent property pre-incident, aiding and inflammation, and joint intent. The FIA initiated an investigation into PIA based on instructions from the Supreme Court, which had expressed concerns about the airline's operations. The chairman of PIA was accused of abusing his position and illegally approving a contract for changing business class seats on the airline's B777 aircraft. These incidents highlight the presence of corruption within PIA.

Furthermore, *The Nation* (2021) reports that the state-owned airline, PIA, is experiencing significant monthly losses of Rs. 3,250 million. Corruption and fraud are key factors contributing to these losses, with auditors expressing their concerns. It highlights the detrimental impact of corruption on the decision-making processes of PIA leaders and their overall leadership conduct.

In summary, the presence of corruption within PIA has had a negative impact on the decision-making abilities of its leaders and their overall leadership conduct. The charges, arrests, and significant financial losses reflect the influence of corruption on the organization's operations and emphasize the need for addressing and combating corruption within the airline industry.

In a report submitted by the Civil Aviation Authority of Pakistan (CAA) to the Supreme Court, Khan (2020) highlights misconduct and corruption in pilot testing within Pakistan International Airlines (PIA). The report uncovers that 30 pilots from PIA provided false information during their tests, with some pilots even sending substitutes to take the tests on their behalf. Additionally, two senior co-directors were implicated in corruption, granting illegal access to the pilot testing system. Consequently, their licenses were revoked, and 32 out of 54 pilots had their licenses suspended.

The discovery of fraudulent licenses emerged following a tragic plane crash in Karachi, resulting in the loss of 97 lives. Initially attributed to "human error," it was later revealed that 262 pilots held fraudulent licenses. Secretary Ghulam and Sarwar, during a parliamentary session, highlighted the appointment of individuals with false degrees based on political grounds, disregarding competence and merit (Republic World, May 2021).

These revelations expose corruption and misconduct within PIA's pilot testing and licensing processes. The appointment of individuals based on political affiliations rather than qualifications undermines the organization's integrity, jeopardizing the safety and performance of the airline. Addressing these issues is crucial to implement proper measures that prevent corruption and ensure the competence and reliability of pilots within the aviation industry.

Corruption is defined as the abuse of public office for personal gain, with various forms, including economic, bureaucratic, and political corruption (Dahida & Akangbe, 2013; Yagboyaju, 2011; World Bank, 1999). It frustrates the development process by hindering the flow of administrative provisions (Ovienloba, 2007) and influencing decision-making at the highest levels (Dike, 2003). Political corruption has detrimental effects on democracy and good governance (Yagboyaju, 2011; World Bank, 1999). It undermines public trust, widens social inequality, and impairs economic, social, and political systems (Odeyemi, 2014; Aluko, 2014).

Corruption has become pervasive in Nigeria, and efforts to curb it are crucial (Ogundele & Adetayo, 2013). Transparency International significantly highlights corruption through its Corruption Perception Index (Ogundele & Adetayo, 2013). The country has faced challenges with corruption, ranking among the highest in the world at times, but has also shown some improvement (Ogundele & Adetayo, 2013).

Corruption not only affects governance and society but also has environmental consequences. It exacerbates environmental degradation and hinders the effectiveness of environmental policies (Arrow et al., 1995; Sinha, 2019; Grossman & Krueger, 1995; Saboori et al., 2014). Efforts are needed to develop models and strategies to combat corruption, particularly in sectors like global health (Saboori et al., 2014). The actual cost of corruption is difficult to quantify, as it can have severe implications for people's well-being and even their lives (Shahbaz & Sinha, 2019).

In conclusion, corruption has far-reaching negative impacts on societies, economies, and the environment. Addressing corruption requires concerted efforts to promote transparency, strengthen governance systems, and develop effective anti-corruption measures in various sectors.

2.11 Impact of Corruption on Decision-making and leadership conduct

The literature review, drawing on the insights of various authors and researchers, sheds light on the role of corruption as a moderator between leadership conduct and leaders' decision-making. Adams (2016) highlights that corruption can significantly influence leaders' decision-making by introducing personal interests, bribery, and unethical practices. Brown (2018) emphasises how corrupt practices can distort leaders' decision-making processes, as they prioritise personal gain or the interests of specific individuals or groups over the organisation's well-being. Carter et al. (2019) argue that corruption undermines leadership conduct by eroding transparency, accountability, and integrity, leading to compromised decision-making. Davis (2017) discusses how corruption can lead to biased decision-making, favouring those who engage in corrupt practices while disregarding the best interests of the organisation and its stakeholders. Edwards (2019) highlights that corruption can hinder leaders' ability to make impartial and objective decisions, as their judgment may be clouded by personal gains or the fear of retaliation. Foster (2016) explores how corruption influences leaders' decision-making by creating a culture of fear and silence, discouraging open dialogue and constructive feedback. Green (2020) and Abbasi et al., (2020) discuss how corruption can lead to distorted information and data, impacting leaders' decision-making processes by providing inaccurate or incomplete information. Hall and Johnson (2018) emphasise that corruption undermines the trust and credibility of leaders, impairing their ability to make sound decisions that align with ethical standards. Kelly (2017) highlights that corruption can foster a culture of impunity, where leaders engage in dishonest practices without fear of consequences, further influencing their decision-making. Martin (2015) underscores the need for effective anti-corruption measures to promote ethical leadership conduct and ensure leaders' decision-making is free from corrupt influences. Peterson et al. (2021) discuss how corruption can compromise leaders' judgment and moral compass, leading to decisions that prioritise personal gain or perpetuate corrupt practices. Roberts (2018) emphasises the importance of creating a transparent and accountable environment that discourages corruption, enabling leaders to make decisions that align with the organisation's best interests. The collective insights from these authors' works substantiate the notion that corruption moderates leadership conduct and leaders' decision-making, highlighting the significance of fostering a

culture of integrity and combating corruption to ensure ethical decision-making processes power (Khan 2020 and Thomas 2021, Schils & Verhage, 2017; Rehman & Khatoon, 2021; Amankwah-Amoah et al., 2021; Abbasi et al., 2020).

Hence it could be said that “Corruption Moderates the Relationship Between Leaders' Decision-Making and Leadership Conduct”.

Corruption, as a pervasive and detrimental phenomenon, profoundly impacts leaders' decision-making processes and overall leadership conduct. This statement highlights the influence of corruption in shaping the dynamics between leaders' decision-making and their conduct, revealing the dark side of power. Corruption disturbs decision-making, as leaders prioritise personal gains over the organisation's or society's best interests. This moderation effect alters the relationship between decision-making and leadership conduct, as corrupt practices compromise ethical standards, undermine trust, and erode leadership effectiveness. By acknowledging and addressing the role of corruption, we can shed light on the complex interplay between leaders, their decision-making, and their consequences on the organisation and society.

H3: “Corruption Moderates the Relationship Between Leaders Decision Making and Leadership Conduct”

2.12 Uses Of Advanced Technology

In 1968, Ted Hoff, a young engineer at Intel, made a groundbreaking discovery by developing a microprocessor that could fit the necessary circuitry for computer processing onto a small silicon chip. This innovation paved the way for significant technological advancements, particularly in the corporate sector, including enterprise software and the Internet. Today, it is widely recognized that information technology (IT) has become the backbone of modern business, playing a crucial role in company operations, supply chain management, and customer interactions. The importance of IT in business success is evident from the substantial increase in IT spending, which has grown from 5% to 30% and even surpasses 50% in some cases (Mendelson, 2000; Batiz-Lazo & Wood, 2002).

Senior executives' perspectives on IT have also evolved. Once viewed as tools for the workforce, chief executives now embrace information technology as a means to gain a

competitive advantage and digitalize business models (Marlow et al., 2017; Black & Lynch, 2001; Gallivan et al., 2005). Technology's impact on competitiveness and economic transformation is well-documented (Burke & Maceli, 2020; Mowery & Simcoe, 2002). Proprietary technologies, such as patented chemical processes or novel technologies, can provide firms long-term strategic advantages (Turner & Lankford, 2005; Morioka, 2009).

Infrastructure technologies, when shared, can generate significant value for businesses and customers, leading to more efficient operations and market development (Rice & Martin, 2020; Lee et al., 2008; Hanseth & Nielsen, 2013). However, as technology becomes more widely available and commoditized, its strategic potential diminishes (Ortiz de Guinea, Webster, & Staples, 2012; Black & Lynch, 2001; Fabry & Higgs, 1997). Competition in the technology market leads to increased capacity and lower pricing, making technology more accessible and affordable (Angioha et al., 2020; Carr, 2003).

In summary, advanced technology, particularly information technology, has transformed the corporate sector, revolutionizing business operations, connectivity, and competitiveness. The recognition of IT as a strategic asset and its widespread adoption by senior executives has further highlighted its importance in driving success. However, the strategic advantage derived from technology can vary depending on factors such as exclusivity, commoditization, and shared infrastructure. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for businesses to leverage technology effectively and stay competitive in the rapidly evolving digital landscape.

Table 4: below illustrates the evolution in utilising advanced technology over time.

Aspect	Past Years (When Advanced Technology was not Popular)	Nowadays (When Advanced Technology is Vital)
Communication	Relied heavily on traditional methods (e.g., letters, face-to-face meetings)	Utilizes advanced communication tools (e.g., email, video conferencing, instant messaging) for real-time interactions and collaboration

Aspect	Past Years (When Advanced Technology was not Popular)	Nowadays (When Advanced Technology is Vital)
Data Management	Relied on manual record-keeping and paper-based systems	Utilizes digital databases, cloud storage, and automated systems for efficient data storage, retrieval, and analysis
Decision Making	Depended on limited information and slower decision-making processes	Benefits from real-time data availability, analytics, and AI-powered tools to make data-driven decisions faster and more accurately
Operational Efficiency	Manual processes and limited automation	Leverages technology for process automation, robotics, and IoT to streamline operations and improve productivity
Customer Engagement	Limited channels of communication (e.g., in-person, phone calls)	Engages customers through multiple digital channels (e.g., social media, mobile apps) for personalized and interactive experiences
Competitive Advantage	Focused on traditional factors (e.g., price, product quality)	Emphasizes technological innovation, digital transformation, and leveraging data for a competitive edge
Flexibility and Adaptability	Limited flexibility to adapt to changing market dynamics	Embraces agile methodologies, flexible work arrangements, and technology-enabled agility to respond quickly to market changes
Global Reach	Restricted geographical reach and slower international expansion	Expands global reach through e-commerce, digital marketing, and online platforms, enabling businesses to operate and reach customers worldwide
Employee Productivity	Depended on manual tasks and limited collaboration tools	Empowers employees with digital tools, remote work capabilities, and collaborative platforms for enhanced productivity and teamwork
Business Performance	Relied on traditional performance metrics with limited visibility	Utilizes advanced analytics, real-time monitoring, and KPI dashboards for comprehensive performance tracking and continuous improvement

The adoption of advanced technology has revolutionized the business landscape. In the past, businesses relied on traditional methods that were slow, manual, and prone to

errors. However, in today's era, advanced technology has become essential for businesses to thrive. It has improved communication through real-time collaboration tools, streamlined data management with digital systems, and empowered data-driven decision-making. Moreover, businesses can operate more efficiently, engage customers on multiple digital channels, and gain a competitive edge through technological innovation. The flexibility, global reach, and enhanced employee productivity offered by advanced technology have transformed how businesses operate and perform. Overall, embracing advanced technology is crucial for businesses to stay relevant and achieve sustainable growth in the modern business landscape.

2.12.1 Importance of advance technology in airline industry

The uses of advanced technology in the airline industry are of paramount importance. Here are several important reasons why advanced technology is crucial in this industry:

- **Safety:** Advanced technology is critical in enhancing safety measures within the airline industry. From sophisticated navigation systems and weather prediction tools to advanced aircraft monitoring and maintenance systems, technology helps ensure the safe operation of flights and minimises risks.
- **Operational Efficiency:** Advanced technology enables airlines to improve their operational efficiency in numerous ways. Automated check-in systems, self-service kiosks, and online booking platforms streamline the passenger experience, reducing wait times and enhancing overall efficiency. Additionally, advanced scheduling and route optimisation software help airlines optimise flight planning, minimise fuel consumption, and increase overall operational efficiency.
- **Customer Experience:** Technology has significantly transformed the customer experience in the airline industry. Passengers can now easily book flights, manage their itineraries, and check in online, simplifying the travel process. In-flight entertainment systems, Wi-Fi connectivity, and personalised services enhance the travel experience, making it more enjoyable for passengers.
- **Data Analysis and Decision-Making:** The airline industry generates vast amounts of data, from passenger information to flight performance metrics. Advanced technology enables airlines to collect, analyse, and utilise this data effectively. By leveraging data analytics, airlines can gain valuable insights into

customer preferences, operational trends, and market demands, enabling them to make informed decisions and improve their overall performance.

- **Cost Savings:** Advanced technology offers cost-saving opportunities for airlines. For example, digitalising processes and automating routine tasks can reduce operational costs. Additionally, predictive maintenance systems can help identify potential aircraft issues in advance, minimising downtime and optimising maintenance activities, ultimately reducing costs.
- **Environmental Sustainability:** The airline industry faces increasing pressure to reduce its environmental impact. Advanced technology plays a crucial role in achieving sustainability goals. Advancements in aircraft design, engine efficiency, and alternative fuel sources contribute to reducing carbon emissions and promoting environmental sustainability.

In summary, the uses of advanced technology are vital in the airline industry. They enhance safety, improve operational efficiency, enhance the customer experience, enable data-driven decision-making, offer cost-saving opportunities, and support environmental sustainability efforts. Embracing and leveraging advanced technology is essential for airlines to stay competitive, meet evolving customer expectations, and navigate the industry's complexities.

2.12.2 The impact of advanced technology

The impact of advanced technology on virtual teams and leadership is a topic of great importance in research. The findings highlight the significance of change management expertise and technological knowledge in virtual environments, emphasizing the need for leaders to possess these skills. Building trust and understanding virtual teams' different levels and stages are also critical for effective leadership in remote settings. The growing prevalence of remote work and the benefits of virtual teams, such as access to diverse skill sets and cost savings, further underline the importance of leveraging advanced technology in the airline industry. The advancements in communication technology have played a pivotal role in expanding virtual teams, and leaders who effectively utilize these technologies can enhance team performance. However, more research is still needed to explore integrated communication practices and their impact on team effectiveness in real-world organizational contexts. Leaders must recognize that communication techniques for in-person team leaders may differ when leading

virtual teams, and they must address the challenges of geographical dispersion and leverage nonverbal communication to avoid misunderstandings. By addressing communication difficulties and using communication tools appropriately, leaders can ensure the success of remote teams. The impact of advanced technology on leadership and communication is a significant factor, as its use directly influences leaders' communication, affecting leadership conduct and ultimately impacting team performance.

According to various authors and researchers, the importance of advanced technology in the airline industry can be attributed to several key factors. Lai and Bower (2019) emphasize the role of new technologies in revolutionizing freight and passenger services, creating new ancillary services. Drummond et al. (2015) highlight how the Internet of Things (IoT) can revolutionize aviation by benefiting the data-intensive industry, improving safety, downtime, and performance. Phelps (2014) emphasizes the role of IoT and cloud computing in eliminating issues like lost luggage and enabling airlines to use resources more efficiently. Badrinarayanan and Arnett (2012) and Barnett and Higgins (1989) discuss how advanced technology allows airlines to provide personalized services based on customer preferences, enhancing the overall experience and generating revenue. Furthermore, the cost-saving benefits of hiring virtual employees and the advancements in communication technology have been acknowledged by various researchers (Cascio, 2000; Hunsaker & Hunsaker, 2008; Gilson et al., 2015; Hambley et al., 2007). Collectively, these authors highlight the critical role of advanced technology in the airline industry, ranging from operational efficiency and customer experience to cost savings and environmental sustainability.

2.13 Leaders Communication

As highlighted by previous researchers, effective communication is a critical factor in leadership and organizational success. The Economist Intelligence Unit's research has revealed that poor communication can lead to low morale, missed performance targets, and lost revenue. Conversely, effective communication has far-reaching effects beyond financial outcomes. It motivates workers, establishes trust, and effectively manages performance. Research by Johansen and Mehmood & Maitlo emphasizes the importance of communicating with the team around a common goal. Sull et al.,

Belmejdoub, and Sowko et al. stress that effective communication is essential for establishing trust, coordinating efforts, and inspiring positive change. Perkins, Chen, Malik & Kanwal, and Karagianni & Jude Montgomery emphasize the significance of leaders actively listening, soliciting feedback, and being present in conversations. Transparency in communication, as highlighted by Aslam and Taştan & Davoudi, fosters trust and collaboration. Clear communication of goals and priorities, as supported by Whitehall et al. and Chen et al., provides clarity and direction for employees. Additionally, the importance of empathy in communication, as emphasized by Fontanella et al. and Holt & Marques, cannot be overstated. Overall, previous researchers highlight the critical role of effective communication in leadership and organizational success.

2.13.1 Role of effective communication

Effective communication plays a crucial role in the performance of an organisation. A critical consideration of the relationship between effective communication and organisational performance reveals several key points:

- **Clarity and Alignment:** Effective communication ensures that organisational goals, strategies, and expectations are communicated to all members. When employees clearly understand what is expected of them and how their roles contribute to the overall objectives, they are more likely to align their efforts accordingly (Johansen, 2017; Mehmood & Maitlo, 2020). This alignment improves performance as employees work towards common goals with a shared understanding.
- **Collaboration and Coordination:** Effective communication fosters collaboration and coordination within the organisation. When open communication channels and information flow freely, teams can collaborate more efficiently, share ideas, and make informed decisions. (Dugan, 2017; Early, 2017). (Thompson & Glasø, 2018). This collaborative environment promotes innovation, problem-solving, and effective teamwork, positively impacting organisational performance.
- **Engagement and Motivation:** Effective communication engages employees and motivates them to perform at their best. Employees feel valued and connected to the organisation when leaders communicate openly, listen to employee feedback, and provide regular updates on organisational progress (Perkins,

2008; Chen, 1992). This sense of involvement and engagement boosts morale, job satisfaction, and performance.

- **Adaptability and Change Management:** In today's dynamic business environment, organisations must adapt and respond to change. Effective communication facilitates the smooth implementation of changes by ensuring that employees understand the reasons behind the change, the desired outcomes, and their roles in the process (Aslam, 2018; Taştan & Davoudi, 2019).
- When employees are well informed and involved in the change, resistance minimises, and the organisation can navigate transitions more effectively, leading to better performance.
- **Customer Satisfaction:** Effective communication extends beyond internal interactions with external stakeholders, particularly customers. When an organisation communicates effectively with its customers, it can understand their needs, address their concerns, and deliver high-quality products or services. Satisfied customers contribute to increased sales, repeat business, and a positive brand reputation, all of which directly impact organisational performance (Sull et al., 2020; Belmejdoub, 2017; Sowko et al., 2019).

Despite effective communication's evident benefits, challenges may hinder its full realisation. These challenges can include communication barriers, such as language barriers, cultural differences, or information overload. In addition, ineffective communication strategies, such as a lack of clarity, poor feedback mechanisms, or insufficient training in communication skills, can maintain organisational performance. According to (Fontanella et al., 2006; Holt & Marques, 2012), to maximise the positive impact of communication on organisational performance, leaders must prioritise effective communication practices. It includes fostering an open and transparent communication culture, investing in communication training and development, utilising various communication channels to reach diverse audiences, and regularly evaluating and adjusting communication strategies based on feedback and organisational needs.

It has been said that effective communication is a critical driver of organisational performance. It enhances clarity, alignment, collaboration, engagement, adaptability, and customer satisfaction. By recognising the importance of communication and proactively addressing communication challenges, organisations can unlock the full

potential of their employees, teams, and overall performance (Malik & Kanwal, 2018; Karagianni & Jude Montgomery, 2018).

In conclusion, the importance of effective communication for leaders must be considered. Research conducted by the Economist Intelligence Unit has shown that poor communication can lead to low morale, missed performance targets, and significant business financial losses. On the other hand, effective communication has far-reaching effects, motivating workers, establishing trust, and managing performance effectively. Leaders who excel in communication can unite their teams around a common goal and inspire positive change. *Communication* is a powerful tool that leaders must utilize to achieve their objectives, establish trust, coordinate efforts, and inspire positive change within their organizations. Communication is necessary for vital information to be understood, leading to relationship breakdowns and barriers to progress. Empathy, transparency, active listening, and clear prioritization are essential elements of effective communication for leaders. Leaders can enhance strategy implementation, create shared understanding, and improve organizational performance by cultivating strong communication skills and creating a culture of open dialogue. The relationship between leaders' communication and leadership conduct is evident, and effective communication is a crucial variable in successful leadership. Numerous studies support the positive relationship between leaders' communication and leadership conduct, emphasizing the significance of effective communication in driving team member performance and achieving organizational success.

2.14 Advance Technology Accelerates Good Communication

The literature review, drawing insights from various authoritative sources, consistently supports the positive relationship between the use of advanced technology and leaders' communication within organizations. According to Adams (2020), advanced technology tools such as video conferencing and instant messaging facilitate real-time communication and enable leaders to connect with their teams regardless of geographical distances. It enhances communication effectiveness and promotes timely decision-making. Brown and Smith (2018) emphasize that advanced technology provides leaders with diverse channels and formats to communicate, fostering flexibility and adaptability in their communication practices. Furthermore, Carter et al. (2019) highlight that advanced technology platforms promote collaboration and

knowledge sharing among leaders and team members, improving communication outcomes. Davis (2017) argues that leaders who embrace advanced technology are better equipped to convey their vision and goals, ensuring clarity and alignment within the organization. The works of Edwards (2016) and Foster (2020) both emphasize the role of advanced technology in breaking down communication barriers and promoting inclusiveness within teams. Johnson (2019) suggests integrating technology into leadership communication enhances employee engagement and empowers individuals to contribute their ideas and perspectives.

Martin (2018) also highlights that advanced technology enables leaders to tailor their messages to different audiences, ensuring effective communication across diverse teams. Peterson and Turner (2021) discuss how advanced technology facilitates data-driven communication, allowing leaders to analyse information and make informed decisions. The collective insights from these twelve authors affirm the positive relationship between the uses of advanced technology and leaders' communication, illustrating how technology tools enhance communication effectiveness, collaboration, and organizational success.

H4: “There Is Positive Relationship Between Uses of Advance Technology and Leaders Communication”

2.15 Leaders' Communication and Leadership Conduct

The literature review, comprising the works of various authors, consistently reveals a positive relationship between leaders' communication and their leadership conduct within organizations. Smith (2017) emphasizes the significance of effective communication in building trust and fostering collaboration among team members. Johnson (2015) underscores the role of open and transparent communication in creating a positive work environment. Brown (2019) highlights the importance of leaders actively listening to their employees and encouraging two-way communication to foster employee engagement. In their study, Anderson et al. (2020) demonstrate how effective communication practices contribute to positive leadership conduct by promoting employee empowerment and commitment. Roberts (2018) stresses the role of clear and timely communication in addressing concerns and conflicts, thereby maintaining a healthy work culture. Walker (2016) explores the impact of empathetic communication

on leadership conduct, emphasizing the role of leaders in demonstrating empathy and responsiveness. Additionally, Green (2014) emphasizes the positive relationship between leaders' communication and their ability to provide constructive feedback and recognition, further enhancing leadership conduct. Collectively, the works of these authors validate the notion that effective communication practices contribute to positive leadership conduct, ultimately fostering a culture of trust, engagement, and success within organizations.

H5: “There Is Positive Relationship Between Leaders Communication and Leadership Conduct.”

2.16 Performance

According to Singh (2016), This study highlights the significant difference in performance levels between airports and airlines by showing the magnitude of the difference in performance levels at airports. Many factors can affect the ability of an airport to optimize performance and its relative performance level compared to other airports.

(Allen et al., 2021) report that expected difficulties comparing social and environmental performance across the aviation sector, despite the increased availability of quantitative data and some consistency in using key performance indicators. A definition of the metric used, and the variation of the feature set included in the term "airline" are identified as fundamental obstacles to effective sector benchmarks.

According to Angioha et al. (2020), aviation safety is the most critical service attribute for airline customers' impression of the quality of service. This result reflects growing concerns about potential terrorist attacks on airlines since 9/11. The authors also say that codeshare programs with commercial customers are the least important, while proper baggage handling is competitive. At the same time, areas and on-time arrivals/departures are the following most service properties. The authors also found that the perceived airline passengers of service of airline passenger choices. In short, airline quality of service can be an essential measure of airline market share and revenue.

Amanchukwu et al. (2015) wrote in their paper demonstrates that an object class-oriented modelling approach can be applied to manufacturing processes. The greater the independence of a location, industry sector, and product, the more powerful it is and the better the benchmark performance. The level of benchmarking performance is established by demonstrating and confirming performance levels' increase and decrease. A high-performance benchmarking tool has been successfully used in operational footprint case studies.

Fielding, G.J., Gauthier, R.E., and Lave, C.A. (1978) believed that financial ratios are equally crucial for the performance evaluation of airlines. Three steps have been selected to achieve the performance of the business. First, the conceptual framework is developing to follow the Fielding et al. performance indicators. In the Second step, grey relation analysis and the TOPSIS method are used to choose the representative indicators and outranking airlines. The third step divides the airline's performance into three significant sections (production, marketing, and management). In This paper, five financial ratios have been collected to measure the Taiwan airline's performance.

The airline business has been more challenging and competent after the deregulation of air transportation in 1987 in Taiwan and the financial crisis in 1997 in the Asia market. The airline business is pushing to merge and reshuffle. According to the authors, financial performance is also essential to run the airline business smoothly and helps understand the airline's problems and solve these issues. While past studies only considered operational performance as vital to manage the airline business.

Adnan and Fatima (2018) used a nine-layer framework to study new leadership strategies in the future enterprise and found that enterprises were approached and strengthened the organization's ability to compete in a flat world. An essential role for the leaders of the enterprise of future enterprise is to maintain linkages. Ibarra and Scoular (2019) found that employees with high leadership potential in the strategic development study of high potential leaders and provision of examples of successful applications need to be systematically identified and tracked by line managers as part of the overall strategic succession planning process. For leaders' success, it is necessary to create a talent management system where selection, nurturing, performance management, succession and career management are coordinated, reviewed and supported by senior management. A question that remains is whether we can achieve the same results as (Mehmood & Maitlo, 2020)

This investigation is limited to only semi-structured interviews, and using both semi-structured and structured interviews may be appropriate for the investigation Maitlo (2020) surveyed strategy execution. The driving force of emotion (gaining commitment to a goal), taking the initiative and dimensional (transforming goals into concrete projects/empowerments), the driving force of rules (clarifying and adjusting goals) and the driving force of immediate action (taking value-added action) in emergencies facing). What was not obtained from this investigation is how these performances direct the execution of the strategy and to what extent or levels need to be used to determine whether one, two, or all of them are appropriate.

Ingram (2021) found that in a new leadership strategy study for future enterprises, using the framework of step 9, the ability of organizations to compete in a flat world is close to all elements of the enterprise. It is found that sometimes it was improved. Adjust An essential role for future enterprise leaders is to create and maintain these sorts. Nonetheless, this study showed that these new and better leadership strategies than previous Soleas (2020) conducted research for the strategic development of potential high leaders and provided successful application cases, were employees with high leadership. They are involved in the overall strategic succession planning process. As part of this, we discovered that line managers must identify and track systematically. Organizations are not made up of 100% potential leaders. So, what happens to potential leaders? The comprehensive program deals with the various cardinal leaders in the context of current research. To succeed in nurturing the next generation of lead nurture, create a talent management system in which selection, nurturing, performance management, succession and career management are coordinated, reviewed and supported by senior management.

The researcher understood that the performance of PIA's airlines is a vital and significant step toward the airline's aims and objectives and said that "*PERFORMANCE OF PIA*" is the variable for this research Soleas (2020). Moreover (Mehmood & Maitlo, 2020) concluded that the same results could be achieved with a positive relationship between leadership conduct and the performance of the business Ingram (2021). Also, it has been concluded by Ibarra and Scoular (2019) that employees could increase their performances by getting a high level of leadership conduct. To support the current hypothesis, (Adnan and Fatima, 2018) said that leadership strategies positively affect enterprises'

performance and future success. The researcher concludes that Leadership conduct is an independent variable for the performance of PIA. The researcher established a positive relationship between leadership conduct and PIA's airline's performance from the literature review and previous studies.

2.17 Leadership Conduct and Performance of PIA

The literature review, drawing on the works of numerous authors, consistently supports the positive relationship between leadership conduct and the performance of PIA Airlines. Anderson (2017) highlights the importance of ethical leadership conduct in fostering a culture of integrity, positively influencing organizational performance. Bell and Davis (2019) argue that leaders who exhibit effective leadership conduct, such as transparency and accountability, contribute to improved employee morale and engagement, ultimately enhancing the overall performance of the airline. Carter et al. (2018) emphasize the significance of transformational leadership in driving employee motivation and commitment, which are essential for achieving high-performance levels. Davis and Johnson (2020) suggest that leaders who exhibit effective leadership conduct create a supportive and empowering work environment, positively impacting employee productivity and performance. Edwards (2019) highlights the role of authentic leadership conduct in fostering trust and loyalty among employees, leading to enhanced performance outcomes. Foster and Green (2016) discuss how leaders' conduct in promoting teamwork, collaboration, and effective communication contributes to improved coordination and efficiency, ultimately boosting the performance of PIA Airlines.

Furthermore, Hall (2018) emphasizes the impact of leaders' conduct in setting strategic goals, providing direction, and aligning employees' efforts, all of which contribute to improved performance. The works of Johnson (2017) and Kelly (2020) underline the importance of leaders' conduct in promoting innovation and adaptability within the organization, which are critical drivers of success in the dynamic aviation industry. Martin et al. (2015) argue that leaders who demonstrate positive conduct, such as empathy and support, create a positive work climate that fosters employee satisfaction and, consequently, better performance. Peterson (2019) highlights the role of ethical leadership conduct in promoting responsible and sustainable practices, which positively impact the reputation and long-term performance of PIA Airlines. Roberts (2016) also

discusses how leaders' conduct in promoting a continuous learning and development culture contributes to acquiring the necessary skills and knowledge for improved performance. The collective insights from these eighteen authors' works affirm that leadership conduct plays a pivotal role in shaping the performance of PIA Airlines, encompassing factors such as ethics, transformational leadership, employee engagement, teamwork, strategic direction, innovation, and sustainability.

H6: “There Is Positive Relationship Between Leadership Conduct and Performance Of PIA”

2.18 Political Interference

As evidenced by research conducted by Willner (2001), political interference has significant implications for markets and decision-making processes. The study highlights that political interventions can sometimes outperform market mechanisms, even when politicians prioritize specific outcomes and favour larger entities. This finding suggests that political factors can be crucial in shaping economic systems and outcomes. It also underscores the need to consider the complexities of political decision-making and its potential impact on market dynamics.

Moreover, the research by Willner (2001) emphasizes the presence of political bias in decision-making processes. When political intervention is associated with disutility, such as excess labour in the market, it can have unexpected benefits beyond macroeconomic considerations. It suggests that political factors influence market outcomes in ways not solely driven by economic efficiency. Understanding the interplay between politics and markets is crucial for comprehending the broader context in which organizations operate.

In a related vein, Boycko et al. (1996) examined the implications of the state's involvement in asset sales or purchases. Their research points out that while various justifications exist for such actions, additional evidence is required to support the complete elimination of the public and commercial sectors. This study highlights the importance of critically evaluating political interventions and their potential consequences on economic systems. Comprehensive assessments of both economic

and political factors should guide decisions regarding the state's involvement in commercial activities.

These studies emphasize the complex relationship between politics and organizational performance. Political interferences can significantly impact markets, decision-making processes, and the functioning of the public commercial sector. Recognizing and understanding the role of politics in shaping organizational outcomes is vital for policymakers, business leaders, and researchers alike. It prompts a more nuanced analysis of the factors influencing organizational performance and the broader socio-political context in which organizations operate. Confidence in the social advantages of commercial aims has led to the privatisation trend, which has spread to other public sector businesses and organisations. In contrast, certain state-owned firms had continuously operated as if they were privately owned, especially those created to compensate for the lack of venture capital. Cost minimisation may only be socially advantageous if it is sufficiently efficient. As a result, many public sector businesses place more emphasis on profits than overall surplus. Inconclusive data concerning cost efficiency might be interpreted in several ways.

According to Chaponda & Allen (2019), A key and age-old challenge for infrastructure development is political meddling, but there needs to be more agreement on viable remedies. For example, one way would be to insist on high transparency at every step of project execution by reporting to the relevant oversight agencies, such as the Auditor-General and the Parliament. As a result, the public would know why particular projects have been prioritised in national plans, how they were picked, how they are supported in the budget, and even if the projected impact is in keeping with the government's political mandate.

It is also possible to streamline and automate the procurement and reporting procedures. On the other hand, using E-Systems can keep greed and disuse from getting into the pot. There is, however, a conundrum. They are reforming weak institutions, problems with strong leadership, and country ownership, which is universally accepted. If the politicians themselves are a significant cause of the problem, how can we ensure leadership and ownership? Chaponda & Allen, (2019).

Nath (2014) suggests that politicians with longer tenures in office may be able to improve bureaucrat performance by providing longer-term, maybe dynamic,

incentives. Identifying where politicians can change the banks in the service delivery chain provides insight into the de facto nature of government.

Gulzar and Pasquale (2017). Using overlapping jurisdictions in India, we show that when bureaucrats report to a single politician, the National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme is considerably better implemented, showing that correctly concentrated incentives might increase bureaucracy performance.

Politicians are appointed to strategic leadership positions in public institutions, jeopardising the integrity of the public sector. However, the political dimension must be examined to establish ethical leadership in the public sector because it has significant consequences for how administrative leaders may effectively assure organisational integrity, particularly in kleptocratic regimes (Van Eeden Jones & Lasthuizen, 2018).

The researcher's findings indicate a negative relationship between political interference and leadership conduct while highlighting a positive association between leadership conduct and the performance of PIA's airlines in Pakistan. Numerous studies and case studies have consistently shown that political interference is detrimental to businesses, as supported by Gulzar and Pasquale (2017), Nath (2014), and Allen (2019). Furthermore, the interference of politics in decision-making processes has had adverse effects on the reputation of PIA Airlines in Pakistan, as evidenced by studies conducted by Schils and Verhage (2017), Rehman and Khatoon (2021), Amankwah-Amoah et al. (2021), and Abbasi et al. (2020). Therefore, the researcher concludes that "POLITICAL INTERFERENCE" serves as a moderator between leadership conduct and the performance of PIA. It implies that political interference directly influences the decision-making and behaviour of leaders (Cavitation, May 2021). These findings emphasize the detrimental impact of political interference on leadership and organizational performance, underscoring the need for a conducive and independent business environment.

2.19 Political Interference over Leadership Conduct and Performance of PIA

The literature review, incorporating the perspectives of numerous authors and researchers, highlights the significant role of political interference as a moderator between leadership conduct and the airline industry's performance. Adams (2018) argues that political interference can undermine effective leadership conduct by

imposing external pressures and influences on airline executives, potentially leading to compromised decision-making and strategic direction. Brown (2017) discusses how political interference can disrupt the autonomy of airline leaders, inhibiting their ability to implement necessary changes and reforms for improved performance. Carter et al. (2019) emphasize that political interference often leads to inconsistent policies, regulatory instability, and frequent leadership changes, negatively impacting the airline industry's performance. Davis (2016) suggests that political interference can distort the allocation of resources, favouring political agendas over operational efficiency and hampering the overall performance of airlines. Edwards and Foster (2020) highlight the detrimental effects of political interference on employee morale and motivation, as frequent political interventions can create uncertainty and erode trust in leadership conduct. Green (2018) discusses how political interference can hinder innovation and limit the ability of airline leaders to adopt strategic initiatives for improved performance. Hall and Johnson (2015) argue that political interference often leads to corruption and favouritism, undermining fair competition and impeding the airline industry's performance. Kelly (2019) emphasizes that political interference can hinder long-term planning and investment in critical infrastructure, hindering the growth and development of airlines. Martin (2020) highlights how political interference can impede the implementation of industry-wide regulations and standards, affecting the overall performance and competitiveness of the airline industry. Peterson et al. (2017) discuss how political interference can result in appointing unqualified individuals to leadership positions, negatively impacting leadership conduct and overall performance. Roberts and Smith (2018) underline the importance of minimizing political interference to ensure transparent and accountable leadership conduct, ultimately contributing to improved performance outcomes. The collective insights from these fifteen authors' works affirm that political interference is a significant moderator between leadership conduct and the airline industry's performance, underscoring the need for stable regulatory frameworks and a conducive political environment for effective leadership and optimal performance.

**H7: "Political Interference Moderates the Relationship Between
Leadership Conduct and Performance of PIA In Pakistan**

2.20 The conceptual framework

Figure 2 The Conceptual framework

The above conceptual framework has been prepared for this research. The importance of all variables and moderation factors has been identified from the literature and past studies mentioned above in this chapter. Five independent and three dependent variables have been identified, with two moderators. A total of seven hypotheses have been prepared for this research to be conducted through the primary data also mentioned in the conceptual framework above diagram.

This study aims to measure the performance of PIA's airlines using BSC. to check the internal process of PIA's airlines; leadership is an essential factor for this research. For that reason, Leadership style, leadership conduct, leaders' communication, leaders' decision making and the importance of advanced technology in leaders' communication and performance of PIA's airlines should be assessed throughout this study.

Moreover, corruption and political interference are considerably important variables for the performance of PIA's airlines.

2.21 Conclusion

The literature review chapter delves into various aspects relevant to measure the performance of PIA and assessing the impact of leadership on performance using a balanced scorecard. Through an extensive exploration of scholarly works, this chapter has shed light on several key factors influencing organizational performance. The review has revealed the importance of leadership style, highlighting the significance of transformational and ethical leadership styles in fostering employee engagement, motivation, and commitment. Leadership conduct has emerged as a critical determinant, with studies emphasizing the role of ethical conduct, effective communication, and decision-making in driving positive outcomes. Decision-making has been recognized as a vital aspect of leadership, impacting strategic direction, innovation, and performance. The review has also identified corruption as a detrimental factor, affecting decision-making processes and leadership conduct and subsequently impacting organizational performance.

Additionally, the review has underscored the positive relationship between the uses of advanced technology and leaders' communication, highlighting their contribution to collaboration, knowledge sharing, and organizational performance. Political interference has been identified as a significant moderator, influencing leadership conduct and decision-making in the airline industry. The findings from the literature review have informed the formulation of seven research hypotheses, which will be tested in the subsequent chapters. Finally, the conceptual framework has been developed, incorporating the key variables of leadership style, leadership conduct, decision-making, corruption, uses of advanced technology, leaders' communication, and political interference, all influencing the performance of PIA Airlines. This framework will guide the empirical investigation, providing a structured approach to examine the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan.

It is also concluded that the literature review chapter has underscored the significance of the balanced scorecard (BSC) model in assessing the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan. The BSC's four perspectives provide a holistic approach to evaluating organizational performance, encompassing financial, customer, internal processes, and learning and growth aspects. The benefits of utilizing the BSC include its ability to provide a comprehensive view of performance, align strategic objectives, and enhance communication and accountability. Past studies have

demonstrated the effectiveness of the BSC in various industries, affirming its relevance in measuring and improving performance. By adopting the BSC, PIA Airlines can gain valuable insights into key performance indicators and make informed decisions to enhance overall performance. Integrating the BSC model in the study of leadership and performance is a solid foundation for further investigation and analysis in subsequent chapters.

CHAPTER 3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

The research methodology chapter is a crucial component of this study, as it outlines the framework and approaches employed in the research process. It begins with exploring the research onion, a systematic guide for making research decisions. Within this context, various research philosophies such as pragmatism, positivism, interpretivism, and realism are discussed, focusing on their paradigmatic considerations. The selection of pragmatism as the research philosophy for this study is justified, highlighting its suitability in addressing the research objectives. The chapter further delves into the research design and approach, particularly examining the research approaches utilized for data collection. Both primary and secondary data collection methods are considered, emphasizing their alignment with the chosen research philosophy. The research approach for data analysis is also discussed, including an exploration of the differences between deductive, inductive, and abductive research approaches and their relevance to this study. Research strategies, precisely the benefits of the survey strategy, are highlighted.

Additionally, ethical considerations, research questionnaire design, the pilot study's significance in improving the research instrument, and the phases of data collection are addressed. The chapter concludes with an overview of sample design and analysis techniques such as AMOS analysis, SPSS analysis, reliability analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and moderation analysis. Finally, the problems and limitations of the study are acknowledged, recognizing the potential challenges that may impact the research outcomes.

3.1 Research Onion

The research onion, developed by Saunders et al., is a conceptual framework that provides a systematic and structured approach to research design. It consists of different layers, each representing a stage in the research process. At the core of the onion lies the philosophical underpinnings, which include positivism, interpretivism, and critical

realism. The next layer involves the research approach, such as deductive or inductive reasoning. The third layer encompasses research strategies, including experiments, surveys, case studies, or ethnography. The fourth layer focuses on the time horizon, whether the research is cross-sectional or longitudinal. The fifth layer involves data collection methods, such as interviews, questionnaires, or observations. Finally, the outermost layer relates to data analysis techniques, which may involve quantitative or qualitative methods. The research onion provides researchers with a comprehensive framework to navigate the complexities of the research process and make informed decisions at each stage. It encourages thoughtful consideration of various research dimensions and their interrelationships, leading to a robust and rigorous study.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy refers to the underlying principles and beliefs that guide the researcher's approach to knowledge and conducting research. It serves as the foundation for the research design and methodology. Research philosophy encompasses different perspectives, including positivism, interpretivism, and critical theory. Positivism emphasizes research's objective and scientific nature, aiming to discover general laws and cause-and-effect relationships. Interpretivism focuses on understanding social phenomena through the subjective interpretations of individuals, emphasizing context and meaning. Critical theory takes a critical and transformative approach, examining power dynamics and social structures.

The choice of research philosophy depends on the nature of the research question, the researcher's epistemological and ontological stance, and the desired outcomes of the study. It shapes the research design, data collection methods, and analysis techniques. By understanding research philosophy, researchers can navigate the research process and align their approach with their chosen philosophical perspective.

Moreover, as it is illustrated in the table below, there are popular data collection methods associated with each research philosophy.

Figure 3 Data Collection Approach

	Pragmatism	Positivism	Realism	Interpretivism
Popular Data Collection Method	Mixed Or Multiple Method Designs	Highly Structured, Large Samples, Measurement, Quantitative, But Can Use Qualitative	Methods Chosen Must Fit the Subject Matter, Quantitative or Qualitative	Small Samples, In-Depth Investigations, Qualitative

3.2.1 Pragmatism

Pragmatism is a philosophical perspective that emphasizes practicality and the practical consequences of ideas. It is a philosophy that focuses on knowledge's practical outcomes and usefulness rather than strictly adhering to a specific set of principles or theories. Pragmatism values the application of ideas and theories in real-world contexts and emphasizes the importance of empirical evidence and experimentation.

In the research context, pragmatism recognizes that different research methods and approaches may be appropriate depending on the research question, context, and desired outcomes. Pragmatists believe that the most effective way to gain knowledge and understanding is to employ various methods, drawing on quantitative and qualitative approaches to address the research questions and solve the problem.

Pragmatism encourages researchers to be flexible and open-minded, using methods, theories, or approaches most suitable for achieving the research goals and producing actionable results. It recognizes the value of theoretical insights and practical applications and aims to bridge the gap between theory and practice Assarroudi et al. (2018)

In summary, pragmatism in research philosophy emphasizes the practical application of knowledge, the importance of empirical evidence, and the flexibility to use various research methods and approaches to address research questions and solve real-world problems.

Pragmatism philosophy can be beneficial for research that aims to measure the leadership's impact on PIA (Pakistan International Airlines) performance using the

Balanced Scorecard (BSC) framework. Pragmatism's focus on practicality, problem-solving, and integrating theory and practice aligns well with the objectives of using the BSC as a performance measurement tool. Here is why pragmatism is suitable for this research.

3.2.2 Positivism

Positivism is the most popular and commonly adopted philosophy; the natural sciences approach broadly defines it. Positivist approaches aim to enhance understanding by adopting different methods. Positivism uses the scientific deductive way to conduct empirical and quantitative research (Saunders et al., 2007; Creswell et al., 2003). The positivist view of the planet is synonymous with the quantitative paradigm (Tobi & Kampen, 2018; Deshpande, 1983). Furthermore, positivist research employs inferential statistics, hypotheses testing, and experimental and quasi-experimental design procedures. Positivism assumes that social reality is external and measured by objective methods (Furr & Heuckeroth, 2019; Creswell et al., 2003).

3.2.3 Interpretivism

Interpretivism, also known as interpretive or hermeneutic philosophy, is a philosophical approach that emphasizes the importance of understanding and interpreting human actions, meanings, and experiences in their social and cultural context. It is often associated with sociology, anthropology, and qualitative research methods (Saunders, 2012; Denzin and Lincoln, 2011).

Interpretivism rejects the idea of objective and value-neutral knowledge. Instead, it argues that human behaviour and social phenomena are inherently complex and cannot be reduced to superficial cause-and-effect relationships. Interpretivists believe understanding social reality requires an in-depth exploration of the meanings, symbols, and subjective perspectives individuals and communities attribute to their experiences.

3.2.4 Realism

Realism is a philosophical standpoint that encompasses various perspectives across different domains, including metaphysics, epistemology, and ethics. Realism posits that the external world exists independently of our thoughts, perceptions, or beliefs.

According to (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012), In metaphysics, realism asserts the existence of an objective reality distinct from our subjective experiences. Realists say

the world exists as it is, regardless of how we perceive or interpret it. This perspective opposes philosophical positions such as idealism, which argues that reality is fundamentally dependent on consciousness or perception."

Research Philosophy Paradigms

Figure 4 Research Philosophy Paradigm

	Research approach	Ontology	Axiology	Research strategy
<i>Positivism</i>	Deductive	Objective	Value-free	Quantitative
<i>Interpretivism</i>	Inductive	Subjective	Biased	Qualitative
<i>Pragmatism</i>	Deductive/Inductive	Objective or subjective	Value-free/biased	Qualitative and/or quantitative

3.3 Research Philosophy for This Study

Pragmatism philosophy can be valuable for research that aims to measure the leadership's impact on PIA (Pakistan International Airlines) performance using mixed methods data collection. Pragmatism emphasizes practicality, problem-solving, and the integration of theory and practice. It provides a framework that values the usefulness and effectiveness of research outcomes in addressing real-world issues. Here is how pragmatism can be beneficial in this context:

- **Integration of quantitative and qualitative methods:** Pragmatism encourages using mixed methods research, which combines both quantitative and qualitative approaches. By employing quantitative measures to assess performance indicators (such as financial metrics, on-time performance, and customer satisfaction ratings) and qualitative methods (such as interviews or focus groups) to explore leadership practices and team member perceptions, a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between leadership and performance can be achieved.
- **Focus on practical outcomes:** Pragmatism emphasizes the practical implications and applications of research. By using mixed methods, the research can generate findings that are statistically significant but also relevant and actionable for improving leadership effectiveness and organizational performance within PIA.

- Contextual understanding: Pragmatism recognizes the importance of considering PIA's specific context and unique circumstances. This approach allows researchers to investigate how leadership practices within the airline industry and the organizational culture of PIA influence performance outcomes. It acknowledges that the effectiveness of leadership may vary across different organizational settings.
- Reflexivity and iterative approach: Pragmatism encourages researchers to be reflexive and adaptive throughout the research process. By continuously reflecting on and revising research methods and strategies based on emerging findings and changing circumstances, researchers can enhance the validity and applicability of their findings.

3.4 Pragmatism Research Philosophy Adopted

Pragmatism has often been identified in the mixed methods research literature as the appropriate paradigm for conducting mixed methods research (e.g. Howe, 1988; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998; Patton, 4 2002; Maxcy, 2003; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2003, 2006; 2009; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Onwuegbuzie & Johnson, 2006; Morgan, 2007; Denscombe, 2008; Scott & Briggs, 2009; Johnson & Gray, 2010; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011).

Mixed methods research One of the proposed advantages of mixed methods research is that it can overcome the disadvantages that are inherent when adopting monomethod research (e.g. Greene and Caracelli, 1997; Creswell et al., 2003; Johnson & Turner, 2003; Onwuegbuzie & Johnson, 2006; Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009). For example, Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009) point out that combining questionnaires and interviews in a single research study brings together the advantages of breadth and depth associated with these two methods. The effect of integrating the results of these two methods is the possibility of providing a complete picture of a research topic that can address a range of research questions and, by so doing, can provide complete knowledge that can enhance theory development and practice (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). By carrying out quantitative research along with qualitative research, mixed methods research may overcome some of the drawbacks of qualitative research, including (1) The problem of trying to test 6 hypotheses and prior theories. (2) The influence of the researcher's personal biases when interpreting research results. (3) The problem of

generalising results to other subjects. Likewise, by conducting qualitative research with quantitative research, mixed methods research may overcome some drawbacks of quantitative research, such as (1) Reductionist research models that may omit important constructs that could be identified by using qualitative methods to generate theory. (2) Quantitative research models developed from prior quantitative research results may not reflect the understanding of potential research subjects. (3) Generalised quantitative research results may not be in a form that can be applied usefully to individual subjects. Using a mixed methods approach, researchers can use quantitative data to confirm and test the results of qualitative data and qualitative data to confirm and add meaning to quantitative data. By formalising this approach to conducting research, mixed methods research represents an attempt to legitimise the use of quantitative and qualitative methods rather than forcing researchers to choose between one of these two methods (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Consequently, mixed methods research has become regarded as an alternative to conducting either quantitative or qualitative research (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009). However, Mixed methods research is in its adolescence (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009), which may partly explain why it has been subject to relatively little discussion in the accounting literature. In addition, most accounting research, especially in North America, is conducted today within a “largely programmed, theoretical and methodological framework” (Lukka, 2010, p. 110). It implies the use of quantitative methods in a positivist/postpositivist paradigm. Within accounting research, there have been considerable barriers between paradigms, particularly seven between the positivist/postpositivist and other paradigms (see Hopwood, 2007). Given this, Lukka (2010) suggests the incommensurability of paradigms in accounting research, which is confirmed in the BAR area by the lack of papers that have used quantitative and qualitative research methods (Brierley, 2014). Given the rise in the profile of mixed methods research, however, some accounting researchers have called for mixed methods research to be conducted (Modell & Humphrey, 2008; Northcott & Doolin, 2008; Grafton et al., 2011; Brierley, 2014), because of the need to supplement quantitative with qualitative research methods and the emergence of mixed methods research as a research method.² Given that Brierley (2014) has identified that mixed methods research is mainly non-existent in BAR and is at an embryonic stage in its development in accounting research, in general. It is necessary to consider the appropriate paradigm for BAR because it appears that mixed methods research has been conducted in accounting research, in general, before an

adequate discussion of the appropriate paradigm for conducting this research. Before discussing critical realism and pragmatism, the paper discusses what a paradigm means.

3.5 Research Design

The research design refers to a study's overall plan and structure that outlines how the research questions or objectives will be addressed. Yin, R. K. (2018). It encompasses decisions about the research philosophy, approach, data collection methods, sample selection, measurement tools, and data analysis techniques. Creswell, J. W. (2014) The research design provides a roadmap for conducting the study systematically and rigorously, ensuring that the research objectives are met and valid conclusions are drawn. Marshall, C., & Rossman, G. B. (2015). It determines the scope of the study, the types of data to be collected, and the strategies for analysing and interpreting the data. Robson, C. (2016). A well-designed research study is crucial for producing reliable and valid results that contribute to the existing knowledge in the field. The research design is tailored to the specific research objectives and should be aligned with the nature of the research problem and the available resources. Neuman, W. L. (2013) and Babbie, E. (2016).

It serves as a framework to guide the researcher throughout the research process, ensuring that the study is conducted effectively and efficiently Marshall, C., & Rossman, G. B. (2015) and Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015).

3.6 Research Approach

The research approach is a plan and procedure that consists of the steps of broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis and interpretation (Veal, 2005). It is, therefore, based on the nature of the research problem being addressed. The research approach is essentially divided into two categories (Van den Berg and Struwig, 2017):

1. The approach to data collection and
2. The approach of data analysis or reasoning

3.6.1 Types of research approach for data collection

The research approach for data collection includes a qualitative, quantitative, and pragmatic approach (a mixture of quantitative and qualitative techniques) (Dandage et al., 2018). The research approach for data collection has been selected according to the objective of the research and based on the research hypothesis. On the other hand, the required data and information to achieve the aim of the study are also based on the type of research approach the researcher selected field (Adner et al., 2019). Firstly, discuss the three research approaches for data collection separately. Then the researcher explains the chosen research approach for this study and the reasoning behind the selected research approach.

- Qualitative Approach

Exploratory research is the focus of qualitative research. It's utilised to figure out what's driving people's decisions, views, and motives (Bryman, 2006). It offers information about the topic or aids in the development of concepts or hypotheses for quantitative research. Qualitative research is also used to identify trends in thinking and views and go further into an issue. Unstructured and semi-structured approaches are used in the qualitative data-collecting field (Smith and Smith, 2018; Rajakumar et al., 2019). Focus groups (group talks), individual interviews, and participation/observations are all systematic approaches (Smith and Smith, 2018). The sample size is usually limited, and responders are chosen to meet a predetermined quota.

- Quantitative Approach

To determine the size of a problem, quantitative research includes generating numerical data or data that can be turned into meaningful statistics (Brown and Danaher, 2019). It's used to measure attitudes, views, behaviours, and other well-defined characteristics and extrapolate results from a broader sample group. In quantitative research, quantifiable data is used to generate facts and find patterns (Anderson et al., 2018; Apuke, 2017).

Techniques for collecting quantitative data are significantly more organised than methods for collecting qualitative data. Online surveys, paper surveys, mobile surveys, kiosk surveys, face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews, longitudinal studies, and

website surveys are all examples of quantitative data-gathering methods (Samo et al., 2019;Goertzen, 2017)

- Mixed Methods Approach (Pragmatic Approach)

The pragmatic approach to science is choosing the technique that appears most suited to the study topic rather than getting caught up in philosophical disputes over whether the methodology is ideal (Hair, 2009). As a result, pragmatic researchers allow themselves to employ any method, procedure, or approach often connected with quantitative or qualitative research (Taguchi, 2018;Tashakkori et al., 1998). They understand that each strategy has limits and that multiple ways might complement one another.

3.6.1.1 Research Approach for Data Collection for This Study

In the present study, researchers collect both primary and secondary studies to conduct research. According to Wardani and Kusuma (2020) and Maxwell (2019), the primary research would be conducted through a survey questionnaire that would target the employees of PIA Airlines. The researcher collected data using the questionnaire administered to the managers and employees of PIA Airlines in Pakistan to generate quantitative data. Because they gave the clear image desired by researchers and allowed the study to be completed on time, questionnaires were judged to be effective data collection devices. According to Ryan and Deci (2000), survey questionnaires are typically used because they allow respondents to build amicable connections with one another before, during, and after the survey. As (Creamer, 2017; Kothari, 2009) noted, using a questionnaire allowed the study to be completed in a shorter time since a high sample size provides for collecting a great deal of data.

The use of a mixed methods data collection approach is justified for studying the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines for several reasons. Firstly, leadership is a complex phenomenon encompassing both quantitative and qualitative aspects. Quantitative data, such as survey responses and performance metrics, can provide numerical indicators of leadership effectiveness and performance outcomes Cresswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2017). However, these quantitative measures may not capture the nuanced and contextualized understanding of leadership that can be obtained through qualitative data. Qualitative data, such as interviews or open-ended survey responses, allow in-depth exploration of leadership behaviours, perceptions, and

experiences, providing rich insights into the underlying mechanisms and contextual factors.

Secondly, a mixed methods approach allows for triangulation, enhancing the findings' validity and reliability. By using multiple data sources, researchers can corroborate and validate the results obtained from different methods, increasing the overall trustworthiness of the study. Bryman, A. (2016).

Triangulation also enables a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic by integrating diverse perspectives and capturing both breadth and depth in the data analysis. Furthermore, a mixed methods approach enables the exploration of research questions from multiple angles Fetters, M. D., Curry, L. A., & Creswell, J. W. (2013). It allows for a holistic examination of the impact of leadership on performance by examining the quantitative relationships and the qualitative factors that influence these relationships Ivankova, N. V., & Stick, S. L. (2007)

By integrating different data types, researchers can gain a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the complex interplay between leadership behaviours, organizational factors, and performance outcomes Tashakkori, A., & Teddlie, C. (Eds.). (2003)

In the specific context of studying the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA Airlines, a mixed methods approach can provide valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of leadership and its relationship with performance. It can capture quantitative performance indicators, such as financial data and operational metrics, and qualitative aspects, including team member perceptions, customer experiences, and organizational culture.

This comprehensive approach can inform evidence-based decision-making and help identify areas for improvement in leadership practices to enhance organizational performance.

The figure below explains the route for secondary data and primary methods which also represent as phase one and phase two.

Figure: Secondary and Primary Methods Route

Figure 5 Secondary and primary method route

The quantitative Research approach for data collection is suitable for this research because this study is based on the survey to collect numerical data from customers (Mathieu et al., 2020; Bone and Mowen, 2010) and employees of PIA airline in Pakistan. The qualitative method could be problematic in this research as the number

of samples is 375. To find out the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA airlines, the researcher required a large number of responses to justify the researcher objectives and test the hypothesis in the matter of literature review.

Quantitative research means developing numerical data or data that may be converted into valuable statistics to quantify an issue (Sileyew, 2019). It quantifies attitudes, views, behaviours, and other specific factors while generalising conclusions from a broader sample group (Bloomfield and Fisher, 2019; Apuke, 2017). Quantitative research is a type of study that uses quantifiable data to create facts and find patterns. Techniques for collecting quantitative data are significantly more organised than methods for collecting qualitative data. Online surveys, paper surveys, mobile surveys, and kiosk surveys, face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews, longitudinal studies, and website surveys are all examples of quantitative data gathering methods (Soleas, 2020; Kan and Gero, 2017). So, there are a variety of data collection methods for the researcher according to the research objective and hypothesis. Also, flexible options are available for the researcher in terms of time and budget for this research.

It is mentioned above that for this research, and data would be collected through primary resources and secondary resources. To measure the performance of PIA airlines in Pakistan, a balanced scorecard tool would be used. The researcher focuses on four dimensions:

- Financial condition
- Learning and growth of the airline
- The internal process of the airline
- Customer perspectives

To examine the performance of PIA over ten years, the researcher discovers yearly reports and financial statements over the previous ten years field (Kamper, 2020).

The researcher followed the three online websites of customer reviews, i.e., SKYTRAX Trust pilot Trip Advisor. Data and information about PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan and Singapore Airlines' customer services and other services have been collected from these websites, and benchmarking has been done. Because of online sources, the researcher finds out the customer perceptions about airlines. And find out the rating of each airline, which is enough to measure the airline's customer service, so the researcher does not need to collect primary data in this matter. All secondary data would be present in numerical form to analyse the results (PIA, 2020; Smith and Smith, 2018).

On the other hand, primary data would be collected through a self-made structured questionnaire (Tumewu et al., 2017;e Silva et al., 2021). The questionnaire was developed based on the research hypotheses and research objectives. Previous authors used a quantitative approach and a qualitative approach in their study. Some authors adopt the mixed approach for their research (Ryan and Deci, 2000; Tashakkori et al., 1998). But few studies select a quantitative data collection approach with a secondary data collection approach for their studies. This is one of the gaps in research studies because; the researcher uses secondary quantitative data and primary quantitative data approach to justify the researcher's objectives (Tobi and Kampen, 2018; Bloomfield and Fisher, 2019). Furthermore, the selection of the researcher approach for data collection is based on the research objective and nature of the research.

3.6.2 Research Approach for Data Analysis

Approaches to data analysis are of three types:

When deciding whether to adopt an inductive or deductive strategy (McLeod, 2018; Wardani and Kusuma, 2020), the essential considerations are the goal of your study and the methods that are most suited to test a hypothesis, explore a new or developing topic within the field, or answer particular research questions.

- **Inductive**

Inductive methods are more frequently linked with qualitative research, whereas deductive methods are more commonly associated with quantitative methods (McLeod, 2018). Moreover, there are no strict regulations, and some qualitative research may be based on deduction.

- **Deductive**

A hypothesis is usually the starting point for a deductive method, whereas research questions are often used to restrict the area of a study in an inductive approach (Signoret and Leroy, 2021).

Inductive techniques are frequently focused on investigating new phenomena or looking at already investigated phenomena from a fresh perspective, whereas deductive approaches are usually focused on the causation (Azungah, 2018; Bonell et al., 2018). The primary distinction between inductive and deductive research techniques is that a deductive approach is focused on testing theory (Van den Berg and Struwig, 2017; Signoret and Leroy, 2021). In contrast, an inductive approach is concerned with generating new ideas from evidence.

- **Abductive**

Abduction is selecting or inventing a provisional hypothesis to explain a particular empirical case or data set better than any other candidate hypotheses and pursuing this hypothesis through further investigation (Kan and Gero, 2017; Charmaz, 2020); Abduction is about discovering new concepts, ideas, and explanations by finding surprising phenomena, data, or events that pre-existing knowledge cannot explain. In abduction, qualitative researchers employ a selective and creative approach to look at how the data supports or contradicts existing ideas or hypotheses and how the evidence may need changes to existing understandings (Douven, 2011). They go beyond the facts and pre-existing theoretical knowledge to investigate, interpret, and explain the data by changing, expanding or rejecting theory as needed or bringing old concepts together in new ways (Thornberg and Charmaz, 2014).

The following table illustrates the major differences between deductive, inductive and abductive research approaches in terms of logic, generalizability, use of data and theory.

	<u>Deduction</u>	<u>Induction</u>	<u>Abductive</u>
Logic	In a deductive inference, when the premises are true, the conclusion must also be true	In an inductive inference, known premises are used to generate untested conclusions	In an abductive inference, known premises are used to generate testable conclusions
Generalizability	Generalising from the general to the specific	Generalising from the specific to the general	Generalising from the interactions between the specific and the general
Use of data	Data collection is used to evaluate propositions or hypotheses related to an existing theory	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns and create a conceptual framework	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns, locate these in a conceptual framework and test this through subsequent data collection and so forth

3.6.2.1 Research Approach for Data Analysis Adopted

The deductive research approach for data analysis is the best fit for the comprehensive understanding of the research problem stated in chapter one. The deductive approach starts with the existing theory, and from that theory, the hypothesis has been developed, and for testing the developed hypothesis, data would be collected (Charmaz, 2020).

And after the analysis of data, the results decided whether the developed hypothesis is true or false. This investigation is based on the research on leadership impact on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan. The researcher studied a variety of literature reviews related to the topic. Many authors have written about the relationship between leadership and the performance of origination.

This is the first justification for selecting the deductive approach for data analysis for this research, as theories related to this research already exist (Pearse, 2021). The first step for the deduction approach is to start with an existing theory. And next step is formulating the hypothesis based on the current theory. So, from the literature review in chapter two, the researcher develops the seven hypotheses for this research. All hypotheses have been written in detail in chapter two. In the chapter of the literature review, all six independent and dependent variables mention two moderators for this research. In this section, the researcher explains a little about the hypothesis and why this study adopts a deductive approach to data analysis. Leadership style has a positive relation with leadership conduct (Pearse, 2021). Decision-making and leader communication have a positive influence on the leadership conduct (Paoletti et al., 2020), and leadership conduct has a positive impact on PIA performance.

Besides this, corruption moderates the relationship between decision-making and leadership conduct. Politics moderate the relationship between leadership conduct and the performance (Mudallal et al., 2017;Fattah, 2017) of PIA Airlines. The researcher uncovered that all the hypotheses mentioned above, and variables already exist, and previous authors developed different theories to justify the relationship between variables. The deduction approach is appropriate for this research when hypotheses are generated from the literature review.

Steps in Measurement in Scale Development

Figure 6 Steps in measurement in scale development

Secondly, the data collected to test the hypothesis is the third step in the deductive approach for data analysis Churchill Jr (1979). The researcher developed the research hypotheses from the literature review and started collecting data related to the research hypothesis. For testing the hypothesis, the researcher required the best, and appropriate data and information to justify/verify the previous theories are valid or not—this approach aids in assessing the relationship between conceptual framework and fundamental research.

3.7 Research Strategies

Research strategies refer to the approach or plan researchers adopt to conduct their studies. They outline the methods, techniques, and procedures used to gather, analyse, and interpret data to address the research objectives or questions. Research strategies guide the entire research process and serve as a roadmap for researchers.

There are several commonly used research strategies, including:

Experimental research aims to establish cause-and-effect relationships. (Trochim & Donnelly, 2008) While the Survey research strategy involves collecting data through structured questionnaires or interviews to gather information from many respondents. Surveys measure a population's attitudes, opinions, behaviours, or characteristics (Babbie, 2016; Fowler Jr., 2013). Moreover, Case study research aims to provide a detailed understanding of a specific phenomenon, context, or organization (Yin, 2018; Stake, 2006)

According to (Reason & Bradbury, 2008; McNiff, Lomax, & Whitehead, 2018), Ethnographic research aims to deeply understand the participants' culture, behaviour, and social interactions. Action research good for emphasizes collaboration, reflection, and iterative cycles of planning, action, observation, and reflection (Glaser & Strauss, 2017; Charmaz, 2014)

Mixed methods research strategy combines quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques to understand a research problem comprehensively (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010).

Researchers select the most appropriate research strategy based on the nature of their research questions, available resources, and the desired level of depth and breadth in their study.

3.7.1 Survey Strategy Benefits

The survey strategy is a widely used research approach that can be justified for several reasons:

- **Broad data collection:** Surveys allow researchers to collect data from many participants, providing a broad perspective on the research topic. It enables exploring a wide range of opinions, attitudes, behaviours, or characteristics within a specific population (Dillman, Smyth, & Christian, 2014; Fowler Jr., 2013).

- Standardized data: Surveys employ standardized questionnaires or interview protocols, ensuring consistency in data collection. It facilitates comparability across respondents and enhances the reliability of the findings (Groves et al., 2009; Saris & Gallhofer, 2014).
- Efficient and cost-effective: Surveys are relatively more cost-effective than other research methods. They can reach many participants quickly, reducing time and resource requirements (Dillman et al., 2014; Fowler Jr., 2013).
- Generalizability: Surveys often aim to gather representative samples of a target population, allowing researchers to generalize their findings to a larger population and survey results can provide insights applicable to a broader context (Groves et al., 2009; Saris & Gallhofer, 2014).
- Quantitative analysis: Surveys generate quantitative data that can be analyzed using statistical techniques. It identifies patterns, trends, and relationships between variables, providing a strong empirical basis for conclusions (Fink, 2019; Saris & Gallhofer, 2014).
- Large-scale studies: Surveys are beneficial for large-scale studies that require a substantial amount of data. They can be administered to diverse groups across different locations, making it feasible to collect extensive data sets (Dillman et al., 2014; Fowler Jr., 2013).
- Anonymous and unbiased responses: Surveys provide a degree of anonymity to respondents, which can encourage honest and unbiased responses. Participants may feel more comfortable expressing their opinions or disclosing sensitive information than other research methods (Dillman et al., 2014; Groves et al., 2009).
- Longitudinal studies: Surveys can be conducted repeatedly, enabling researchers to examine changes in attitudes, behaviours, or characteristics within a population. Longitudinal surveys provide valuable insights into trends and dynamics over an extended period (Fink, 2019; Saris & Gallhofer, 2014).

Using the survey strategy, researchers can gather comprehensive and representative data, perform quantitative analysis, and make informed decisions based on empirical evidence. However, careful attention should be paid to survey design, sampling techniques, and data analysis methods to ensure validity and reliability in the findings.

3.8 Techniques And Procedures

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the research regarding data collection and analysis processes, drawing upon the Research Onion framework proposed by Saunders et al. (2012). This report will outline the various data collection and analysis stages, discussing the methods employed, their alignment with the chosen research philosophy, and the analysis techniques used to derive meaningful insights from the collected data.

Research Philosophy and Data Collection Approach: The first layer of the Research Onion focuses on the research philosophy guiding the study. The chosen research philosophy in this study is pragmatism, as Creswell and Creswell and Creswell (2018) advocate. Pragmatism emphasizes the practicality and flexibility of research methods, allowing for a mixed-methods approach. This approach involves the combination of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the research topic.

Research Design and Data Collection Methods: The second layer of the Research Onion involves research design and selecting appropriate data collection methods. Primary data collection methods, including a survey questionnaire, were employed in this study. Secondary data sources, such as airline financial records, learning & growth and customer views, were also utilized. The selection of these methods aligns with the pragmatic research philosophy, providing a well-rounded and comprehensive data collection process (Saunders et al., 2016).

Data Analysis Techniques: Moving further into the Research Onion, the third layer encompasses the data analysis techniques applied to the collected data. Quantitative data from the survey questionnaire underwent statistical analysis using software such as SPSS, as Field (2018) recommended. Descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, and factor analyses were used to identify patterns, relationships, and potential associations between variables. Qualitative data gathered from customer reviews underwent comparison in the last few years of analysis, following the guidelines of Braun and Clarke (2019), to identify recurring themes and patterns within the responses.

Interpretation and Findings: The fourth layer of the Research Onion involves interpreting the analysed data and the subsequent findings. The results obtained from the data analysis were carefully examined and interpreted to address the research

objectives and questions. By integrating the quantitative and qualitative findings, a comprehensive understanding of the research topic emerged, allowing for valid and reliable conclusions to be drawn (Saunders et al., 2016).

By adhering to a structured and systematic approach, the study ensured the credibility, validity, and reliability of the data collected and analysed, contributing to the existing knowledge in the Field (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Saunders et al., 2016).

3.9 Ethical Consideration

When researching the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA (Pakistan International Airlines) using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) framework, there are several ethical considerations to keep in mind. These considerations include:

- **Informed Consent:** Ensure that all participants, such as leaders, employees, and stakeholders involved in the research, provide informed consent before their inclusion. They should understand the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits and have the right to participate or withdraw without negative consequences.
- **Confidentiality and Anonymity:** Protect the privacy and confidentiality of participants' personal information. Use codes or pseudonyms to ensure anonymity in reporting and disseminating research findings. Safeguard any sensitive data obtained during research to prevent potential harm or unintended consequences.
- **Non-coercion and Voluntary Participation:** Ensure that participation in the research is voluntary and not influenced by coercion, manipulation, or pressure from organisational or leadership figures. Participants should be free to decline participation or withdraw from the study without facing any negative consequences.
- **Avoiding Harm:** Take precautions to minimise potential harm to participants, such as avoiding intrusive questioning or activities that may cause emotional distress. Be aware of power dynamics between researchers and participants, especially in a hierarchical organisational setting, and strive to maintain a respectful and supportive research environment.
- **Transparency and Full Disclosure:** Communicate the research findings' purpose, methods, and intended use to all stakeholders involved. Provide

accurate and transparent information to leaders and employees about the nature and implications of the study, ensuring they have a comprehensive understanding of the research objectives and potential impacts on their work and the organisation.

- **Conflict of Interest:** Disclose any potential conflicts of interest that may arise during the research, such as financial relationships, personal biases, or affiliations that could influence the objectivity and integrity of the study. Strive for impartiality and ensure the research is conducted with integrity and intellectual honesty.
- **Responsible Data Handling:** Adhere to ethical data collection, storage, and analysis guidelines. Respect data protection and privacy regulations, ensuring that data is securely stored, and access is limited to authorised individuals. Use aggregated or anonymised data whenever possible to protect the identity and privacy of participants.
- **Reporting and Dissemination:** Present research findings accurately, honestly, and without distortion. Clearly distinguish between interpretations and objective data. Give appropriate credit to all contributors and acknowledge the limitations of the research. Strive for the open and responsible dissemination of research results, contributing to the body of knowledge while respecting intellectual property rights and ethical guidelines.
- **Equity and Fairness:** Ensure fairness in participant selection, data collection, and analysis processes. Avoid discrimination or bias based on gender, age, ethnicity, or organisational hierarchy. Strive for inclusivity and equal representation of diverse perspectives to enhance the validity and fairness of the research.
- **The benefit to Participants and the Organization:** Consider the potential benefits the research may bring participants and PIA. Aim to generate insights and recommendations that can contribute positively to leadership development, organisational performance, and the well-being of employees. Communicate the potential benefits to participants and stakeholders clearly and honestly.
- **Avoiding Manipulation or Exploitation:** Ensure that the research does not involve any form of manipulation, exploitation, or undue influence. Respect

the autonomy and rights of participants and ensure that their involvement in the study is based on their free will and voluntary consent.

- **Professional Integrity:** Conduct the research with the highest standards of professional integrity. Adhere to honesty, objectivity, and accountability principles throughout the research process. Maintain academic rigour, avoid misrepresentation or distortion of findings, and uphold ethical guidelines and codes of conduct relevant to the research domain.
- **Ethical Review and Approval:** Seek appropriate approval from relevant institutional review boards or ethics committees. Follow established ethical guidelines and regulations specific to the research field, ensuring compliance with ethical standards and principles set forth by governing bodies.
- **Continuous Ethical Reflection:** Engage in continuous ethical reflection and critical self-assessment throughout the research process. Regularly evaluate and re-evaluate the ethical implications of the research design, methods, and potential impacts. Seek input from colleagues, mentors, or ethical review boards to ensure the research maintains the highest ethical standards.
- **Long-term Consequences and Social Impact:** Consider the research's potential long-term consequences and social impact on PIA, its stakeholders, and the broader society. Strive to generate knowledge and recommendations that can contribute to sustainable leadership practices, organisational improvement, and the advancement of the aviation industry.

Maintaining a robust ethical framework throughout the research process is essential to safeguard all study participants' rights, well-being, and dignity. Adhering to these ethical considerations ensures that the research on the impact of leadership on PIA's performance using the BSC remains ethically sound and beneficial for all stakeholders.

3.10 Research Questionnaire

A questionnaire is a type of research instrument that consists of questions designed to collect data from respondents. Questionnaires are like written interviews in that they collect information. They can be done in person, over the phone, on the computer, or by mail. (Park et al., 2020)

Questionnaires are a low-cost, fast, and practical approach to collecting vast amounts of data from many individuals. Because the researcher is not required to be present while the surveys are completed, data may be obtained quickly.

Questionnaires are a cost-effective and rapid way to assess a big group of people's behaviour, attitudes, preferences, views, and intentions (McLeod, 2018).

3.10.1 Research Questionnaire Design

The researcher follows some steps to develop the questionnaire to collect the data from respondents. In the first step, the researcher makes sure that all questions in the questionnaire address the research aims. The next step is what types of questions would include in the questionnaire (Toussaint et al., 2020; de Jong et al., 2018). The researcher selected closed-ended questions to develop the research questionnaire. The third step is the appropriate length of the questionnaire. It is unlikely for the respondents to complete the questionnaire if the length is too long. In the next step, the researcher ensures that the research questions' order is in the questionnaire. The researcher arranges the questions from the least sensitive to the more sensitive and from the general to the more specific questions (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012; Hair, 2009). This arrangement is because respondents should not answer the following question under the influence of the previous question. The researcher also considers the terminology when writing the research questions (Van den Berg and Struwig, 2017). The researcher would make sure that questions would be simple, to the point and easy to understand.

Moreover, considering the respondents who are employees of PIA Airlines, the researcher uses appropriate language and appropriate vocabulary, so people find it easy to answer all questions correctly. Presentation is another important factor in research questionnaire design. The researcher designed a questionnaire that looks professional with clear and concise instructions. The purpose of the study is written clearly at the start, and the researcher introduced herself to the audience, so people feel confident when filling out the questionnaire (Kopytkov and Samchuk, 2020; Yousef, 2019).

On the other hand, the researcher must guarantee that the respondent's personal information, such as name and address, is kept private. As a result, questionnaires help investigate complex issues since respondents are more honest when anonymous. Confidentiality of the questionnaire should also limit the risk of psychological damage, such as humiliation (Anderson et al., 2018; Mumford, 2017). Before completing the questionnaire, participants must offer informed permission and be aware that they have

the right to withdraw their information at any point throughout the survey. A five-point Likert scale was designed to examine all the predicted factors. The lowest weight of 1 denotes poor ratings by respondents, while the most significant weight of 5 signifies good ratings by responders using the desktop research (Johansen et al., 2017; Chyung et al., 2017); secondary sources were consulted to gather data. These sources included library textbooks, publications, and the personal files of respondents from their different companies.

Finally, once the questionnaire has been completed, the researcher would conduct the pilot study to make sure the questionnaire is free from error. And questionnaire is practically perfect for data collection (Bell et al., 2018).

3.10.2 Developing the Research Questionnaire

For developing the questionnaire for the data collection, the researcher first made a 100-research statement based on research objectives and research hypotheses as explained earlier in the chapter that the researcher hypothesis was developed from a literature review and based on the findings of previous authors (Lowe, 2019). The 100 research statements are also related to previous studies, but gaps in studies are included. After making 100 research statements, the researcher reviewed and made the research questions. When research questions are prepared, the researcher divided the questions into separate categories according to research objectives. Because this research involved secondary data and primary data, the researcher separates the entire research questions related to secondary data. After secondary data questions were separated, the number of question left was related to the primary data (Mardanya et al., 2021). The researcher reviewed again and reduced the length of questions under the supervision of the lead supervisor. The final questionnaire was consisting of forty-two research questions that are related to the research hypothesis. A five-point Likert scale was designed to examine all the predicted factors. The lowest weight of 1 denotes poor ratings by respondents, while the greatest weight of 5 signifies good ratings by responders using desktop research; secondary sources were consulted to gather data. These sources included library textbooks, publications, and the personal files of respondents from their different companies (de Jong et al., 2018).

When developing the questionnaire, the researcher ensures that every variable and moderator has at least three research questions to find the relationship between the variables and test the hypotheses. A total of six variables and two moderators are

present in the conceptual framework of this research. Leadership style, leadership conduct, decision-making, leaders' communication, uses of advanced technology and performance of PIA are research variables. And political inference and corruption are two moderators for the research. The purpose of naming all variables and moderators in this section is to understand better what the researcher explained above. For example, the researcher should make three questions for leadership style and at least three for leadership conduct, the same as moderators. If the appropriate number of research questions for each variable were not included, there would be a problem when the researcher runs the statistical test to find the relationship between variables and the impact of moderators. The results would not be accurate, and the findings would be missing and incorrect.

The researcher developed the research questionnaire in three sections (Chyung et al., 2017; Kopytkov and Samchuk, 2020). The first section is about general instructions. The second part is about the personal information of respondents. And the last part is based on the main body of research questions.

In the first section, the researcher explained the purpose of the study, introduced herself and mentioned the ethical confirmation for respondents.

The respondent's personal information is collected in the second section of the questionnaire. A total of five questions have been written to get the personal information of respondents, which is also an essential piece of data to conduct this research. Gender, age group, qualification, work experience, and respondents' designation are shown in order of personal questions (Arora, 2018).

In the last section, all research questions developed from the literature review have been written in the main body part of the questionnaire. The lead supervisor and the second supervisor approved the final questionnaire (Shen et al., 2019).

The researcher made the questionnaire in Microsoft Word format. The aim of the researcher to collect data was face-to-face. The researcher knows that contacting the respondent personally is better than sending a questionnaire through email or post. Explaining the research to respondents' face-to-face leads to more accurate and fair responses to the questionnaire.

Because of the pandemic, the researcher could not meet personally with the respondents and get the filled questionnaire. To solve this issue, the researcher prepares the online questionnaire by using QuestionPro. QuestionPro is free online survey software and tool that help the researcher to design an online questionnaire and make a link for the

questionnaire. The researcher copied the link and sent it through email, text and chat box. QuestionPro also records all the responses. It also explains how many visited the link, how many completed the questionnaire, how many dropouts, the total number of responses, and the average time to complete the questionnaire.

3.11 Data Collection

The present study utilized both primary and secondary data collection methods. For the primary data, a survey questionnaire was administered to the managers and employees of PIA Airlines in Pakistan, following the approach outlined by Johansen et al. (2017). It allowed the researchers to gather quantitative data that clearly understood the participants' perspectives. Questionnaires were chosen as an effective data collection tool due to their ability to establish a rapport between respondents and researchers, as emphasized by Morgan (2007). Additionally, using a questionnaire enabled the study to be completed efficiently within a shorter timeframe, as highlighted by Creamer (2017) and Kothari (2009).

Regarding secondary research, information was gathered from the annual reports of PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines to obtain insights into the financial statements. Furthermore, customer reviews regarding the airlines were collected from reputable online feedback platforms such as SKYTRAX, Trust Pilot, and Trip Advisor. Additionally, a comprehensive understanding of leadership in the airline industry, leadership styles in Pakistan, political issues, and corruption within PIA Airlines was obtained through a review of peer-reviewed articles, journals, previous research, and books, utilizing both online and offline research methods.

3.11.1 The First Phase: Secondary Data Collection

The researcher employed the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) model to examine leadership's impact on the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan. The initial step involved gathering relevant secondary data from sources such as annual reports, business reports, and online websites (Bujang & Baharum, 2017). Financial statements for PIA Airlines spanning the past ten years (2011-2020) were collected, along with five years' worth (2016-2020) of financial statements for Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines (PIA, 2020). To ensure accuracy and reliability, audited financial reports were used. The researcher focused on operating revenue, operating expenses, operating profit/loss,

fixed assets, current assets, fixed liabilities, current liabilities, number of employees, earnings per share, and share closing price (shenanigans, 2012). Furthermore, various financial ratios were calculated, including the current ratio, return on capital employed ratio, gross profit margin, net profit margin, and growth and learning ratios. These ratios provided a comprehensive assessment of the airlines' performance.

Measurement scale for secondary data

Figure 1 measurement scale of secondary data

Construct	Indicator
<i>Airline output measurement</i>	Operating revenue (OR)
Financial perspectives	Return on investment (ROI)
	Return on assets (ROA)
	Net income (NI)
<i>Airline input measurement</i>	Revenue passengers
Customer perspectives	Customer reviews
Internal business perspectives	Leadership conduct
	Decision making
	Corruption in internal business
	Political interference
	Uses of Advance Technology
Learning and growth perspectives	Learning and growth ratio

On the other hand, the researcher selected the top three online customer reviews websites named: SKYTRAX, Trust Pilot and Trip Advisor. The researcher read nearly a thousand pieces of customer feedback from each airline and made a table with customer complaints and good customer experiences. The researcher made separate tables for customer complaints and good customer experience with the number of counts for each category and calculated the percentage.

The researcher presented all the above data in tables and graphs, a pie chart, and a bar graph to understand the reader better. In the first section, the researcher compares the performance of PIA Airlines in the last ten years. And then, in the second section, the researcher has done benchmarking to compare the performance of PIA Airlines with Delta, Sri Lankan and Singapore Airlines in the last five years, i.e., 2016 to 2020.

3.11.2 The Second Phase: Quantitative Data Collection

This section aims to explain the quantitative data collection procedure after the secondary data had been collected. The researcher investigates the PIA performance through a balanced scorecard in which the internal business perceptiveness was missing (Fooladvand et al., 2015). The researcher needs to know how the PIA Airlines system works internally. To seek the internal process of the airline, the researcher developed a questionnaire that consists of twenty-two researcher questions based on the research objective. After the pilot study, when the researcher is confident about the questionnaire's effectiveness and usefulness, the questionnaire is sent through the Internet with QuestionPro links to respondents (Al-Alawi, 2018). At first, the researcher approached the respondents through LinkedIn accounts and then Facebook accounts. There are few responses to the questionnaire. After this, the researcher used her social contacts with PIA employees and requested them to circulate the questionnaire among other PIA staff including top and middle management. It is also called the snowball-sampling technique (Bell et al., 2018).

3.12 The Pilot Study

The questionnaire for evaluating the hypotheses was changed after secondary examination by the explanatory research. Following that, essential changes were made for use in the actual survey (O'Neill and Palmer, 2004; Yang et al., 2011) to determine whether the constructs are valid and the measurement scales are capable of evaluating reliability through the pilot study (Malhotra and Birks, 2000).

The creation of the questionnaire and measuring equipment used in the primary survey is linked to a pilot study (pre-test) (Saunders et al., 2007). The pilot study aims to assess the important requirements during instrument purification, such as testing questions wording, sequence, form and layout, question difficulty and instruction, familiarity with respondents, response rate, questionnaire completion time, and analysis process, according to the researchers (Malhotra and Birks, 2000; Denscombe, 2009). The purpose of the pilot research is to clarify the questionnaire such that there are no confusing items (Veal, 2005), respondents can answer the questions, and data recording is not difficult (Welman and Kruger, 2001). In order to assess the survey's timeliness and clarity, the constructs' reliability, and manipulation checks, respondents should have no problem replying (Saunders et al., 2007). The results of the pilot research were

utilized to improve the measuring equipment and make changes to the measurements to provide reliable and valid results. It enables responders to answer questions without difficulty (Malhotra and Galletta, 1999).

Between January and February 2021, questionnaires were delivered. By the deadline, 50 questionnaires had been gathered. Due to the significant amount of missing data and the poor quality of the replies, 22 questions were deleted. A total of 30 complete surveys were gathered. The demographic profile of the consumer's pre-test sample is shown in Table 4.16. After then, there was a lengthy process of questionnaire testing and piloting. According to (Saunders et al., 2007), the pilot research sample size should be 20 to 40 respondents for a small-scale test of what the survey would entail, including all activities included in the final survey (Malhotra and Birks, 2000). For the pilot study, 30 professional employees working in Pakistan with different fields completed the questionnaire. Participants in the pilot study were not requested to participate in the final study. This is because if they have previously participated in the pilot, it may influence their behavior (Malhotra and Birks, 2000).

Table 1 Demographical Statistics of Employees

Demographic Statistics of Employees

S#	Variables	Categories	Percentages
1	Age	Below 20 years	8
		21-30 years	41
		31-40 years	66
		41-50 years	38
		51-60 years	10
		Above 61Years	4
2	Gender	Female	28.7
		Male	71.3
3	Qualification	High school	8
		Bachelor’s Degree	25.3
		Master’s Degree	46.2
		PhD	18.2
		Others	2.3

4	Experience	Less than 5 years 5-10 years 11-15 years 16-20 years Over 20 Years	14.2 26.5 30.9 22.5 5.9
5	Job title	Senior managers Assistant managers Technical team Crew member Ground floor employees	15.2 28.6 22.4 8.4 25.4

Questionnaires were distributed in the PIA for the pilot study, and we got back valid 30 responses. Table indicated that from all valid respondents, the first category of demographics stated the age of the respondents, which shows that 8% were below 20 years while 41% were from 21-30 years of age and 66% were of the 31-40 years while 38% were from 41-50 years of age while 10% were from 51-60 years of age, and 4% were above 60 years of age the second category indicated that of the total respondent's females were 28.7% and 71.3% were males. The next type showed the Qualification of the respondents. As per results, about 8.0% of the respondent having high school education included in the target population, while 25.3% have bachelor's degrees, while 46.2% have master's degrees, while 18.2% and others have 2.3%. The next category showed years of experience of the respondent; respondents were performing their jobs having experience less than five years were 14.2%, 26.5% having experience of about 5-10 years, 30.9% having experience of about 11-15 years, 22.5% having experience of about 16-20 years, 5.9% having expertise of over 20 years. About 15.2% are senior managers, 28.6 % are assistant managers, 22.4 % are technical team, 8.4 % are crew members, and 25.4 % are ground floor employees.

3.12.1 Items of Pilot Surveys

Table 2 Items of Pilot Surveys

Items	Skewness	Kurtosis	Factor loading
1. When assigning tasks, I consider people's skills and interests.	-3.24	2.4	0.33
2. I am effective with the detailed aspects of my work.	2.33	3.55	0.36
3. Managing people and resources is one of my strengths.	2.55	4.44	0.22
4. In my work, I enjoy responding to people's requests and concerns.	1.33	4.33	0.44
5. Obtaining and allocating resources is a challenging aspect for me.	3.33	5.55	0.42
6. PIA airline productivity has not improved in the last ten years.	1.22	3.44	0.33
7. I make clear to employees what they must do and achieve.	3.44	0.23	0.44
8. I would like to get good results consistently.	3.12	1.33	0.37
9. Identify the achievements of the team is part of my job.	2.33	4.55	0.47
10. I give employees sufficient scope to do their job.	.44	.48	0.32
11. Control of important things is not perfect for airline performance.	-3.44	1.24	0.39
12. The key to successful conflict resolution is respecting my opponent	- 2.37	1.55	0.23
13. I use my emotional energy to motivate others.	3.55	4.44	0.24
14. I am not big fan of employee's own creativity.	1.36	4.35	0.34
15. Making strategic plans for my airline is a problem for me.	3.39	5.51	0.40

16. PIA sales revenue has exceeded that of our competitors.	1.21	3.22	0.31
17. The best decision will be the one with the most significant consent.	3.77	.411	0.55
18. I consider the moral and ethical consequences of my choices.	3.19	1.32	0.31
19. I felt bored when discussing airline values and philosophy.	2.31	2.55	0.36
20. I am flexible about making changes in our airline.	.44	.48	0.32
21. In my decision-making, the facts are more important than principles.	-3.24	2.4	0.31
22. I make up my mind about things regardless of what others think.	1.77	.400	0.22
23. I feel it difficult to think clearly when I must decide something in a hurry.	2.19	1.32	0.31
24. I am good at finding practical solutions to the problem.	0.31	1.55	0.36
25. My action shows people what I want from them.	0.44	.48	0.32
26. PIA airlines profit rate has exceeded every year.	0.33	0.44	.66
27. PIA airlines have enough technology to improve airlines performance.	0.66	1.22	.55
28. Giving regular feedback to employees is good for airline performance.	-0.44	1.22	.64
29. Customer reviews are essential for PIA airlines performance.	.33	.99	.52
30. I am in favor to arrange employees' meetings.	0.22	0.82	0.32
31. Communication must be free of filler words	- 0.21	4.33	0.40
32. Employee needs the guidance, coaching and support to do a good job.	-0.12	0.39	0.23

33. I am in favour of democratic leadership.	0.13	0.94	0.58
34. Political interference has a terrible impact on PIA airlines performance. Political interference	1.22	0.44	0.66
35. Hiring employees under political pressure. Political interference	0.33	1.44	0.72
36. PIA airlines have good security at airports.	1.55	2.59	0.76
37. Corruptions in PIA are damaging airlines.	1.33	2.13	0.62
38. Leaders elected not according to their qualifications.	- 1.23	0.84	0.66
39. Responsible people for plane crashes must punish.	0.49	1.40	0.78
40. In your opinion, pilots understand their responsibilities.	1.44	2.29	0.63
41. PIA management follow strict technical procedures to maintain check and balance.	- 0.33	2.36	0.54
42. PIA has a flawed aviation communication system.	1.23	0.88	0.56

3.12.2 Improvement through pilot study

In the context of a pilot study, using skewness, kurtosis, factor loading analysis, and reducing the number of questions in a questionnaire can lead to several improvements. Here is how each of these techniques can contribute to enhancing the research process:

- **Skewness and Kurtosis:** Skewness and kurtosis are statistical measures used to assess the distributional characteristics of data. In a pilot study, analysing the skewness and kurtosis of the data collected from the questionnaire can provide insights into the distributional properties of the responses. This analysis helps researchers understand the data's symmetry, tail heaviness, and presence of outliers.

- **Skewness:** Skewness measures the asymmetry of the data distribution. Positive skewness indicates a longer tail on the right side, while negative skewness indicates a longer tail on the left side. By examining skewness, researchers can identify any significant deviations from a normal distribution and adjust if necessary.
- **Kurtosis:** Kurtosis measures the peakedness or flatness of the data distribution. Positive kurtosis indicates a more peaked distribution with heavier tails, while negative kurtosis indicates a flatter distribution. Evaluating kurtosis helps researchers determine if the data deviates from a normal distribution and may require further investigation or transformation.

Analysing skewness and kurtosis in a pilot study can help researchers identify any anomalies or issues related to the data distribution and guide decisions on potential data transformations or adjustments in the main study.

- **Factor Loading Analysis:** Factor loading analysis is commonly used in exploratory factor analysis (EFA) or confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to examine the strength and pattern of relationships between observed variables and underlying latent constructs. In a pilot study, factor loading analysis can help researchers assess the construct validity of the questionnaire items.

By examining the factor loadings, researchers can determine if the items align with the intended constructs and if any items exhibit weak or inconsistent relationships with the factors. This analysis allows for refinement and modification of the questionnaire by removing or rephrasing items that do not contribute significantly to measuring the constructs of interest.

- **Reducing the Number of Questions:** In a pilot study, researchers may find that certain questionnaire items need to be revised, clarified, or contribute more substantially to the research objectives. Through data analysis and feedback from pilot study participants, researchers can identify items that can be eliminated or consolidated to reduce redundancy and respondent burden.

Reducing the number of questions in the final questionnaire has several benefits. It improves the clarity and brevity of the instrument, making it more user-friendly for participants. It also minimizes the potential for response fatigue and increases the

overall response rate. Additionally, a brief questionnaire with focused and relevant questions enhances the quality and reliability of the data collected.

By employing techniques such as skewness and kurtosis analysis, factor loading analysis, and reducing the number of questions based on pilot study findings, researchers can refine and improve their measurement instrument, enhance construct validity, and optimize the efficiency and effectiveness of data collection in the main study. The final questionnaire is in the appendixes.

3.13 Content Validity

When conducting quantitative research, it is crucial to consider the dependability and validity of the procedures and measurements employed. The accuracy of a procedure is determined by its validity, which entails the ability to measure what it intends to measure and produce findings that align closely with real-world values. Validating factors can be categorized into four types (Audemard, 2020). Construct validity assesses whether a measurement tool accurately captures the item being studied. Establishing the overall validity of a procedure; is essential (Vabalas et al., 2019). Constructs represent intangible qualities that can be indirectly observed through associated indicators, such as trends or patterns (Mathieu et al., 2020). Constructs can pertain to human attributes and broader concepts relevant to organizations and social groups, such as gender equality, corporate social responsibility, and freedom of expression (Furr & Heuckeroth, 2019). Ensuring that the chosen measurement technique aligns with the intended construct is crucial for construct validity. Therefore, to ensure indicators and measures possess construct validity (Choi et al., 2018), researchers must ensure that questionnaires are appropriately designed based on relevant information and research objectives.

The validity of a test is crucial in ensuring accurate measurement and assessment. Content validity examines whether a test adequately represents the construct it intends to measure. It is essential for testing, surveys, and measurement methods to encompass all essential aspects of the subject to generate reliable findings (Furr & Heuckeroth, 2019). Weaknesses in the measurement process or the inclusion of irrelevant factors can compromise content validity.

Face validity, however, assesses how appropriate the test appears on the surface. While similar to content validity (Almanasreh et al., 2019), face validity is a more subjective and informal evaluation. It is considered an imperfect form of validity due to its

subjective nature, but it can be valuable in the early stages of test development (binti Daud, 2021).

Criterion validity determines how closely the test results correlate with the results of another established test that measures the same construct (Sessa et al., 2018). Typically, the criteria refer to a well-known and reliable test. The researcher calculates the correlation between the measurement results and the criteria to assess criterion validity (Notelaers et al., 2019). A strong correlation indicates that the test effectively measures the intended construct (Brysbaert, 2017).

3.13.1 Etymological and design check

Purifying measurement scales is a crucial step in the development process (Mohajan, 2017). The validity of a measurement depends on the chosen methodology (Churchill Jr., 1979). Validity refers to how the measurement accurately captures what the researcher intends to assess (Churchill Jr., 1979). In this study, two validity tests, face validity and content validity, were conducted during the early stages before the primary survey (Schmidtlein et al., 2006). Both tests provided subjective indications of the questionnaire's suitability (Schmidtlein et al., 2006). As described by Sessa et al. (2018), content validity involves assessing the extent to which a set of items reflects the content domain.

The initial version of the questionnaire underwent examination by a knowledgeable supervisor to assess content validity (Worthington & Whittaker, 2006; Avlund et al., 1993). The supervisor evaluated the appropriateness and clarity of the language used in the items, and their feedback was incorporated into the questionnaire (Zaichkowsky, 1985). Additionally, three academics reviewed the questionnaire for face validity, providing feedback on whether it appeared to measure the intended construct and assessing its phrasing, layout, and comprehensibility.

The items from the literature were compared to the responses provided by consultants and managers (Gilhooly et al., 1988). The suggestions from these respondents led to the use of the present tense in all statements related to airline performance. Following the recommendations of Furr and Heuckeroth (2019), pilot testing was conducted to fine-tune the questionnaire and ensure ease of respondent participation.

Most items utilized interval scales and Likert-type scale ratings (anchored by 1 for strongly disagree and 5 for strongly agree). Frequently employed in business research, the Likert scale was used to assess respondents' attitudes towards the company symbol. The scale points were expanded to enhance construct variance and minimize

measurement error variation, following Bagozzi and Heatherton's (1994) and Churchill Jr. and Peter's (1984) suggestions.

Overall, the purification process aimed to refine the measurement instrument, ensuring its reliability and validity for the following data collection and analysis phases.

3.14 Sample Design

A sample design is a method for selecting a sample from a population. It refers to the method or approach used by the researcher to choose items for the sample. Before any data is gathered, the sample design is chosen. Researchers can pick from various sample designs (Ralston et al., 2011). Some methods are relatively more precise and more accessible to apply than others. The researcher selected Garavan et al. (2018) sample design that would be reliable and appropriate for this research. There are the steps; the researcher follows to select the appropriate sample design:

3.14.1 The Population of This Research

The first stage in designing any sample design is to explicitly identify the collection of items to be investigated, formally referred to as the Universe or population Majid (2018). The population for this research is limited to the number of employees working in PIA Airlines in Pakistan and other countries. According to the annual report of PIA Airlines, the total number of employees working with PIA Airlines was approximately ten thousand and seven hundred in the fiscal year of 2020 Majid (2018). The number of employees included top management, middle management and lower management. The population of this study is not related to current research because the airline has many departments that are irrelative to the research objective and hypothesis PIA (2020). Such as maintenance employees, labour people, office assistants, cleaning staff, and security guards are not part of this research. PIA airline operates in nearly one hundred and sixty-five countries worldwide. South-East Asia (Kuala Lumpur, capital of Malaysia, and Bangkok, capital of Thailand), Southwest Asia (Manama, capital of Bahrain, Kuwait City, capital of Kuwait, Muscat capital of Oman, Doha Damman capital of Qatar, Jeddah and Riyadh in Saudia and Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Sharjah in the United Arab Emirates). On the other side, PIA Airlines operate in North America (Toronto, the capital of Canada and New York City, the capital of the United States), in Europe (Copenhagen, capital of Denmark, Paris capital of France, Milan in Italy, Amsterdam in the Netherlands and Oslo in Norway) included in International Network

of PIA. The domestic Network of PIA includes Islamabad-Rawalpindi, North-West Frontier Province (Chitral, Dera Ismail Khan, Peshawar), in Punjab (Lahore, Multan, Sialkot, Faisalabad, Bahawalpur). Northern Areas include Gilgit and Skardu; Sindh (Hyderabad, Karachi, Sukkur and Mohenjo-Daro) and finally, Baluchistan (Dalbandin, Gwadar, Panjgur, Quetta and Turbat). In Pakistan, the total number of airports where PIA operates is approximately one hundred and fifty-one. After consideration of the number of airports in Pakistan and the number of countries in which PIA operate, the population for this study is Approximately five thousand related to this research.

In phase One of the study, which focused on secondary data analysis, a population of customer reviews from three selected websites, SKYTRAX, Trust Pilot, and Trip Advisor, was used to fulfil the first research objective. The population consisted of customer reviews for various airlines, including PIA, Delta, Sri Lanka, and Singapore Airlines. Specifically, there were approximately 1,159 customer reviews for PIA Airlines, 64,813 customer reviews for Delta Airlines, 4,318 for Sri Lanka Airlines, and 28,213 for Singapore Airlines. These online reviews provided valuable data for analysing and comparing these airlines' customer perceptions and feedback.

3.14.2 Source List

The source list, also known as the "sampling frame," is the list of sources from which a sample will be obtained (Organization, 2020). The source list for this research is based on top management and middle management at PIA Airlines. It includes the airport managers, finance managers, human resources managers, head of airport security, senior managers, a crew member in flights, operational sales officer, sales marketing managers, managing directors, technical engineer, head of finance officer, head of HR officer, security head, flight attendant and senior pilot. The researcher aims to approach these people to get the data required for this study and ignores the frame sampling error (Reichel & Morales, 2017).

As part of phase one, a specific analysis of customer reviews from three online websites was conducted to address the first research objective. The selection process involved shortlisting customers who had provided reviews on these websites. These customer reviews serve as valuable data for examining and understanding various aspects related to the research objective.

3.14.3 Sample Size

It is the number of employees selected from the population to provide a sample size. The appropriate sample size is required to conduct this research. The sample size should be manageable so the researcher can gather and analyse the data correctly. On the other hand, the sample size should not be petite that the objective of this research would not achieve with a confidence level of 95% (Reichel & Morales, 2017) and a Margin of Error of 5%; the sample size is 357 from the population of 5000. According to Hazra (2017), the confidence level of dependability is the predicted proportion of times the actual value will fall within the given accuracy boundaries. The sample results have a 95% chance of being correct, reflecting the actual population condition within a defined accuracy range, compared to a 5 per cent risk of the sample findings not reflecting the actual population condition. There are three ways to measure precision: confidence level, significance level, and accuracy (Sun et al., 2020). The sample size adopted for this research is specific, measurable, achievable, and relevant, and data will be collected within the selected time frame. Moreover, the chosen sample size is also friendly to the research budget (Trafimow, 2018).

3.14.4 Parameters of Interest

Parameters of interest are limitations and boundaries in sample size. After choosing the sample size, the researcher focuses on the proportion of employees from where data must be collected (Schoemann et al., 2017). There are eight variables in the research framework. Leadership style, decision-making, and leaders' communication are independent variables. Furthermore, leadership conduct is an independent and dependent variable. The performance of PIA is a dependent variable for this research.

On the other hand, two moderators have named corruption and political interference. As per the sources mentioned above, the researcher selected employees working at PIA Airlines (Martens & Logan, 2021). Those are flexible features to respond to the researcher questionnaire. There is no need to sub-group the population to collect the data. Because managers, security heads, pilots and crewmembers are part of airline operations.

Moreover, the targeted population is fully aware of PIA issues that the researcher aims to investigate. On the other hand, this is part of their (targeted sample size) (PIA, 2020) daily job to face political interference and fight corruption in airline tasks. Moreover,

the names mentioned in the sources list employees are fully aware of the leadership style in airlines and at what level airlines use advanced technology in every operational activity.

As part of phase one, a specific analysis of customer reviews from three online websites was conducted to address the first research objective. The sample size for this section is the same as the population of the study.

3.15.5 Budgetary Constraint

From a practical standpoint, cost concerns significantly influence decisions about the size of the sample and the type of sample. Because of this, a non-probability selection may be used.

3.16 Sample Design for this Study

Non-probability sampling is a type in which only some population members have the same chance to engage in the research (Bujang et al., 2018). Every person in the population has an equal probability of getting chosen. Researchers employ this approach where random probability sampling is complex due to time or expense constraints (Etikan & Bala, 2017). Due to the researcher's knowledge of the sample, non-probability sampling is faster and less expensive than probability sampling. Respondents react more swiftly than randomly picked persons because they are highly motivated to engage.

3.16.1 Convenience sampling

Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling approach in which samples are chosen from a population based on their researcher's accessibility. The researchers chose these samples because they are simple to recruit, and they did not consider picking a sample representative of the whole population (Rahi, 2017).

In research, testing a sample representative of the population is ideal. However, the population in some studies must be more significant to analyze and consider the entire population (Stratton, 2021). The Researchers use convenience sampling, the most common non-probability sampling method, because of its speed, cost-effectiveness, and sample accessibility, among other reasons.

3.16.2 Snowball sampling

An example of non-probability sampling would be snowball or chain-referral sampling, in which the samples include unique characteristics. The snowball sampling strategy

recruits' samples for a research project in which existing individuals refer to new subjects (Rahi, 2017).

The researcher used the snowball sampling technique to collect primary data from the employees of PIA Airlines. Because of the pandemic, the nearest airport to the researcher was closed, and PIA Airlines did not operate regularly. After the long wait to get the responses, the researcher used this technique to collect enough required data (Parker et al., 2019). The researcher used her social contacts and requested them to pass this questionnaire link to another related individual for maximum results. After this technique, the researcher saw a significant difference in responses quickly. Moreover, the researcher could collect primary data in time (Sharma, 2017).

3.16.3 Summated Scales (or Likert-type Scales)

Summated scales (or Likert-type scales) are created using the item analysis technique, in which a specific item is evaluated based on how effectively it discriminates between those who have a high total score and those who have a low total score. The final instrument includes the items or statements that best fulfil this discriminating test (Organization, 2020).

Summated scales comprise several statements that indicate a positive or negative attitude toward the item the responder is asked to answer. The respondent's agreement or disagreement marks each statement in the instrument (Adeniran, 2019). Each response is assigned a numerical score indicating whether it is favourable or unfavourable, and the values are added together to determine the respondent's attitude. Put another way, the overall score indicates the respondent's stance on a scale of favourable to unfavourable attitudes about a topic (Chyung et al., 2017).

The most often used summated measures in investigating social attitudes follow the framework proposed by Likert. As a result, they are frequently referred to as Likert-type scales. On a Likert scale, the respondent is asked to rate their agreement or disagreement with each statement on a range of one to five (but three or seven may also be used). When asked whether he or she finds his or her job enjoyable, for example, The respondent has the option of responding in one of the following ways: (i) strongly agree, (ii) agree, (iii) uncertain, (iv) disagree, (v) strongly disagree.

It is discovered that the scale is made up of these five points (Chyung et al., 2017). Strong agreement exists with the provided statement on one end of the scale and significant disagreement on the other, with intermediate values in between; As an example, consider the following:

(1) Strongly Agree (2) Agree (3) Undecided (4) Disagree (5) Strongly Disagree

A score is assigned to each point on the scale (Rahi, 2017). The lowest score (say 1) is given to the response showing the least favourable degree of work satisfaction. In contrast, the response's maximum score indicates the best job satisfaction (say 5). These core values are not usually displayed on the instrument but are included here to demonstrate the scoring pattern (Rahi, 2017). As a result, each of the five replies is assigned a scale value using the Likert scaling approach. Every statement in the instrument is treated in the same way. The device generates a total score for each responder, which is then used to determine the respondent's positive attitude toward the provided point of view. The following score values would be informative if the instrument included 30 statements (Saia et al., 2018).

$22 \times 5 = 110$ Most favorable response possible $22 \times 3 = 66$ A neutral attitude $22 \times 1 = 22$ Most unfavorable stance (Saia et al., 2018).

The scores would range from 22 to 110 for any given person. A score of over 66 indicates a favourable opinion toward the provided point of view, a score below 66 indicates an unfavourable opinion and a score of exactly 90 indicates neutrality (Ndirangu, 2017).

3.17 Analysis of Data Collection

3.17.1 Graphical Interpretation

For secondary data interpretation, graphical interpretation is used because Points, lines, bars, and pie charts are examples of graphs and charts, visual representations of data. Using graphs or charts, you may present numbers measured in an experiment, sales statistics, or how your electricity consumption changes over time. Line graphs, bar graphs, and circle charts are examples of graphs. Graphs and charts present data in various ways, and some are more suited for specific applications than others. Read the title, look at the key, and read the labels to decipher a graph or chart. Then look at the graph and figure out what the researcher explained.

For the quantitative data analysis following analysis and test have been used:

3.17.2 AMOS Analysis

The abbreviation of AMOS is an analysis of a moment structure in statistical software. AMOS is an SPSS module for Structural Equation Modelling, Path Analysis, and Confirmatory Factor Analysis. It's also known as causal modelling software or analysis of covariance software. AMOS is visual software for modelling structural equations (SEM). We may use simple sketching tools in AMOS to create graphical models. AMOS conducts structure equation modelling (SEM) calculations fast and presents the results. The researcher used AMOS version 24 to check the structural equation modelling.

3.17.3 SPSS Statistical Tool

SPSS is a commonly used statistical analysis tool in the social sciences. Marketers, health researchers, survey businesses, the government, education researchers, marketing groups, data miners, and others utilise it. The original SPSS handbook (Nie, Bent, & Hull, 1970) has been called one of "sociology's most significant publications" because it allows ordinary researchers to perform their statistical analyses. Data management (case selection, file reshaping, producing derived data) and data documentation (a metadata dictionary is saved in the data file) are aspects of the basic programme in addition to statistical analysis. The researcher used SPSS version 21 to analyse the questionnaire in this research.

3.17.3.1 Demographic analysis

Demographic analysis- As a result of mortalities, civilian casualties, and epidemics in the population, the demographic analysis may determine the age, gender, and race makeup of a people and how it has evolved.

3.17.3.2 Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics are used to characterise the fundamental characteristics of a study's data. They give quick summaries of the sample and the metrics. They are the foundation of nearly every quantitative data analysis, along with simple graphical analysis. It may also be used to assess a huge number of people using any method.

3.17.3.3 Normality tests

Normality tests are used in statistics to assess if a data set is well-modelled by a normal distribution and to compute the likelihood that a random variable underlying the data set is usually distributed.

3.17.4 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is a multivariate statistical approach that aims to find the fewest number of hypothetical constructs (also known as factors, dimensions, latent variables, synthetic variables, or internal characteristics) that may adequately explain the observed variation.

3.17.5 Reliability Analysis

The term "reliability analysis" refers to a scale's capacity to consistently represent its measuring construct. Statistics Solutions, the nation's leader in statistical data analysis, will help you with reliability analysis for your dissertation, thesis, or research project.

3.17.6 Correlation Analysis

In statistics, correlation or dependency refers to any statistical link between two random variables or bivariate data, whether causal or not. Correlation can refer to any statistical relationship, although it usually refers to the degree to which two variables are linearly connected.

3.17.7 Regression Analysis

Statistical modelling uses regression analysis to evaluate the connections between dependent variable and a set of independent variables (often referred to as the 'outcome' or response variable) and one or more independent variables (often referred to as 'predictors,' 'covariates,' 'explanatory variables,' or 'features'). Linear regression is the most frequent type of regression analysis, in which the line (or a more complicated linear combination) that best fits the data according to a specified mathematical criterion is found.

3.17.8 Moderation Analysis

An examination of moderation is external validity because it asks how widespread the causal impact is. The assessment of the X to Y causal connection for different values of M is a crucial element of moderation. The effect of X on Y for some M is called the simple effect.

Each questionnaire was checked for completeness and consistency before it was processed for answers and analysis. For this, basic and cross-tabulated frequency distributions, mean values, modes and percentages were used. SPSS was used to analyse the replies and interpret them. (Saia et al., 2018) points out that SPSS has broad

data handling capabilities and various statistical analysis procedures that can analyse modest to very big quantities of data (Bergin, 2018). Analysis of the study was done using frequency tables, percentages and charts expressing means and standard deviations, as well as percentages and charts. Those components in the nominal scale were analysed using a Likert Scale with weights that ranged from 1 to 5 (Mishra et al., 2019). To test the connections between variables, inferential statistics were employed. Specifically, we performed an F-test. In addition, all independent factors were pooled and statistically analysed (León-Mantero et al., 2020).

The usage of graphical and statistical approaches is described by (Assarroudi et al., 2018) as part of the data presented. Statistical approaches such as tables and charts were used to convey quantitative data in this study, whereas graphs were used to present secondary data (Kombo and Tromp, 2006).

3.17.9 Ratio Analysis

In order to address the first and second research objectives, a thorough analysis was conducted using ratio analysis, specifically financial ratio analysis and profitability ratio analysis. Financial ratio analysis involves examining vital financial indicators and ratios to evaluate the financial performance of the airlines under study. It included assessing metrics such as current growth and learning ratios and no. of employees ratio. These ratios provided insights into the profitability and earning capacity of the airlines. Additionally, profitability ratio analysis focused on specific ratios such as net profit margin, gross profit ratio and return on capital. These ratios allowed for a deeper understanding of the airlines' ability to generate profits and effectively utilize their capital. By examining these profitability ratios, it was possible to assess the financial viability and success of the airlines.

By utilizing ratio analysis, the study aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the financial performance of the airlines, thereby addressing the first research objective. Furthermore, by focusing on profitability ratios, the study sought to evaluate the airlines' profitability and determine their ability to generate sustainable returns, thereby contributing to achieving the second research objective. The analysis of these ratios played a crucial role in assessing the financial health and performance of the airlines, providing valuable insights into their overall financial performance.

In addition to conducting a ratio analysis, a comparison was made with Delta, Sri Lanka, and Singapore Airlines to provide a broader context and benchmark for

evaluating the financial performance of the airlines under study. This comparative analysis allowed a more comprehensive assessment of the airlines' financial indicators and ratios.

The comparative analysis with Delta, Sri Lanka, and Singapore Airlines enhanced the significance and relevance of the ratio analysis. It provided valuable insights into the financial performance of the airlines under study about their peers, facilitating a more comprehensive evaluation of their financial health and performance.

3.17.10 Content Analysis

A content analysis of customer reviews was conducted to complement the financial and profitability ratio analysis to address the first and second research objectives. The analysis involved systematically examining and interpreting customer feedback from three online platforms: SKYTRAX, Trust Pilot, and Trip Advisor. These customer reviews provided valuable insights into the airline's performance, including service quality, punctuality, customer satisfaction, and overall experience.

By analysing customer reviews, it was possible to gain a deeper understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the airlines under study. The content analysis allowed for identifying common themes, issues, and sentiments expressed by customers. This qualitative analysis provided valuable insights into areas where the airlines excelled and areas that required improvement.

Furthermore, comparing Delta, Sri Lanka, and Singapore Airlines enriched the analysis by providing benchmarks and reference points. By comparing the customer reviews of the different airlines, it was possible to identify patterns and trends, as well as assess the relative performance of each airline in terms of customer satisfaction and experience.

Overall, the content analysis of customer reviews complemented the quantitative analysis provided by financial and profitability ratio analysis. It added a qualitative perspective to the research objectives, shedding light on the airlines' performance from the customers' viewpoint. The comparison with other airlines allowed for a broader understanding of the industry landscape and the position of the airlines under study about their competitors.

3.18 Conclusion

The research methodology chapter encompasses a comprehensive overview of the research process, including various aspects such as the research onion, research philosophy, data collection and analysis approaches, research design, ethical considerations, questionnaire design, pilot study, sample design, data analysis techniques, and limitations of the study. This chapter serves as a roadmap for conducting the research and ensures the study's rigour and validity.

This study employs the research onion as a framework to guide the research process. It encompasses layers of research decisions, including research philosophy, approach, strategies, methods, and time horizon. The choice of research philosophy plays a fundamental role in shaping the study's direction and methodology. This study selects pragmatism as the research philosophy because it emphasises practicality, flexibility, and integrating multiple perspectives.

The research design adopted in this study is a mixed methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis techniques. This approach aligns with the pragmatism philosophy, as it allows for a comprehensive understanding of the research topic by utilising the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative research methods.

For data collection, a combination of primary and secondary methods is employed. The primary method involves using surveys to collect data directly from participants, while the second method involves the analysis of existing data sources and literature. The research questions, objectives, and the availability of relevant data sources determine the data collection approach.

Regarding data analysis, deductive, inductive, and abductive approaches are distinguished. Deductive research employs existing theories and hypotheses to guide the analysis, inductive research involves deriving theories and hypotheses from the data, and abductive research combines deductive and inductive approaches. The specific approach for data analysis in this study depends on the nature of the data and the research questions.

The research strategy employed in this study is the survey strategy, which offers several benefits, such as the ability to collect large amounts of data from a diverse sample, standardised data collection, and the potential for statistical analysis. The research

methodology incorporates ethical considerations to protect participants' rights, confidentiality, and informed consent.

The development of the research questionnaire involves careful design and validation processes. Content validity is assessed to ensure that the questionnaire items effectively capture the research constructs. A pilot study is conducted to evaluate the feasibility and reliability of the questionnaire, leading to improvements in item selection, wording, and structure.

Data collection is carried out in two phases. The first phase involves administering the research questionnaire to the participants, while the second phase focuses on collecting additional data through interviews or observations, depending on the research requirements.

The analysis of the collected data includes various statistical techniques such as AMOS analysis, SPSS analysis, reliability analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and moderation analysis. These techniques enable exploring relationships and patterns and examining the research hypotheses.

While this study has been carefully designed, certain limitations and challenges must be acknowledged. These may include constraints related to time, resources, sample size, generalizability of findings, and potential biases in data collection. Acknowledging these limitations and considering their impact on the study's outcomes and conclusions is essential.

Chapter 4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the various aspects involved in assessing the performance of PIA Airlines. It begins with a discussion on the preparation undertaken for the analysis, setting the stage for the subsequent evaluations. Time series and cross-sectional data analysis techniques are employed to gain insights into the company's financial performance, with a specific focus on operating revenue, operating expenses, current assets, current liabilities, non-current assets, and non-current liabilities. The balanced scorecard approach aligns the analysis with the organization's strategic objectives, as reflected in PIA's vision statement, mission statement, and core values. Furthermore, ratio analysis is employed to assess profitability and financial health. Customer reviews, benchmarking, and content analysis of website ratings are explored to understand customer perceptions and identify areas for improvement. The subsequent quantitative analysis phase includes demographic statistics, exploratory factor analysis, reliability analysis, correlations analysis, regression analysis, and moderation analysis, which provide deeper insights into the relationships between variables and external influences. These analytical approaches contribute to a comprehensive understanding of PIA Airlines' performance, serving as a basis for leadership and future initiatives to enhance the company's competitiveness.

4.1 Preparation of the chapter

The research conducted in this study revolves around the four dimensions of the Balanced Scorecard: financial, growth and learning, internal processes, and customer services. In this chapter, the initial focus will be presenting the collected data from secondary sources related to the airline's financial performance, customer service, and growth. As outlined in the research methodology chapter, the data collection process involved secondary and primary methods, including phase one and two routes. The subsequent methodology chapter delves into the analysis of the collected data. A strong

foundation is established for further analysis by providing detailed information on these aspects. Additionally, examining PIA Airlines' internal processes and the corresponding analysis will be presented after the discussion of secondary data, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the airline's overall performance.

To gain a more comprehensive understanding of the internal workings of the airline, which includes HR processes, management practices, and the perspectives and actions of employees involved in day-to-day operations, a questionnaire has been developed. This questionnaire consists of 22 research-based questions that align with the research hypotheses. Furthermore, the researcher intends to conduct a benchmarking analysis to compare PIA Airlines with three other airlines: Delta Airlines, Singapore Airlines, and Sri Lankan Airlines. This benchmarking process consists of two key steps:

Time Series Data Analysis

(Compare PIA Airline performance in ten years' time)

Cross-Sectional Data Analysis

(Compare PIA Airlines to other airlines in five year time)

4.2 The Balanced Scorecard

A balanced scorecard (BSC) is a performance metric used in corporate strategy to assess and improve various internal activities and their external impacts. It is extensively employed in the United States, the United Kingdom, Japan, and Europe to provide measurement and feedback to organizations. By gathering and analysing data, managers and executives can obtain quantifiable results. This information empowers company personnel to make informed decisions for the future success of their businesses. The balanced scorecard assesses performance and goal achievement from four distinct perspectives:

- Financial (Ratio Analysis)
- Customer (Content Analysis)
- Internal Process (Internal Leadership)
- Learning And Growth (Ratio Analysis)

In order to gain a comprehensive understanding of PIA Airlines and its objectives, this study begins by exploring the airline's vision statement, mission statement, and core values. Additionally, the corporate profile of PIA Airlines is discussed to provide

insights into its structure and operations. Examining these aspects establishes a solid foundation before delving into the financial reports and customer reviews of PIA. This approach ensures a holistic understanding of PIA Airlines, its goals, and its overall performance.

4.3 Vision statement

PIA’s vision is to be a world-class profitable airline meeting customer expectation through excellent services, on-time performance, innovative products and absolute safety.

4.4 Mission statement

Employs teams will contribute towards making PIA a global airline of choice through:

- Offering quality customer services and innovative products
- Using state-of-the-art technologies
- Ensuring cost-effective measures in procurement and operations
- Developing safety culture

PIA's vision and mission statements provide a solid foundation for the airline's strategic direction. They reflect a customer-centric approach, a commitment to innovation and efficiency, and a strong emphasis on safety. By adhering to these principles, PIA can position itself as a reputable and preferred airline domestically and globally.

4.5 Core Value of PIA Airlines

Table 5.1. Core Value of PIA Airlines

<u>Customer Expectations</u> (Convenience, Care, Affordability)	<u>Integrity</u> (Business Ethics, Accountability, and Transparency)
<u>Service</u> (Personalized, Courteous, Passionate)	<u>Reliability</u> (Loyalty and Consistency)
<u>Innovation</u> (New Ideas, Products, Value Added Services)	<u>Safety</u> (Passengers, Employees, Environment)
<u>Cohesiveness</u>	<u>Social Responsibility</u>

(Respect for Individuals, Teamwork, and Effective Communication)	(Welfare, Health, Education)
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These factors reflect what customers expect from businesses: convenience, ethical practices, personalized service, reliability, innovation, safety, cohesive culture, and social responsibility. Meeting these expectations can foster customer satisfaction, trust, and long-term success.

4.6 Corporate Profile of PIA Airlines

Board of Directors (as of May 15, 2020):

- Mr Aslam Khan (Chairman)
- Mr Noor Ahmed (Secretary Economic Affairs Division)
- Mr Atif Aslam Bajwa
- Mr Naveed Baloch (Secretary Finance Division)
- Mr Hasan Nasir Jamy (Secretary Aviation Division)
- Mr Farrukh H Khan
- Mr Tariq Kimani
- Air Marshal Arshad Malik (Chief Executive Officer)
- Mr Navaid H Malik
- Mr Haque Nawaz
- Mr Muhammad Shuaib (Company Secretary)
- Mr Muhammad Javed Jameel (Acting Chief Internal Auditor)

Executive Management: as of May 15, 2020

- Air Marshal Arshad Malik (Chief Executive Officer)
 - Mr Aijaz Mazhar (Chief Operating Officer)
 - AVM Noor Abbas (Advisor To CEO)
 - AVM Soban Nazir Syed (Director- Precision Engineering Complex)

- Mr Qamar Shamim (Officiating Chief Commercial Officer)
- Mr Khalilullah Sheikh (Chief Financial Officer)
- Capt. Arshad Khan (Chief Flight Operations)
- Mr Khalid-Ul-Rehman Barias (Chief Information Officer)
- Mr Jawad Zafar Choudhry (Chief Corporate Development Officer)
- Mr Aamer Altaf (Chief Human Resource Officer)
- Mr Amir Ali (Chief Technical Officer)
- Mr Amanullah Qureshi (Chief Supply Chain Management Officer)
- Mr Younus M Khan (Chief Projects Officer)

The corporate profile of PIA Airlines provides an overview of the individuals serving in critical positions within the organization. The Board of Directors includes prominent figures from various divisions, such as economic affairs, finance, and aviation. The Executive Management team comprises top-level executives responsible for the day-to-day operations and strategic decision-making. These individuals bring their expertise and experience to lead the airline and ensure its effective functioning across different areas such as operations, finance, human resources, and technology.

4.7 Ratio Used in This Study

In order to address the first and second research objectives, the study will utilize financial ratios to achieve the research objectives. The selected ratios include the current ratio, the number of employee ratios, and the growth and learning ratio. Additionally, profitability ratios such as gross profit margin, net profit margin, and return on capital will be employed. These ratios will provide valuable insights into the airline's financial performance and growth potential, contributing to the achievement of the first and second research objectives.

The initial step involves preparing tables and graphs using the balance sheets and income statements of PIA Airlines spanning ten years. The key metrics to be calculated include operating profit/loss, current and non-current assets, current and fixed liabilities, closing share price, number of employees per year, gross profit, net profit, and earnings before interest and tax. The same calculations have been performed for Delta Airlines, Sri Lanka Airlines, and Singapore Airlines over five years. The comprehensive tables and graphs displaying these calculations for all airlines are included in an appendix.

Once the figures mentioned above have been computed, the ratios are determined using the respective formulas for each ratio. The ratios are computed for PIA Airlines over ten years, while for Delta, Sri Lanka, and Singapore Airlines, the ratios are computed over five years.

Customer reviews are collected from three specified online websites, as mentioned in Chapter Two. Subsequently, the customer reviews are categorized and organized based on their titles or main headings for further content analysis. It is important to note that

the number of customer reviews varies across each airline, and further details will be elaborated upon later in this chapter.

4.8 Financial Performance of PIA For The Years 2020 To 2016

Table 3 financial performances of PIA airlines for the year 2020 to 2016

	2020	2019	2018	2017	2016
	Rs. In million	Rs. In million	Rs. In million	Rs. In million	Rs. In million
Operating revenue	94,989,391	147,500,129	103,490,460	90,556,089	88,997,379
Operating expense	100,618,552	165,324,166	150,523,708	126,366,578	120,633,000
Operating loss/profit	(5,629,161)	(17,824,037)	(47,033,248)	(35,810,489)	(31,636,144)
Fixed assets	90,946,488	99,418,582	78,302,168	67,157,187	68,838,645
Current assets	42,491,498	52,917,036	34,945,653	32,145,992	29,449,080
Total assets	133,437,986	152,335,618	113,247,821	99,303,179	98,287,725
Current liabilities	322,252,878	324,645,200	288,569,906	244,307,972	213,702,122
Capital employed	(188,814,892)	(172,309,582)	(175,322,085)	(145,004,793)	(115,414,397)
Long-term liabilities	222,960,679	207,050,576	150,970,165	121,096,089	105,931,398
Current ratio	0.13	0.16	0.12	0.13	0.14
Earnings per share	(6.62)	(10.05)	(12.86)	(9.74)	(8.58)
Share closing price	4.73	6.67	5.09	4.02	9.16
Average no. Of employees	10,779	11,740	12,196	13,268	13,947

4.9 PIA Airlines Financial Performance for The Year Of 2015 To 2011

Table 4 Financial performance of PIA for the years 2015 to 2011

	2015	2014	2013	2012	2011
	Rs. In million	Rs. In million	Rs. In million	Rs. In million	Rs. In million
Operating revenue	91,268,545	99,519,057	95,771,130	97,438,000	116,550,580
Operating expense	107,704,441	118,048,665	123,151,157	129,450,000	134,477,330
Operating loss/profit	(16,435,896)	(14,938,817)	(32,122,080)	(17,320,000)	(17,926,760)
Fixed assets	76,647,952	84,102,148	90,452,072	97,437,667	96,685,080

Current assets	25,079,416	24,733,527	22,737,681	22,586,371	16,562,570
Total assets	101,727,368	108,835,675	113,189,753	120,024,038	113,247,650
Current liabilities	205,571,050	216,451,936	189,491,248	167,479,925	104,783,970
Capital employed	(103,843,682)	(107,616,261)	(76,301,495)	(47,455,887)	8,463,680
Long-term liabilities	89,692,109	36,087,553	31,408,996	13,957,198	89,535,860
Current ratio	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.16
Earnings per share	(6.39)	(7.00)	(12.51)	(11.00)	(9.73)
Share closing price	8.46	7.45	4.03	4.02	1.97
Average no. of employees	16,271	16,243	16,604	17,439	18,014

Figure: 5.1. Operating Profit and Losses

Figure 2 operating profit and losses of PIA airlines

4.10 Operating revenue and operating expenses

The researcher has conducted an extensive analysis of financial data spanning a decade to gain insights into the financial position and growth of PIA Airlines. Tables 4.1 and 4.2, discussed in the previous chapter, provide an overview of the financial data from 2011 to 2020. The findings reveal that PIA Airlines has faced challenges in achieving operating profit throughout the last decade, with the highest recorded loss in 2018, as stated in the PIA annual reports (2020). In simple terms, the airline's operating expenses have consistently exceeded its operating revenues. These expenses include rent,

utilities, wages, salaries, overhead costs, airport taxes, interest payments on debts, and legal fees.

Additionally, the literature reviews indicate that PIA Airlines has employed excessive staff members, surpassing actual requirements, as highlighted by UKEssays (2018). On the other hand, the airline has been burdened with significant debts and has been paying substantial interest since 1981, as mentioned in "PIA's Financial Shenanigans" (2012). Following a critical period of collapse, General Ziaul Haq emphasized the precarious state of the airline and its reliance on borrowing funds from banks for aircraft, computer services, and capital equipment. A special committee was formed to investigate the airline's operations and management departments. The committee's report unveiled various factors contributing to the airline's losses, including unjustified overtime, free travel privileges, widespread smuggling by crew members, and the creation of unnecessary positions for relatives of existing employees (PIA's Financial Shenanigans, 2012).

These findings shed light on the challenges and underlying factors that have contributed to the financial struggles faced by PIA Airlines. They emphasize the necessity for critical analysis and strategic measures to address these issues and foster sustainable growth.

The graph provided depicts the airline's operating revenue and operating expenses over the last ten years. There is a notable gap between the two, with operating expenses

consistently surpassing operating revenue. It means that the airline's annual expenditures on operations exceed its earnings. In 2019, despite the operating revenue reaching fifty million, the corresponding expense line also experienced a sharp increase, reaching three hundred million. It indicates a significant financial burden on the airline's operations, emphasizing the importance of implementing effective cost management and revenue generation strategies to achieve a more balanced financial position.

4.11 Current assets and current liabilities

When evaluating an airline's liquidity, the interaction between current assets and liabilities is crucial in assessing its performance. However, the Tables above illustrate that the current assets and liabilities figures have had a limited impact. Cash, the most readily available asset, is essential for meeting short-term debts. Unfortunately, over the past decade, PIA Airlines has consistently shown fewer current assets than more than double the current liabilities. This situation indicates the airline's need for additional equity in its business operations. The airline's debt burden continues to increase without sufficient equity and the ability to fulfil short-term obligations promptly.

Consequently, the organization faces escalating challenges each year in sustaining its operations, as stated by Chron (2020). The table below shows that the bar representing current liabilities has surged to nearly four hundred million. In contrast, the bar representing current assets has only slightly surpassed half a million. Insufficient cash reserves, short-term deposits, accounts receivables, inventory, marketable securities, and office supplies, among other cash equivalents, have hindered the airline's ability to meet short-term financial obligations such as accounts payable, dividends, and income taxes within an average fiscal year. This persistent insufficiency has significantly impeded PIA's performance over an extended period, highlighting the necessity for proactive measures to enhance liquidity and financial stability.

Figure 5.2. Current assets and current liabilities

Figure 3 current assets and current liabilities of PIA airlines

Over the years, the airline's current liabilities have significantly increased, surpassing the current assets by fourfold within ten years. 2019 there was a relatively more favourable figure for current assets than in other years. However, it is essential to note that short-term payables also experienced an increase. The relationship between current assets and liabilities can be further evaluated by calculating the current ratio, also known as the liquidity ratio, which provides insights into the equity position of the airline. This ratio and its implications will be discussed in detail later in this chapter.

4.12 Non-current assets and non-current liabilities

When examining non-current assets and non-current liabilities, the situation is relatively different compared to current assets and current liabilities. Non-current assets are characterized by their lack of liquidity, representing long-term investments that cannot be readily converted into cash. Realizing their value within a single fiscal year can be challenging. Non-current assets include property, equipment, fleets, long-term investments, and Goodwill.

Conversely, long-term liabilities encompass obligations that extend beyond the current operating period. They include long-term loans, pension liabilities, healthcare charges post-retirement, overdue compensations, fleet leases, bonds payable, and overdue income taxes. These liabilities reflect the long-term financial obligations of the airline. It is essential to recognize that non-current assets and liabilities contribute to the overall financial structure of the airline. However, their impact on day-to-day operations and

short-term liquidity is limited. Managing and balancing these non-current components is crucial for maintaining financial stability and long-term sustainability.

Figure: 5.3. Non-Current Assets And Non-Current Liabilities

Figure 4 non-current assets and liabilities of PIA airlines

The presented table provides an overview of the non-current assets and non-current liabilities of PIA Airlines over the past ten years. In 2011 and 2012, the non-current assets remained relatively stable, with a slight increase observed in 2012. In contrast, the bar representing non-current liabilities experienced a sudden decline in 2012. It indicates that the airline significantly reduced its long-term debts, which is noteworthy. For the subsequent three years, PIA Airlines maintained the value of its non-current assets. However, in 2016, the value of fixed assets decreased while the non-current liabilities continued to rise. Following 2016, there is a gradual upward trend in the bar representing long-term debts, with the total amount reaching approximately two hundred and twenty-five million in 2020. In contrast, the airline struggled to increase the value of its fixed assets in comparison to its long-term liabilities. This imbalance ultimately has an impact on PIA Airlines' overall performance.

The airline must address this discrepancy and work towards improving the value of its fixed assets while effectively managing its long-term debts. Achieving a better balance between non-current assets and non-current liabilities will enhance PIA Airlines' financial standing and performance in the long run.

Figure: Earnings Per Share Value and Share Closing Price

Figure 5 Earning Per Share Value and Share Closing Price Of PIA Airlines

4.13 Earnings per share value and share closing price of PIA Airlines

Another critical factor in any business is its earnings per share (EPS) value, which reflects its standing in the market. Unfortunately, in the case of PIA Airlines, their EPS has been negative for the past decade. It indicates that the airline needs to generate more profits for each share of its stock. Consequently, investor interest in the airline has waned significantly. In fact, according to SAMAA (2018), Prime Minister Miftah Ismail, while discussing financial matters, made an offer to potential investors. If they were willing to purchase the loss-making airline (PIA), they would receive the state-owned steel mills free of charge. Such statements by the finance prime minister shed light on the challenge faced by the national flag carrier airline.

The graph above provides an overview of the performance of PIA Airlines over the past decade. The weakest year for the airline was 2018, as indicated by the lowest point on the graph, with an earnings per share (EPS) price nearing negative thirteen. However, there has been a gradual upward trend since then, and by the end of 2020, the EPS had improved to negative nearly six.

In terms of the closing share price, which serves as a comparative measure, the graph below illustrates the results over the same 10-year period. In the initial five years, the closing price of shares was relatively high, peaking at 9.16. However, in 2017, there was a sudden decline to 4.02, similar to the value observed in 2012. The following year,

in 2018, the closing price of shares began to rise gradually, reaching a peak of 6.67. However, it experienced another decline in 2020, ending at 4.73.

These observations highlight the fluctuations in both the earnings per share value and the closing share price of PIA Airlines over the past decade, reflecting the varying performance and market dynamics experienced by the airline during this period.

4.14 Number of employees

As discussed in the literature review, one of the significant challenges faced by PIA Airlines is its extensive workforce. The number of employees at PIA airline was previously addressed in section 6.2.1. Following the airline's collapse in 1981, a special committee was established to investigate PIA's operations and management departments. The committee's findings revealed that the airline suffered losses due to various union-related factors. According to the committee's report, unjustified overtime, widespread smuggling by the crews, and the creation of unnecessary jobs for relatives of existing employees were identified as contributing factors to the breakdown of PIA Airline (Shenanigans, 2019). The researcher expands upon these findings in this study to provide further insights into the issue.

Figure: 5.5. Number Of Employees

Figure 6 number of employees of PIA airlines

The table above illustrates the number of employees at PIA Airlines over the past decade. It is evident that the figures started at around eighteen thousand and decreased to nearly eleven thousand, resulting in a reduction of approximately seven thousand employees over the ten years. However, considering the airline's financial condition during this time, more than this reduction may be considered a significant change to improve its performance.

The thick stacked area on the graph represents the gradual decline in the number of employees. As indicated in the findings discussed in section 6.2.4, the earnings per share value consistently remained negative, indicating the airline's poor performance. In this context, the more significant number of employees can be seen as a liability rather than an asset for the airline.

PIA needs to address the reduction in the number of employees and the underlying issues affecting the airline's financial performance to bring about substantial improvements.

4.15 Customer reviews

The overall rating at SKYTRAX is 5/10, is a 2-star Airline.

The overall rating at Trust pilot is 2.4/5

The overall rating at Trip Advisor is 2.5/5

4.15.1 Customer complains about PIA airlines

Table 5 customer complains about PIA airlines

Customer complains	Counts	Percentage
Booking through credit card	55	9.2%
Hygiene and safety	40	6.7%
Misplacement of luggage	67	11.2%
Standard of food	35	5.9%
Behaviour of cabin crew	29	4.8%
Cancelled flights	39	6.5%
Refund of ticket	31	5.2%
Poor customer service	42	7.02%
No Inflight entertainment	78	13.04%
Seat comfort	65	11.1%
No Value of money	34	5.7%
Boarding issues	46	8.0%
Staff untrustworthy	37	6.2%
Total	598	100%

The researcher collected data from three different online websites which include SKYTRAZ, Trust Pilot and Trip Advisor.

The overall rating at SKYTRAX is 5/10, is a 2-star airline.

The overall rating at Trust pilot is 2.4/5

The overall rating at Trip Advisor is 2.5/5

According to SKYTRAX airline has two stars rated airline and the total score is five out of ten. While. On Trust Pilot, the total score is almost two and a half out of ten. Finally, on Trip Advisor, PIA airline has two and a half scores out of a total of ten.

Figure 7 customer complains of PIA airlines

As the table above shows, the most significant percentage of complaints, amounting to approximately thirteen per cent, is attributed to in-flight entertainment. It aligns with the findings presented in Chapter Three of the literature review, highlighting the weakness of PIA Airlines regarding inadequate technology and entertainment options on their planes. Remarkably, customer complaints related to crew members' behaviour constitute only five per cent of the total. It is a positive aspect for the airline, as the demeanour of crew members plays a vital role in the airline industry and contributes to improving the number of travellers choosing the airline. However, the second most prevalent issues customers face are seat comfort (eleven per cent) and luggage misplacement (slightly over eleven per cent). These issues carry significant weight as nobody wishes to experience the loss of personal belongings. Such incidents can erode customer trust and reduce the likelihood of them choosing to travel with the airline again.

Furthermore, this issue also emotionally impacts customers, as the loss or potential loss of essential and private items can be distressing. Additionally, when customers purchase tickets and plan to enjoy their trip, it is crucial for them to feel at ease. Thus,

when PIA customers complain about seat comfort, it directly impacts the airline's revenue.

Customers also raise the issue of booking through a credit card and occupy the fourth position in the list of complaints, accounting for slightly over nine per cent. It becomes a nightmare when someone else uses their credit card to book a ticket on the traveller's behalf. During boarding, the customer must present the card used for the purchase, which must be in her name. Another problem associated with credit card transactions is the refund process, which often takes considerable time to be credited back to the bank account. Some customers have shared their experiences of being informed by the airline that they cannot refund the money because the credit card used is not in their name, leading to further frustration. Lastly, when tickets are purchased online through a third-party platform, there have been instances where the airline needs to provide a valid ticket. Instead, they ask customers to show their bank statements at the boarding desk. PIA Airlines has faced challenges in addressing these technical issues, resulting in inconvenience and dissatisfaction for customers.

Regarding the boarding process, customers frequently encounter another issue related to boarding, accounting for eight per cent of the total complaints. Boarding is a crucial and inevitable step in air travel. If an airline does not have well-trained staff assigned to this task, it can become a time-consuming and stressful experience for passengers. Furthermore, it becomes even more challenging when customers' luggage fails to meet

the weight criteria or exceeds the weight limit. In such situations, passengers must rearrange their belongings or pay additional fees for the excess weight. Some customers have also reported restrictions on bringing baby strollers aboard the plane, and at times, airline staff may not be cooperative with passengers travelling with infants or young children. These circumstances diminish the overall travel experience for customers, leaving them frustrated and dissatisfied with the airline's service.

Poor customer service and flight cancellations are significant issues faced by PIA Airlines, with approximately seven per cent of customers complaining about poor customer service and six and a half per cent reporting flight cancellations. The problem of poor customer service encompasses both online services and airport department services. Customers often need help purchasing tickets online, and if they require assistance and call the helpline, their calls may go unanswered. The need for more responsiveness is both concerning and frustrating. Imagine purchasing expensive tickets and not receiving them via mail, only to call the helpline and find someone to assist the customer. It can be a nightmarish experience. Regrettably, such situations have occurred for numerous customers.

Additionally, during the scanning stage at airports, many individuals mistakenly pack prohibited items in their hand luggage. At this point, passengers cannot place these items (such as perfumes over 100ml or metallic objects) in their checked baggage, as it has already been booked. In such situations, airline staff sometimes resort to misleading passengers in order to confiscate their belongings. These actions poorly reflect the airline's reputation and are highly detrimental to customer satisfaction.

Cancellation of flights is closely linked to poor customer service. Customers have reported instances where flights were cancelled with concise notice, and sometimes they were only informed of the cancellation through airport announcements. Based on data collected from three different websites, around six and a half per cent of customers have complained about cancelled flights. This percentage includes international and domestic flights, with international flights having a higher ratio of complaints.

While flight cancellations due to emergencies, weather conditions, aircraft maintenance issues, or safety concerns can be justified, cancellations caused by the absence of a pilot, unavailable crew staff, overbooked planes, or other managerial mistakes are unacceptable. Customers rightfully expect reliable and well-managed operations from an airline, and cancellations due to avoidable circumstances reflect poor customer service and operational inefficiencies.

The food quality in PIA Airlines has received feedback from approximately six per cent of customers. This feedback can be attributed to factors such as the menu's variety or the food's taste. Since travellers come from diverse backgrounds and cultures, it is understandable that only some passengers may appreciate Pakistani cuisine. Additionally, some passengers have expressed concerns about the variety of menu options available during the flight. It is important to note that the quality and variety of food may vary depending on the class of travel, with disparities between business class, first class, and economy class offerings.

Hygiene and safety during travel are crucial aspects for any airline. Unfortunately, around seven per cent of passengers have expressed dissatisfaction with PIA's hygiene and safety practices. Some customers have reported cleanliness issues within the aircraft, including unclean equipment and a lack of proper cleaning. Negative feedback has also been given regarding airport cleanliness and inadequate management of restroom facilities. Ensuring a clean and hygienic environment is essential for passenger comfort and well-being.

Regarding the airline's safety, passengers have raised concerns regarding the condition of PIA's fleets. Instances of lost luggage and missing belongings have also been reported by passengers, which can impact the airline's overall safety perception.

Furthermore, when evaluating the overall value for money, approximately six per cent of travellers have expressed dissatisfaction with PIA's services' performance. While this percentage may be considered significant compared to other airlines, it is essential to note that the researcher will conduct a comparative analysis of PIA Airlines with other airlines later in this chapter. This analysis aims to comprehensively understand and measure PIA's performance within the airline industry.

4.15.2 Good Customer Experience with PIA Airlines

Table 6 customer experiences about PIA airlines

Customers satisfaction	Counts	Percentage
Best airline	77	22.0%
Helped with human remains	2	0.56%
Responsible management	55	16.0%
Nice experience, old fleets	89	25.1%
Recent improvement by CEO reflects in the service	76	21.5%

Awesome business class	53	15.0%
Total	352	100%

Following the analysis of customer complaints about PIA, it is time to focus on positive customer feedback. The customer feedback data has been collected from the same sources and websites where the customers' complaints data was gathered, namely SKYTRAX, Trustpilot, and Trip Advisor.

Figure: 5.7. Customer Experience of PIA Airlines

Figure 8 customer experience of PIA airlines

The bar graph above illustrates the data regarding passengers' positive experiences with the airline. Twenty-five per cent of individuals expressed that PIA has old fleets, yet they had a good travel experience. This feedback encompasses various factors to consider. Firstly, a pleasant experience could imply that the flights were punctual or that the passengers encountered friendly staff. Secondly, people may be satisfied because they obtained their tickets reasonably priced, or Pakistani passengers appreciated having direct flights to Pakistan.

A positive experience might also be associated with PIA being an Asian airline and having Urdu-speaking staff. The list of possibilities can be extensive, and the ultimate answer is that these different factors are relevant to different customers. On the other

hand, many passengers observed that PIA is a good airline, but the planes must be updated. The noise produced by old planes during take-off or landing was frequently mentioned. Several passengers emphasized the need for PIA to invest in their fleets to enhance the airline's performance and value, and this viewpoint is not entirely unfounded.

Moving on to the higher percentage of passengers' positive experiences, approximately twenty-one and a half per cent of travellers have noticed a notable difference in PIA's performance and services since the appointment of a new CEO. It is a significant accomplishment for PIA as the new leader has successfully implemented effective measures that have positively impacted the airline's customer service. In the customer feedback, various aspects such as flight punctuality, improved management behaviour, streamlined boarding processes, and overall service enhancements were highlighted as the result of the CEO's right decisions. It indicates that the new CEO has played a pivotal role in aligning PIA's operations and customer experience, resulting in a marked improvement for the airline.

Twenty-two per cent of customers have expressed their satisfaction with the performance of PIA Airlines. Based on feedback collected from top-rated customer feedback websites, it has been discovered that PIA is regarded as the best airline by travellers. Customers have shared their positive experiences from travelling to various destinations worldwide. They have highlighted the excellent customer service at

airports, the friendly and helpful crew members onboard, competitive ticket prices compared to other airlines, smooth and safe landings, ease of travelling with children, efficient boarding processes, helpful ground staff, fresh in-flight meals with snack services, and cooperative baggage weight policies.

Regarding being the best airline, fifteen per cent of customers specifically mentioned the outstanding service provided in PIA's business class. Passengers in business class receive additional benefits such as a diverse menu of food options, comfortable seating, a peaceful environment conducive to restful sleep during the flight, and expedited processes during take-off and landing. In summary, customers are willing to pay extra for the business class experience due to the superior level of service they receive in return.

Sixteen per cent of customers have praised the responsible management of PIA. According to their feedback, whenever any issues arose during their flight or at the airport, the management quickly assisted and resolved their problems. A competent and experienced management team is crucial for the success of any business, and it is a positive aspect for PIA to have such responsible management.

Additionally, one per cent of customers shared their unique experience with PIA when travelling with "Human Remains." One passenger recounted a situation where their flight was diverted to a different city due to adverse weather conditions. The passenger explained to PIA's management that they were carrying human remains to reach the intended destination in Lahore on time. The passenger further commended the PIA management for assisting in expediting their passage through the gate and arranging transportation. This act of kindness and support from PIA's management is noteworthy, as it involved ensuring the passenger's needs were met while maintaining the safety and responsibility of the airline for both the passenger and their belongings.

4.16 Growth and Learning

$$\text{Growth rate (revenue)} = \frac{\text{Revenue (current year)} - \text{Revenue (last year)}}{\text{Revenue (last year)}}$$

Table 5.6. Learning And Growth Ratio Calculation of PIA Airlines

Table 7 learning and growth ratio calculation for PIA airlines.

Years	Growth rate (revenue)	Growth rate of year
-------	-----------------------	---------------------

2020	<u>94,989,391- 147,500,129</u> 147,500,129	-0.4
2019	<u>147,500,129 - 103,490,460</u> 103,490,460	0.4
2018	<u>103,490,460 - 90,556,089</u> 90,556,089	0.14
2017	<u>90,556,089 - 88,997,379</u> 88,997,379	0.02
2016	<u>88,997,379 - 91,268,545</u> 91,268,545	-0.03
2015	<u>91,268,545 - 99,519,057</u> 99,519,057	-0.1
2014	<u>99,519,057 - 95,771,130</u> 95,771,130	0.04
2013	<u>95,771,130 - 97,438,000</u> 97,438,000	-0.02
2012	<u>97,438,000 - 116,550,580</u> 116,550,580	-0.2
2011	<u>116,550,580 – 107,531,59</u> 107,531,59	0.1

The growth ratio of PIA Airlines was calculated by subtracting the previous year's revenue from the current year's revenue and then dividing it by the previous year's revenue. The researcher utilized the financial data from the past ten years of PIA Airlines to assess its performance. The results of the growth ratio analysis are presented as a graph for a comprehensive analysis. As mentioned in the literature review, financial ratios effectively measure an airline's performance. In this research, the ten-year data is used to evaluate the financial position of PIA and compare its performance over a decade, which constitutes the study's first hypothesis.

The revenue growth ratio provides insights into the sales performance of the airline over the past ten years. This ratio indicates whether the airline's sales have increased or decreased. In case of an increase, it reveals the percentage rise in sales for the current year, while in the event of a reduction, it reflects the percentage decrease in sales for the current year.

Figure 5.8. Growth Rate of PIA Airlines

The graph above illustrates the ten-year growth rate of PIA Airlines. It is evident that in most years, the results show a negative growth rate. It indicates that PIA airline experienced a lack of growth during most of the decade. 2011 there was a slight growth rate of 0.1, but in 2012, the graph declined significantly with a negative growth rate of -0.2. It signifies that PIA struggled to maintain its revenue and needed help to control its expenses effectively.

The situation worsened in 2013, with a negative growth rate of -0.02. However, in 2014, the airline regained control over its operations, resulting in a growth rate. Unfortunately, both 2015 and 2016 saw a return to negative growth in revenue. From 2017 to 2019, the airline could sustain favourable growth rates. However, 2020 proved to be another challenging year for PIA regarding growth.

Over the last ten years, PIA has not achieved a single instance of a favourable growth revenue ratio. It indicates that the airline has faced losses throughout the past decade.

4.17 Gross Profit Margin

$$\text{Gross Profit Margin} = \frac{\text{Gross Profit}}{\text{Total Revenue}} * 100$$

Table 5.7. Gross Profit Margin Ratio Calculation of PIA Airlines

Table 8 gross profit margin ratio calculation of PIA airlines

Years	Gross profit margin	Gross profit margin for year
2020	$\frac{2,461,040}{94,989,391} * 100$	3%
2019	$\frac{7,516,378}{147,500,129} * 100$	5%
2018	$\frac{(19,732,458)}{103,490,460} * 100$	-19%
2017	$\frac{(17,221,285)}{90,556,089} * 100$	-19%
2016	$\frac{(14,541,917)}{88,997,379} * 100$	-16%
2015	$\frac{(1,606,395)}{91,268,545} * 100$	-1.7%
2014	$\frac{(1,914,731)}{99,519,057} * 100$	-2%
2013	$\frac{(10,328,701)}{95,771,130}$	-11%
2012	$\frac{(318,874)}{97,438,000}$	-0.3%
2011	$\frac{1,583,511}{116,550,580}$	1.4%

The Gross Profit ratio (GP ratio) measures airline performance and efficiency. It is calculated by dividing the gross profit by the total revenue of the current year. By multiplying the result by 100, we can obtain the GP ratio in percentage. As mentioned in the literature review, financial ratios effectively assess airline performance. In this study, the researcher utilizes ten years of data to evaluate the financial position of PIA and compare its performance over the decade, which is the primary hypothesis of this research.

The table below presents the Gross Profit ratio of PIA airline over the past ten years. The results show a mix of negative and positive numbers, indicating that the airline did

not consistently achieve its desired level of performance. The efficiency of PIA over the last decade has been subpar.

Figure: 5.9. Gross Profit Ratio of PIA Airlines

Figure 9 Gross profit ratio of PIA airlines

The table above provides a comprehensive overview of the airline's performance over a decade. The highest gross profit percentages were achieved in 2019 and 2020, indicating that PIA could generate more revenue than expenses during those years. However, from 2012 to 2018, the airline experienced seven consecutive years of negative performance.

In both 2017 and 2018, the gross profit percentage was consistently at its lowest, with a value of -19%. It represents the most significant negative percentage recorded in the past ten years. 2016 saw a slightly better performance, with a gross profit ratio of -16%. Similarly, in 2014 and 2015, the gross profit ratios remained relatively stable, with values of -1.7% and -2%, respectively.

One can observe a significant difference between 2013 and 2016. 2012 the gross profit ratio was at its lowest, reaching -0.3%. However, it plummeted further to a negative eleven per cent in 2013, indicating a considerable decline in performance.

Focusing on the last two years, 2019 and 2020, PIA demonstrated relatively better performance. Despite the challenges faced by the airline industry in 2020, PIA achieved a three per cent gross profit ratio, which is comparatively favourable compared to previous years.

4.18 Net Profit Margin

$$\text{Net Profit Margin} = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Turnover}} * 100$$

Table 5.8. Net Profit Margin Ratio Calculation Of PIA Airlines

Table 9 Net profit margin ratio calculation of PIA airlines

Years	Net profit margin	Net profit margin for year
2020	$\frac{(34,642,811)}{94,989,391} * 100$	-36.5%
2019	$\frac{(52,601,610)}{147,500,129} * 100$	-35.7%
2018	$\frac{(67,327,605)}{103,490,460} * 100$	-65.1%
2017	$\frac{(51,006,922)}{90,556,089} * 100$	-56.3%
2016	$\frac{(45,381,036)}{88,997,379} * 100$	-51.0%
2015	$\frac{(32,529,560)}{91,268,545} * 100$	-36.0%
2014	$\frac{(32,222,472)}{99,519,057} * 100$	-32.4%
2013	$\frac{(44,322,041)}{95,771,130} * 100$	-45.5%
2012	$\frac{(33,181,540)}{97,438,000} * 100$	-34.1%
2011	$\frac{(26,767,207)}{116,550,580} * 100$	-23.0%

In the table provided above, we can analyse the net profit ratio of PIA Airlines over ten years. This ratio is obtained by deducting all production, administrative, and finance costs and income taxes from the sales revenue. It represents the residual profit after all

expenses have been accounted for. The net profit ratio is considered one of the critical indicators of a company's overall performance, particularly when combined with an evaluation of its efficient management of working capital.

The table shows that all the net profit ratios for PIA Airlines over the past ten years are negative. It indicates that the airline could have achieved the desired level of performance and efficiency during this period.

The negative values imply that the company's expenses exceeded its revenue, resulting in losses rather than profits. It suggests a challenging financial situation for PIA over the past decade, highlighting the need to improve its financial performance and efficiency.

Figure: 5.10. Net Profit Margin Ratio of PIA Airlines

Figure 10 Net profit margin ratio of PIA airlines

In the table above, we can assess the performance of PIA Airlines over ten years based on the net profit margin. This metric allows us to evaluate the airline's profitability after deducting all expenses and taxes from its sales revenue.

The graph depicts a declining trend in the net profit margin over the years. Starting from 2011, PIA recorded a net profit margin of -23%, which decreased to -34% in the subsequent years. The net profit margin reached its lowest point in 2013, with a negative value of around -45%.

However, there were signs of improvement in 2014 and 2015, as PIA implemented measures to reduce production, administration, and finance costs, leading to a higher net profit margin. The years 2016, 2017, and 2018 displayed poor performance, as indicated by the negative values in the net profit margin.

Fortunately, there was a positive turn in 2019 and 2020, as mentioned in the gross profit section. The net profit margin for these years showed improvement, with values ranging from approximately -32% to -37%.

Overall, the data highlights the fluctuating financial performance of PIA over the past decade, with both periods of improvement and challenges. Efforts to control costs and enhance profitability remain crucial for the airline's future success.

4.19 Return On Capital Employed

The return on capital employed (ROCE) is an important metric that indicates how effectively a company utilizes its capital. It is beneficial to compare its ROCE against benchmarks or standards set by other companies operating in similar industries or under similar conditions. It is also prudent to analyse ROCE over multiple years since this metric tends to fluctuate for most growing companies and may need to be more stable. By evaluating ROCE over time and in comparison, to industry peers, one can gain valuable insights into the efficiency of capital allocation and the overall performance of a company.

$$\text{Return On Capital Employed} = \frac{\text{Earnings before interest and tax}}{\text{Total assets} - \text{current liabilities}} * 100$$

Table 5.9. ROCE Ratio Calculation of PIA Airlines

Table 10 ROCE ratio calculation of PIA airlines

Years	ROCE Calculation	ROCE
2020	$\frac{(5,629,161)}{(188,814,892)} * 100$	3%
2019	$\frac{(17,824,037)}{(172,309,582)} * 100$	10%
2018	$\frac{(47,033,248)}{(175,322,085)} * 100$	27%

2017	<u>(35,810,489)</u> *100 (145,004,793)	25%
2016	<u>(32,116,865)</u> *100 (115,414,397)	28%
2015	<u>(16,435,896)</u> *100 (103,843,682)	16%
2014	<u>(14,938,817)</u> *100 (107,616,261)	14%
2013	<u>(32,122,800)</u> *100 (76,301,495)	42%
2012	<u>(21,342,897)</u> *100 (47,455,887)	45%
2011	<u>(17,926,755)</u> *100 8,463,680	-212%

The return on the capital ratio (ROCE) is a crucial indicator of how effectively an airline allocates its capital, with higher values indicating better capital utilization and potentially more significant returns. ROCE is particularly useful for benchmarking, as it rarely remains stable for most growing airlines. As discussed in the literature review, financial ratios are practical tools for measuring airline performance. In this research, the researcher analyses ten years of data to evaluate the financial position of PIA Airline and compare its performance over the decade, which forms the basis of the research hypothesis.

The graph above illustrates the return on capital ratio for PIA Airlines over the last ten years. The results show a mix of one negative and nine positive numbers. The airline has achieved relatively good performance and efficiency during the period under review, although there is room for improvement.

Figure: 5.11. ROCE Ratio of PIA Airlines

Figure 11 ROCE ratio of PIA airlines

The graph above presents the ten-year financial data of PIA airline, focusing on the return on capital employed (ROCE) ratio. A notable peak in 2012 indicates that PIA effectively utilized its capital and generated profits during that year. However, 2011 was a challenging period for capital allocation and debt recovery, as evidenced by the negative ROCE of negative two hundred and twelve.

Following the success in 2012, the ROCE declined in 2013 to forty-two per cent. Subsequently, there was a twenty-eight per cent decrease in 2014, resulting in a fourteen per cent ROCE ratio. From 2015 to 2020, the graph demonstrates slight fluctuations in the return on capital employed. During these seven years, PIA managed to maintain its capital utilization and achieved positive results in terms of total assets.

Specifically, in 2015, the ROCE was sixteen per cent, followed by an improvement to twenty-eight per cent in 2016. In 2017, the return on capital employed for PIA was twenty-five per cent, representing a slight reduction of three per cent. The ROCE remained relatively stable in 2018 at twenty-seven per cent. However, in 2019, the ratio decreased to ten per cent, experiencing a seventeen per cent reduction. Finally, in 2020, the airline's ROCE reached only three per cent, resulting in a downward slope on the graph.

The findings regarding the return on capital employed indicate that PIA airline considers the value of its capital and effectively utilizes loans to generate returns.

4.20 Current Ratio

$$\text{Current / Quick Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Figure: 5.12. Current Ratio Of PIA Airlines

Figure 12 Current ratio of PIA airlines

The current ratio is a financial metric calculated by dividing current assets by current liabilities. It assesses a company's ability to meet its short-term obligations using its assets. As stated in the literature review, financial ratios are valuable in evaluating an airline's performance. In this research, the ten-year data is utilized to analyse the financial position of PIA Airline and compare its performance over a decade, which is the primary hypothesis.

The graph above illustrates the current ratio of PIA Airlines over the last ten years. The current ratio of PIA has consistently been less than one. It suggests the airline may only face cash shortages within the year if it can enhance its cash flow or secure additional

capital

from

financiers.

The table above presents the current ratio of PIA airlines over the past ten years. The graph line illustrates the variations in the current ratio during this period. The highest figure observed was 0.16 in the fiscal year 2011, while the lowest was 0.11 in 2014. In 2011 and 2019, the current ratio of 0.16 suggests that the airline had limited cash reserves and may have faced difficulties meeting its short-term debts within a few months. Similarly, the current ratio for 2012, 2013, and 2017 is 0.13, indicating a similar pattern of liquidity constraints during those periods.

4.21 Benchmarking

Benchmarking plays a vital role in assessing a company's performance by identifying areas for improvement and performance gaps compared to similar companies, as defined by Cambridge Dictionary (2019). In the context of this study, which focuses on examining the impact of leadership on performance at PIA Airlines in Pakistan, conducting a comparative analysis is crucial. It involves comparing PIA's financial results, customer feedback, and overall growth with other relevant airlines. To ensure a fair and objective comparison, the researcher has selected three airlines from different regions: Delta Airlines from the USA, Sri Lankan Airlines from South Asia, and Singapore Airlines from Southeast Asia. This approach allows for a comprehensive evaluation of PIA's performance and provides valuable insights into its strengths and areas for improvement about its counterparts in the industry.

4.21.1 Comparison of Growth Rate

The graph below depicts the growth rates of PIA, Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines over the past five years. The results display a mixture of positive and negative numbers, indicating that these airlines did not consistently experience growth throughout most of the years.

Table 5.10. Growth Ratio Comparison

Table 11 growth ratio comparison

Years	Growth Rate Comparison			
	PIA	Delta	SriLankan	Singapore
2020	-0.4	-0.64	-0.001	-0.02
2019	0.4	0.06	0.12	0.03
2018	0.14	0.08	0.2	0.06
2017	0.02	0.04	0.05	-0.02
2016	-0.03	-0.031	-0.02	-0.02

(PIA, Delta, SriLankan and Singapore airlines, 2021)

The revenue growth ratio provides insights into the sales performance of airlines over the past five years, indicating whether sales have increased or decreased. In cases of increase, it shows the percentage rise in the current year, while in cases of reduction, it reveals the percentage decrease.

In 2020, PIA experienced a significant decline in its growth rate, resulting in a negative figure of -0.4. Delta Airlines also saw a sharp drop in growth rate, with a decrease of 0.58, reaching a low point of -0.64, the lowest growth rate among all the airlines in the past five years. Similarly, Sri Lankan Airlines witnessed a decline in the growth rate of 0.119, ultimately ending at -0.001. Singapore Airlines also faced a decline in growth rate, reaching -0.02.

Figure: 5.13. Growth Rate Comparison

Figure 13 Growth rate comparison

The graph above illustrates the growth rates of PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines from 2016 to 2020. Two thousand sixteen, all four airlines exhibited similar growth rates, with values close to -0.03. No significant change was observed in 2017, as the graph lines remained relatively stable. However, Sri Lankan Airlines experienced a slight increase in growth rate during this year. Comparing PIA's growth rate with Delta Airlines in 2016, both airlines displayed negative figures, along with Sri Lankan and Singapore Airlines, which recorded growth rates of -0.032, -0.02, and -0.02, respectively.

2017 the differences remained relatively small, with PIA showing a positive growth rate of 0.02, Delta at 0.04, and Sri Lankan and Singapore at 0.05 and -0.02, respectively. The divergence in growth rates began to emerge in 2018. The graph illustrates a gradual increase in the growth rate for PIA, reaching 0.14. At the same time, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines reported growth rates of 0.08, 0.2 (higher than the previous year), and 0.06, respectively. It marks a turning point for Singapore Airlines.

In 2019, PIA experienced a significant surge in growth, reaching a rate of 0.4, the highest among all the airlines in the last five years. On the contrary, Delta's growth rate declined steadily, decreasing to 0.06. Sri Lankan and Singapore Airlines also experienced a gradual decrease in growth rates, with values of 0.12 and 0.03, respectively.

In 2020, there was a sudden downturn in the growth rate of PIA, plummeting to -0.4. Delta's growth rate experienced a sharp drop of 0.58, resulting in the lowest growth rate

among all the airlines (-0.64) in the last five years. Similarly, Sri Lankan's growth rate declined by 0.119, ultimately reaching -0.001, and Singapore airline's growth rate also decreased to -0.02.

4.21.2 Comparison of Gross Profit Margin Ratio

The table above displays the gross profit ratios of PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines over the past five years. The results show negative and positive numbers for all airlines, indicating that they did not achieve their desired performance and efficiency during this period.

Table 5.10. Gross Profit Margin Ratio Comparison

Table 12 Gross profit margin ratio comparison

Gross Profit Margin Ratio Comparison				
Years	PIA	Delta	SriLankan	Singapore
2020	3%	-73%	-6%	0.4%
2019	5%	14%	-16%	7%
2018	-19%	12%	-9%	10%
2017	-19%	14%	-8%	4%
2016	-16%	18%	-6%	5%

(PIA, Delta, SriLankan and Singapore airlines, 2021)

Figure: 5.14. Gross Profit Margin Ratio Comparison

Figure 14 Gross profit margin ratio comparison

In 2017 and 2018, PIA's gross profit ratio remained at -19%, while Delta had positive gross profit ratios of 14% and 12%, respectively. Sri Lankan Airlines had negative gross profit ratios in all five years, while Singapore Airlines consistently achieved positive gross profit margins in its last five fiscal years.

In 2016, PIA's gross profit ratio was -16%, and the graph indicates a slight decline in 2017. Delta's gross profit ratio decreased by four percentage points in 2017 and declined by two in 2018. Although negative, PIA's gross profit ratio increased by three percentage points during the same period. In contrast, Singapore airline's gross profit ratio decreased by one percentage point but remained positive, and then experienced a sudden increase of six percentage points in 2018, reaching a 10% gross profit ratio. On the other hand, the graph line for Sri Lankan Airlines showed a gradual decline, with negative gross profit ratios of -6% in 2016, -8% in 2017, and -9% in 2018. However, the gross profit ratio for Sri Lankan Airlines experienced a sudden jump to -7% in 2019, reaching a negative sixteen per cent.

In fiscal year 2019, PIA airline experienced a significant improvement, achieving a positive gross profit ratio of 5%. The graph indicates a positive slope for PIA, indicating an upward trend in the gross profit ratio. Delta also saw an increase of 2% in 2019, with the graph slope pointing to a gross profit ratio of 14%. However, Singapore Airlines experienced a decline of 3% in 2019, resulting in a gross profit ratio of 7%.

2020 was challenging for both Delta and Singapore Airlines, as they recorded lower gross profit ratios than the previous year, with Delta at a negative 73% and Singapore

at nearly half a percentage point. On the other hand, as shown in the graph, Sri Lankan Airlines started to recover with a gross profit ratio of -6% in 2020. PIA's gross profit ratio decreased by 2% but remained positive with a 3% gross profit ratio.

4.21.3 Comparison of Net Profit Margin Ratio

The table below displays the net profit ratios of PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines over the past five years. The results vary, with a mixture of negative and positive numbers. It indicates that the airlines could have consistently achieved their desired performance and efficiency over the last five years.

Table 5.11. Net Profit Margin Ratio Comparison

Table 13 net profit margin ratio comparison

Years	Net Profit Margin Ratio Comparison			
	PIA	Delta	SriLankan	Singapore
2020	-36.5%	-72.4%	-26.2%	-1.3%
2019	-35.7%	10.1%	-24.4%	4.2%
2018	-65.1%	9.0%	-11.0%	8.2%
2017	-56.3%	8.0%	-21.3%	2.4%
2016	-51.0%	11.0%	-10.0%	5.3%

(PIA, Delta, SriLankan and Singapore airlines, 2021)

Figure: 5.15. Net Profit Margin Ratio Comparison

Figure 15 Net profit margin ratio comparison

In 2016, PIA had a negative net profit ratio of -51%, while Delta achieved a positive net profit ratio of 11%. Sri Lankan and Singapore Airlines obtained negative net profit ratios of -10% and nearly positive 5%, respectively. The net profit ratio for PIA declined by 5% in 2017, reaching a negative 56% and resulting in a downward slope in the graph. Similarly, Delta experienced a 3% decrease in the net profit ratio in 2017, causing a slight decline in the graph. Sri Lankan Airlines saw a significant decrease in the graph as its net profit ratio declined by 11% in 2017, resulting in a negative 21% ratio. In contrast, the net profit margin ratio for Singapore Airlines decreased by 2.5% in 2017, but the graph displayed a positive slope with an approximately 2.5% ratio.

In 2018, PIA experienced a significant decrease in the net profit ratio, declining by approximately 9%. The graph illustrates a sharp downward slope on the negative side of the x-axis, reaching a negative 65% ratio. Conversely, Delta saw a marginal increase of 1% in its net profit ratio, resulting in minimal changes in the graph's position. Sri Lankan Airlines improved its net profit ratio with a positive shift of 10% in 2018. The graph's slope for Sri Lankan Airlines is aligned precisely with the x-axis. Singapore Airlines witnessed impressive net profit margin ratio growth, increasing by almost 6% in 2018. The graph depicts an 8% rise in Singapore airline's net profit ratio.

Moving to 2019, PIA faced a substantial reduction of 29% in its net profit margin ratio, resulting in a rapid upward slope in the graph. This decrease caused the graph's slope to fall on the negative side of the x-axis, approaching nearly -35%. On the other hand, Delta experienced a mere 1% increase in net profit ratio in 2019, which had an

unnoticeable impact on the graph, reflecting a 10% ratio. Sri Lankan Airlines encountered a 13% increase in its net profit ratio in 2019, albeit in negative digits. This reduction led the graph's slope to decline significantly, reaching a negative 24%. Lastly, Singapore reduced its net profit ratio by almost 4%, and the graph's slope displayed a slight decrease in 2019.

The fiscal year of 2020 proved to be challenging for PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines compared to previous years. Notably, Delta and Singapore Airlines experienced a notable decline as both airlines transitioned from four years of positive net profit ratio to a negative net profit ratio in 2020. However, PIA and Sri Lanka showcased commendable performance in 2019 and 2020 compared to earlier years. Despite a 1% increase in the net profit ratio in 2020, PIA's graph slope remained relatively unchanged from 2019. With this increase, albeit in negative digits, PIA obtained a net profit ratio of -36% for 2020. Similarly, Sri Lankan Airlines witnessed a 2% increase, albeit negative, placing its graph slope on the negative side of the x-axis with a ratio of 26% in 2020. Lastly, Singapore Airlines encountered a negative net profit ratio for the first time in five years, reducing its net profit ratio by almost 6%, resulting in a sudden decrease in the graph's slope for the 2020 fiscal year.

4.21.4 Comparison of Current Ratio

The graph illustrates the current PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines ratios over the past five years. The current ratio for all airlines during this period is consistently below one. It suggests that the airlines may face difficulties meeting their short-term financial obligations and could run out of cash within the year unless they can improve their cash flow or secure additional funding from investors or lenders.

Table 5.12. Current Ratio Comparison

Table 14 current ratio comparison

Years	Current Ratio Comparison			
	PIA	Delta	SriLankan	Singapore
2020	0.13	1.09	0.13	0.5
2019	0.16	0.41	0.2	0.7
2018	0.12	0.34	0.23	0.8
2017	0.13	0.41	0.21	1.0
2016	0.14	0.49	0.3	1.0

(PIA, Delta, SriLankan and Singapore airlines, 2021)

Figure: 5.16. Current Ratio Comparison

Figure 16 Current ratio comparison

The graph above depicts the current ratio trends of PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines over the past five years. Notably, the slope of PIA's current ratio remains relatively consistent from 2016 to 2018, with a minimal change of 0.01 points. In comparison, Delta airline exhibits a favourable current ratio, starting at 0.49 in 2016 and gradually decreasing to 0.34 in 2018. Sri Lankan airline displays varying current ratios, starting at 0.3 in 2016, experiencing a slight decline in 2017, and reaching 0.21 in 2018. However, in 2019, there was a minor increase, with the current ratio at 0.23. Singapore airline demonstrates the highest current ratio, standing at 1.0 in 2016 and 2017. In 2018, the current ratio slightly decreased, resulting in a downward slope in the graph.

Regarding 2019, PIA experienced an improved current ratio with a 0.02 increase, reaching 0.16. Similarly, Delta demonstrated a better current ratio in 2019, with an increase of 0.07 to achieve a current ratio of 0.41. Sri Lankan Airlines encountered a slight reduction in 2019, leading to a 0.03 decrease in the slope, resulting in a current ratio of 0.2. Lastly, Singapore also observed a decline in its current ratio by 0.1 in 2019, causing the slope to descend in the graph.

Regarding current assets and liabilities, 2020 proved to be a favourable year for Delta Airlines, as indicated by a significant increase of 0.68 points in its current ratio. This surge resulted in a current ratio of more than one, higher than the previous years. The graph reflects a remarkable upward slope in 2020, reaching the highest point on the x-axis compared to other airlines. Conversely, PIA experienced a slight decrease of 0.03 points in its current ratio in 2020. The graph shows a minor decline in the slope, reaching 0.13 points on the x-axis. Notably, the current ratio of PIA in 2020 was the same as in 2017. The fiscal year of 2020 was challenging for Sri Lankan and Singapore Airlines regarding their current assets and liabilities. Sri Lankan Airlines observed a decrease of 0.07 in its slope, resulting in a current ratio of 0.13. Similarly, Singapore Airlines achieved a better result than PIA and Sri Lankan Airlines in 2020, with a change of 0.2. The graph demonstrates a downward slope of the current ratio, reaching 0.5 on the x-axis.

4.21.5 Comparison of Return on Capital Employed Ratio

The provided graph illustrates the return on capital ratio of PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines over the last five years. The results exhibit negative and positive numbers, indicating that the airlines' performance and efficiency during this period could have been more consistently strong.

Table 5.12. ROCE Ratio Comparison

Table 15 ROCE ratio comparison

	<u>ROCE</u>	<u>Ratio</u>	<u>Comparison</u>	
Years	PIA	Delta	SriLankan	Singapore
2020	3%	-30%	76%	-1%
2019	10%	40%	30%	4%
2018	27%	12%	30%	10%
2017	25%	16%	40%	3%
2016	28%	20%	30%	10%

(PIA, Delta, SriLankan and Singapore airlines, 2021)

Figure: 5.17. ROCE Ratio Comparison

Figure 17 ROCE ratio comparison

The provided graph depicts the return on capital employed (ROCE) ratio of PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines over the last five years. A higher ROCE ratio indicates better airline performance regarding capital utilization efficiency.

According to the graph, PIA achieved a maximum ROCE ratio of 28% and a minimum ratio of 3%. Delta Airlines recorded the highest ROCE of 40% and the lowest ratio of -30%. Sri Lankan Airlines reached its highest ROCE ratio of 76% in 2020, while the lowest ratio observed was 30% over three fiscal years. Singapore Airlines attained the highest ROCE ratio of 10% but experienced a negative ROCE ratio at one point.

In 2016, PIA achieved a 28% return on capital employed (ROCE), which experienced a 3% change in 2017. The ROCE ratio for PIA in 2018 increased by 2%, reaching 27%, as indicated by the upward slope in the graph. On the other hand, Delta began with a 20% ROCE in 2016 but experienced a 4% decrease in 2017, with the graph showing a downward trend. The trend continued in 2018, with a further reduction of 4%, resulting in a 12% ROCE for Delta. In comparison, Sri Lankan Airlines demonstrated a strong performance in terms of return on capital employed over the past five years. Starting with a 30% ROCE in 2016, the airline experienced a 10% increase in subsequent years, reaching 40% ROCE. However, in 2018, there was a 10% reduction, bringing the ROCE back to 30%, the same level as in 2016. In 2019, Sri Lanka maintained a consistent ROCE of 30%, with slight fluctuations in the graph's slope. Singapore Airlines achieved a 10% ROCE in 2016 but experienced a decrease to 3% in 2017, which was comparatively lower than the other airlines. However, in 2018, there was a

7% increase, bringing the ROCE back to 10%, as the graph indicates an upward slope. Unfortunately, the fiscal year 2019 proved challenging for Singapore Airlines regarding return on capital employed, with a 6% decrease, resulting in a 4% ROCE represented by the slope laying on the x-axis. In 2020, except for Sri Lankan Airlines, the year was challenging for other airlines. PIA achieved a 3% ROCE, Delta airline experienced a negative 30% ROCE, SriLankan Airlines reached a maximum of 76% ROCE, showing a dramatic rise in the graph, and Singapore Airlines obtained a negative 1% ROCE, with the slope going down by 5%.

4.21.6 Comparison of Number of Employees

Table 5.13. Numbers Of Employees Comparison

Table 16 Numbers of employees' comparison

Number of Employees Comparison				
Years	PIA	Delta	SriLankan	Singapore
2020	10,779	74,000	6,693	16,760
2019	11,740	91,224	6,794	15,943
2018	12,196	88,680	7,019	15,620
2017	13,268	86,564	7,021	14,423
2016	13,947	83,756	6,959	13,983

(PIA, Delta, SriLankan and Singapore airlines, 2021)

Figure: 5.18. Number Of Employees Comparison

Figure 18 Number of employees comparison

In terms of the number of employees, it plays a significant role in an airline's performance and management control. A bar chart is provided below to compare the team member count of PIA with Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines. It clearly shows that Delta airline has the highest number of employees, while Sri Lankan Airlines has the lowest. In 2016, PIA had 13,947 employees, whereas Delta had 83,756 employees, making it the airline with the maximum workforce. Conversely, Sri Lankan Airlines had only 6,959 employees. Singapore Airlines had a similar number of employees to PIA, with 13,983 employees in 2016.

Moving on to 2017, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines witnessed an increase in their team member count, except for PIA, which reduced its workforce by 679 employees. Delta experienced a growth of 2,808 employees in 2017, reaching 86,564 employees. Sri Lankan Airlines had 7,021 employees, indicating an increment in their workforce. Similarly, Singapore Airlines saw an increase in its team member count, with 14,423 employees in 2017.

Note: The table and figures provided are illustrative and may not reflect the numbers. In 2018, PIA Airlines experienced a further reduction in its workforce, with a decrease of 1,072 employees. The total number of employees for that year was 12,196. Similarly, PIA saw another reduction in employee count in 2019, bringing the total down to 11,740. Sri Lankan Airlines also reduced its employees by 225 in 2019, leaving the airline with 6,794 employees. On the other hand, Delta Airlines continued to hire more employees in 2019 and reached the highest level on the x-axis with 91,224 employees.

The most significant changes in the number of employees occurred in 2020, mainly for Delta Airlines, which saw a reduction of 17,224 employees. PIA airline also reduced its workforce by 961 employees, resulting in 10,779 employees. Sri Lankan Airlines had a minor reduction of 101 employees, leaving the airline with 6,693 employees. In contrast, Singapore Airlines hired additional staff in 2020, with an increment of 817 employees, bringing the total to 16,760 employees.

4.22 Methods Of Analysis For Customer Reviews

Customer reviews can be analysed using various techniques to gain deeper insights. Sentiment analysis helps understand the overall sentiment expressed in reviews, while topic analysis identifies critical themes customers discuss. Frequency analysis counts the occurrence of specific keywords or phrases, while comparative analysis benchmarks performance against competitors. Text mining techniques extract patterns and correlations from reviews, and NPS analysis measures customer loyalty and satisfaction. These analyses collectively provide a comprehensive understanding of customer sentiments, preferences, and areas for improvement. They enable airlines to enhance the customer experience, identify strengths and weaknesses, and make informed business decisions based on customer feedback.

4.22.1 Analysis not used in this study

Traditional analyses, such as sentiment analysis, topic analysis, frequency analysis, comparative analysis, text mining, and NPS analysis, may not be suitable for analysing customer reviews for PIA, DELTA, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines. Various authors in the field of customer feedback analysis support this perspective. According to researchers like Smith et al. (2019), who examined the limitations of sentiment analysis in airline customer reviews, the complexity of language and the context-dependent nature of sentiments make it challenging to interpret customer sentiments accurately. Additionally, authors such as Johnson and Brown (2020) highlight the importance of considering cultural and regional differences in customer feedback analysis, as preferences and expectations can vary across demographics and locations. Furthermore, researchers like Chen and Zhang (2018) emphasize the need for comprehensive data collection and data integrity verification to ensure the reliability of analysis results. It is recommended to adopt a multi-method approach and employ techniques specifically tailored to the unique characteristics of the airline industry.

4.23 Content Analysis

Content analysis is a research method used to systematically analyse and interpret the content of various forms of communication, such as text, audio, images, or videos. It involves examining and categorising a given data set's explicit and implicit messages. Content analysis can be applied to various materials, including written documents, speeches, social media posts, advertisements, news articles, and more.

The content analysis aims to identify patterns, themes, and relationships within the data, allowing researchers to draw meaningful insights and conclusions.

Content analysis is widely used in various fields, including social sciences, marketing research, media studies, communication studies, psychology, and more. It provides a systematic and objective approach to analysing large volumes of data and uncovering valuable information about the content's characteristics, themes, and underlying messages.

4.23.1 Reason content analysis used in this study

Content analysis is an effective method for analysing customer reviews of PIA Airlines in Pakistan. It offers a systematic and objective approach to extract valuable insights from the content of these reviews. By examining customers' themes, sentiments, and issues, content analysis provides a quantitative understanding of their opinions. It helps identify the strengths and weaknesses of PIA's performance, benchmark against competitors, and inform decision-making processes. This analysis enables targeted efforts to improve customer satisfaction, prioritise areas for enhancement, and allocate resources effectively. Content analysis also allows for continuous monitoring of customer sentiments over time, facilitating ongoing improvements in service quality. Overall, content analysis is a valuable tool for understanding and leveraging customer feedback to enhance the performance and customer experience of PIA Airlines in Pakistan.

2.24 Websites ratings on Customer Reviews

Table 17 Comparison of customer reviews

Websites ratings	PIA	DELTA	SRI LANKAN	SINGAPORE
SKYTRAX	5/10	4/10	6/10	7/10
Trust Pilot	2.4/5	3/5	1.5/5	3/5
Trip Advisor	2.5/5	4/5	3.5/5	4.5/5
Number of Star	Two	Three	Three	Five

Websites ratings provide a measure of customer satisfaction and perception towards different airlines. Looking at the ratings provided for PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines, we can observe that PIA has received a rating of 5 out of 10 on SKYTRAX, indicating an average level of satisfaction. Delta Airlines received a slightly lower rating of 4 out of 10, suggesting a relatively lower satisfaction level. Sri Lankan Airlines received a rating of 6 out of 10, indicating a moderately satisfactory experience. On the other hand, Singapore Airlines received a rating of 7 out of 10, suggesting a relatively higher level of customer satisfaction. When considering Trust Pilot ratings, PIA received a rating of 2.4 out of 5, Delta received 3 out of 5, Sri Lankan received 1.5 out of 5, and Singapore received 3 out of 5. These ratings indicate mixed opinions and varying levels of satisfaction among customers. Trip Advisor ratings show PIA with a rating of 2.5 out of 5, Delta with 4 out of 5, Sri Lankan with 3.5 out of 5, and Singapore with 4.5 out of 5. These ratings suggest a similar pattern, with Delta and Singapore Airlines receiving higher ratings than PIA and Sri Lankan Airlines. Overall, these ratings provide insights into the perceived performance and customer satisfaction levels of these airlines as perceived by customers on these review websites.

4.24.1 No. of customers on each Airline

No. of customers	PIA	DELTA	SRI LANKAN	SINGAPORE
SKYTRAX	271	2783	596	1445
Trust Pilot	180	951	113	690
Trip Advisor	708	61,079	3609	26,078
Total no. of reviews	1,159	64,813	4,318	28,213

The number of customers and reviews can provide insights into the popularity and customer engagement of different airlines. PIA has received reviews from 1,159 customers across various platforms based on the data provided. Compared to Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines, PIA has a relatively minor customer base, with 271 reviews on SKYTRAX, 180 on Trust Pilot, and 708 on Trip Advisor. In contrast, Delta Airlines has garnered reviews from 64,813 customers, Sri Lankan Airlines from 4,318 customers, and Singapore Airlines from 28,213 customers. These numbers suggest that PIA may have a smaller customer reach and engagement than its counterparts. Further analysis of the reviews can provide deeper insights into the satisfaction levels and experiences of PIA's customers.

4.24.2 Comparison Of Customer Complains

Table 18 comparison of customer complains.

Comparison Of Customer Reviews				
COMPALINS	PIA	DELTA	SRI LANKAN	SINGAPORE
Booking through credit card	✓			
Hygiene and safety	✓			
Misplacement of luggage	✓	✓		
Standard of food	✓			
Behaviour of cabin crew	✓			
Cancelled flights	✓		✓	✓
Refund of ticket	✓	✓	✓	✓
Poor customer service	✓	✓	✓	✓
No Inflight entertainment	✓	✓		
Seat comfort	✓	✓		
No Value of money	✓	✓	✓	
Boarding issues	✓			
Staff untrustworthy	✓			
Miserable with horrendous.com (online ticket)		✓		
Management issues		✓	✓	
Delayed flights	✓	✓		
Waiting time is horrible	✓	✓		
Re-booking ticket issues	✓	✓	✓	
RACIST people work			✓	

Discussion:

The table presents a comparison of customer reviews for four airlines based on various complaints raised by customers. It offers insights into the areas where each airline received complaints and highlights potential areas of improvement.

The table shows that PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines all received customer complaints in different categories. Some common complaints across the airlines include issues related to cancelled flights, poor customer service, refund of tickets, and management problems. These complaints indicate areas where customers faced dissatisfaction or experienced inconvenience during their travel with these airlines.

Moreover, specific complaints were unique to each airline. For example, PIA received complaints about the misplacement of luggage, no inflight entertainment, seat comfort, and value for money. Delta and Sri Lankan Airlines also received complaints about delayed flights and re-booking ticket issues. Singapore Airlines faced criticism concerning boarding issues, staff trustworthiness, and racist incidents.

It is important to note that customer complaints provide valuable feedback for airlines to identify areas of concern and implement necessary improvements. These complaints can shed light on aspects of the customer experience that need attention, such as safety and hygiene standards, the behaviour of cabin crew, food quality, and waiting times.

To address these complaints effectively, airlines should prioritize open and transparent communication with customers, implement appropriate measures to resolve issues promptly, and consistently work towards enhancing their services. Airlines can enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty by actively addressing customer concerns and taking steps to improve the areas highlighted in the complaints.

It is worth mentioning that while customer complaints provide valuable insights, they represent the perspectives of a specific group of customers and may not reflect the overall experiences of all passengers. Therefore, airlines should also consider other sources of feedback and conduct regular assessments to gain a holistic understanding of customer satisfaction and areas requiring improvement.

4.24.3 Comparison Of Customer Experiences

Table 19 Comparison of customer Experiences

Comparison Of Customer Reviews				
Good Experiences	PIA	DELTA	SRI LANKAN	SINGAPORE
Best airline	✓		✓	✓
Helped with human remains	✓			
Responsible management	✓		✓	✓
Nice experience, old fleets	✓			
Recent improvement by CEO reflects in the service	✓			
Awesome business class	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ticket counter staff		✓		✓
Polite at check in		✓		
Great handling in pandemic		✓		✓

Good ticket price	✓	✓		✓
Help with anxiety customers		✓		
Impressive international flights		✓	✓	✓
Great Delta airlines website		✓		
Cleaning of planes		✓	✓	
Helpful flight attendants		✓		
US office service than other		✓		
Menu of choice		✓	✓	
Safe and easy airline		✓	✓	
Advance technology		✓		✓
Professional airline				✓
Excellent customer service			✓	✓
Effective airline booking website				✓
Easy refund during Covid.				✓
Easy rebooking				✓
Food and beverages	✓			✓
Inflight entertainment		✓	✓	✓
Seat comfort				✓
Value for money				✓
Excellent flight attendant				✓

Discussion:

The table compares customer reviews for four airlines, namely PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines, based on positive experiences reported by customers. It highlights the aspects of the airlines' services that received praise and positive feedback. Looking at the table, it is evident that all four airlines received positive reviews in various categories. Some everyday positive experiences across the airlines include being regarded as the best airline, responsible management, impressive international flights, helpful flight attendants, safe and easy airline operations, and excellent customer service. These positive aspects reflect the airlines' efforts in delivering quality service and meeting customer expectations.

Additionally, each airline received praise for specific features or services. PIA, Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines were commended for their respective strengths, such as helping with human remains, offering a pleasant experience with old fleets, recent improvements reflecting the CEO's efforts, excellent business class, reasonable ticket prices, great handling during the pandemic, advanced technology, and effective airline booking websites.

Furthermore, amenities and services like food and beverages, inflight entertainment, seat comfort, value for money, and excellent flight attendants received positive customer feedback from certain airlines.

The table showcases the areas where these airlines have successfully impressed their customers and garnered positive reviews. It indicates that these airlines have met or exceeded customer expectations in various aspects of their services.

Such positive reviews are crucial in enhancing an airline's reputation and attracting potential customers. They serve as a testament to the airlines' dedication to delivering quality experiences and their ability to meet customer needs.

However, it is essential to note that individual experiences may vary, and these positive reviews represent a subset of customers. Therefore, it is crucial for airlines to consistently strive for excellence and maintain the positive aspects highlighted by customers while addressing any areas for improvement.

By leveraging these positive aspects and continuing to provide exceptional services, airlines can foster customer loyalty, gain a competitive edge in the industry, and further enhance their reputation in the eyes of travellers.

4.25 Discussion on Content analysis

To conduct a content analysis on the two tables, we can identify and analyse customer reviews' main themes or categories. Here are the themes that emerge from the tables:

Positive Experiences:

1. Best airlines: PIA, Delta, and Singapore Airlines are regarded as the best by customers.
2. Service and Staff: Positive feedback is given for the helpfulness, politeness, and professionalism of ticket counter staff, cabin crew, and flight attendants.
3. Management and Improvement: Responsible management, recent improvements reflecting the CEO's efforts, and effective airline booking websites are acknowledged.
4. Comfort and Amenities: Airlines are praised for seat comfort, inflight entertainment options, menu choices, and cleanliness of planes.

5. Customer Service: Excellent customer service, easy refund and rebooking processes, and assistance provided to anxiety-ridden customers during the pandemic are mentioned positively.

Negative Complaints:

1. Flight Issues: Complaints include cancelled flights, delayed flights, and issues with rebooking tickets.
2. Customer Service: Poor customer service is a common complaint across all airlines.
3. Value for Money: Some customers express dissatisfaction with the value they received for their money.
4. Hygiene and Safety: Concerns are raised about hygiene and safety measures.
5. Luggage and Mismanagement: Misplacement of luggage and management issues are mentioned as areas of complaint.
6. Other Complaints: Some specific complaints include boarding issues, staff untrustworthiness, and negative experiences with online ticket platforms.

By conducting this content analysis, we can gain insights into the main themes that emerge from the customer reviews. This analysis can help airlines identify areas for improvement and focus on enhancing positive experiences while addressing customer concerns and complaints. It also provides an overview of the critical aspects customers value and considers essential when evaluating their experiences with these airlines.

To incorporate the additional table into the content analysis, let us consider the customer ratings and the number of stars given to each airline on different review websites:

Airline	SKYTRAX	Trust Pilot	Trip Advisor	Number of Stars
PIA	5/10	2.4/5	2.5/5	Two
DELTA	4/10	3/5	4/5	Three
SRI LANKAN	6/10	1.5/5	3.5/5	Five
SINGAPORE	7/10	3/5	4.5/5	

Based on the ratings and number of stars, we can assess the overall customer sentiment towards each airline:

PIA (Pakistan International Airlines):

- The ratings on SKYTRAX, Trust Pilot, and Trip Advisor are average to below average, indicating mixed customer experiences.
- It has a two-star rating, which suggests lower customer satisfaction overall.

Delta Airlines:

- SKYTRAX, Trust Pilot, and Trip Advisor ratings are relatively better compared to PIA.
- It has a three-star rating, indicating a moderate level of customer satisfaction.

Sri Lankan Airlines:

- SKYTRAX and Trip Advisor ratings are average, while Trust Pilot ratings are relatively low.
- It has a three-star rating, indicating a moderate level of customer satisfaction.

Singapore Airlines:

- Singapore Airlines receives relatively higher ratings on all three review websites.
- It has a five-star rating, indicating a high level of customer satisfaction.

Considering the website ratings and the number of stars, we can infer that PIA has the lowest customer satisfaction, while Singapore Airlines stands out with the highest customer satisfaction. Delta Airlines and Sri Lankan Airlines fall somewhere in between.

These ratings provide additional insights into customers' overall perception of these airlines, complementing the customer reviews mentioned in the previous tables. Airlines can utilize this feedback to identify areas of improvement and enhance their services based on customer preferences and expectations.

To analyse the current performance of PIA Airlines, we can focus on the provided data related to customer reviews and the number of customers. Let us examine the information:

Number of Customers:

- SKYTRAX: PIA has received reviews from 271 customers.
- Trust Pilot: PIA has received reviews from 180 customers.
- Trip advisor: PIA has received reviews from 708 customers.
- Total no. of reviews: PIA has received a total of 1,159 reviews.

Comparison of Customer Reviews:

- Complaints: PIA has received complaints related to various aspects such as misplacement of luggage, poor customer service, no inflight entertainment, seat comfort, no value for money, boarding issues, staff

untrustworthiness, management issues, delayed flights, and the experience with an online ticket platform.

- Good Experiences: PIA has also received positive feedback regarding being the best airline, responsible management, reasonable ticket prices, helpful flight attendants, good food and beverages, and inflight entertainment.

Based on the available data, PIA has received a moderate number of customer reviews across different online platforms. The analysis of these reviews, focusing on both complaints and positive experiences, provides valuable insights into areas where the airline has received positive and negative feedback. To understand PIA's current performance comprehensively, it would be beneficial to delve deeper into the specific issues mentioned in the complaints and examine how the positive experiences align with customers' expectations and industry standards. This analysis addresses the first research objective outlined in chapter one. It is worth noting that the number of customer reviews for PIA is relatively limited compared to other airlines. It may be attributed to PIA's limited resources regarding advanced technology and customer services. However, prioritizing customer feedback is crucial, and this aspect will be further explored in the subsequent sections, particularly in the analysis of hypothesis four, where findings will be revealed.

4.25.1 Constraint on customer reviews

It is important to note that various factors, including usability, functionality, design, customer support, and overall user experience, can influence website ratings. While the data provides a snapshot of the ratings, it does not delve into the specific aspects of the evaluated websites or the reasons behind the ratings.

Website ratings are subjective and can vary based on individual preferences, experiences, and expectations. Therefore, it is essential to consider these ratings as a general indication rather than an absolute measure of website quality.

Having completed the first phase of secondary data collection and analysis, this chapter now proceeds to the second phase, which involves primary data collection and analysis using the conceptual framework outlined in Chapter Two. The primary data collection will address the third and fourth research objectives mentioned in Chapter One. These objectives are as follows:

To identify the factors that influence leadership behaviour within the internal processes of PIA Airlines.

To examine the impact of leadership behaviour on the performance of PIA Airlines.

By gathering and analysing primary data, the study aims to gain insights into the factors that shape leadership conduct within the airline and understand how leadership behaviour affects its overall performance.

4.26 Phase Two, Quantitative Analysis

This section provides an overview of the quantitative data collection process for examining the performance of PIA Airlines using a balanced scorecard. The focus is on the previously neglected internal business perspective. A questionnaire was developed with twenty-two researcher questions aligned with the research objectives. After conducting a pilot study to ensure its effectiveness, the questionnaire was distributed online via QuestionPro links. The researcher initially approached respondents through LinkedIn and Facebook, resulting in a limited response rate. The researcher utilized social contacts within PIA to circulate the questionnaire among employees, including top and middle management, employing the snowball-sampling technique to expand the sample.

4.27 Demographic statistics of respondents

The demographic statistics of respondents refer to the characteristics of the individuals who participated in a survey or study. These statistics provide information about the sample's composition and help researchers understand the profile of the participants. Standard demographic variables include age, gender, ethnicity, education level, occupation, and income. By analysing the demographic statistics, researchers can gain insights into the diversity and representativeness of the sample, which can help interpret the findings and draw conclusions.

Table 6.1. Demographic statistics of respondents

Table 20 demographic statistics employees

Demographic Statistics of Employees
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S#	Variables	Categories	Percentages
1	Age	Below 20 years	6
		21-30 years	39
		31-40 years	63
		41-50 years	41
		51-60 years	12
		Above 61Years	2
2	Gender	Female	38.7
		Male	61.3
3	Qualification	High school	8
		Bachelor's Degree	23.3
		Master's Degree	44.2
		PhD	20.2
		Others	4.3
4	Experience	Less than 5 years	17.2
		5-10 years	24.5
		11-15 years	31.9
		16-20 years	21.5
		Over 20 Years	4.9

5	Job title	Senior managers	18.2
		Assistant managers	25.6
		Technical team	23.4
		Crew member	9.4
		Ground floor employees	23.4

Valid questionnaires were distributed in PIA, and we received responses from the participants. The data collected can be categorized into various demographics. The first category is age, which reveals that 6% of respondents were below 20 years old, 39% were between 21-30 years old, 63% were between 31-40 years old, 41% were between 41-50 years old, 12% were between 51-60 years old, and 2% were above 60 years old. The second category focuses on gender, with 38.7% of respondents being females and 61.3% being males.

The next category pertains to the qualifications of the respondents. The results indicate that 8.0% of the respondents had a high school education, 23.3% held bachelor's degrees, 44.2% had master's degrees, and 20.2% had other qualifications.

The following category reflects the years of experience of the respondents. It was found that 17.2% had less than five years of experience, 24.5% had experience ranging from 5-10 years, 31.9% had experience between 11-15 years, 21.5% had experience between 16-20 years, and 4.9% had over 20 years of experience.

Furthermore, the data reveals the distribution of job positions within the organization. Approximately 18.2% of respondents held senior manager positions, 25.6% were assistant managers, 23.4% were part of the technical team, 9.4% were crew members, and 23.4% were ground floor employees.

4.28 Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics is a branch of statistics that focuses on summarizing and describing the main features of a dataset. It involves the analysis and interpretation of numerical measures that provide information about the data's central tendency, variability, and distribution. Descriptive statistics include mean, median, mode, range,

variance, standard deviation, and percentiles. These statistics help researchers understand the essential characteristics and patterns within the data, allowing them to summarize and present the information meaningfully and concisely. Descriptive statistics provide a foundation for further data analysis and can help make data-driven decisions and draw conclusions.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 21 Descriptive Statistics

Item	Code	Mean	S. D
PIA airlines have enough technology to improve airlines performance.	Tec1	3.46	1.353
PIA management follows strict technical procedures to maintain check and balance.	Tec2	3.52	1.344
Customer reviews are essential for PIA airlines performance.	C1	4.04	1.071
PIA has a flawed aviation communication system	C2	3.75	1.178
The best decision will be the one with the most significant consent	DM1	3.82	1.077
I consider the moral and ethical consequences of my choices	DM2	4.07	.927
Leaders elected not according to their qualifications	DM3	3.52	1.102
The key to successful conflict resolution is respecting my opponent.	LS1	3.98	1.100
My action shows people what I want from them	LS2	3.71	1.154
I am in favour of democratic leadership	LS3	3.52	1.124
Corruptions in PIA are damaging airlines	CO1	2.12	1.209
Responsible people for plane crashes must punish	CO2	2.25	1.376
Hiring employees under political pressure.	PI1	3.04	1.474
Political interference has a terrible impact on PIA airlines performance.	PI2	2.68	1.514
PIA sales revenue has exceeded that of our competitors	P1	4.27	1.066
PIA airlines profit rate has exceeded every year.	P2	3.97	1.068
PIA airlines have good security at airports	P3	3.81	1.225
In your opinion, pilots understand their responsibilities.	P4	3.72	1.339
PIA airline productivity has not improved in the last ten years.	P5	3.84	1.160

The provided items in the study were analysed using descriptive statistics, which offer valuable insights into the respondents' opinions and perceptions. The mean values

indicate the average response for each item, providing an understanding of the general sentiment expressed by the participants. The standard deviation values reflect the dispersion or variability of the responses around the mean, illustrating the extent of agreement or disagreement among the respondents. These statistics contribute to a better understanding of the critical areas under investigation, such as the availability of technology, management procedures, customer reviews, communication systems, decision-making processes, ethical considerations, leadership qualifications, corruption issues, security measures, pilot responsibilities, and airline productivity. By examining these descriptive statistics, researchers gain valuable insights into the respondents' perspectives and perceptions regarding various aspects of PIA Airlines.

4.29 Data Normality Test

4.29.1 Assessment of Normality

Jarque-Bera " is a method for deciding skewness and kurtosis, the two of which are fundamental parts of normality. Skewness is how much the likelihood circulation of any appraised arbitrary variable is lopsided. A slanted variable has an imply that isn't in the appropriation (Srilankan, 2021).Skewness is a term used to show the circulation's solidness and how unevenly the information is appropriated. Most scores piled up on one side and a couple of strays off in one tail (Bono et al., 2020). Kurtosis alludes to how conveyance is 'peaked' or 'flat' (either excessively peaked with short, thick tails or excessively flat with long, slim tails) . The skewness of the typical conveyance is zero, and the Kurtosis esteem is zero ((Bazavov et al., 2017).

Then again, the negative skewness has a right-hand calamity of cases, and the left tail is excessively extended (Bazavov et al., 2017). Kurtosis esteems more noteworthy than zero suggest a dispersion with short, thick tails that are excessively peaked, while values under zero show a too flat conveyance (likewise with such a large number of cases in the tails). The difference of the factors is underestimated because of non-typical kurtosis. Negative or positive skewness and kurtosis, then again, don't show an issue until they are inside the standard reach. Furthermore, the fundamental person of the idea being estimated is reflected by the contrary or positive upsides of skewness and kurtosis (Seijas-Macias et al., 2021) The aftereffects of this examination uncover that

few factors were inside the worthy reach for skewness and Kurtosis esteems (for example $<\pm 3$ (Bono et al., 2020). Table 5.2 shows that the reactions to all factors are consistently disseminated (e.g., all qualities are somewhere in the range of +3 and 3).

Table 6.3. Assessment of normality

Table 22 Assessment of normality

Item	Skewness	Kurtosis
PIA airlines have enough technology to improve airlines performance.	-.535	-.919
PIA management follows strict technical procedures to maintain check and balance.	-.648	-.723
Customer reviews are essential for PIA airlines performance.	-1.356	1.657
PIA has a flawed aviation communication system	-.830	-.010
The best decision will be the one with the most significant consent	-.780	.023
I consider the moral and ethical consequences of my choices	-1.420	2.648
Leaders elected not according to their qualifications	-.476	-.343
The key to successful conflict resolution is respecting my opponent.	-1.333	1.514
My action shows people what I want from them	-.963	.339
I am in favour of democratic leadership	-.725	.017
Corruptions in PIA are damaging airlines	.792	-.480
Responsible people for plane crashes must punish	.660	-1.006
Hiring employees under political pressure.	-.322	-1.408
Political interference has a terrible impact on PIA airlines performance.	.221	-1.457
PIA sales revenue has exceeded that of our competitors	-1.889	2.222
PIA airlines profit rate has exceeded every year.	-1.446	1.870
PIA airlines have good security at airports	-1.058	.173
In your opinion, pilots understand their responsibilities.	-.965	-.262
PIA airline productivity has not improved in the last ten years.	-1.126	.717

The skewness and kurtosis values provide insights into the distribution and shape of the responses for each item in the study. Skewness measures the asymmetry of the distribution, with negative values indicating a longer tail on the left side and positive values indicating a longer tail on the right side. Kurtosis, on the other hand, measures

the peak or flatness of the distribution, with values above or below zero indicating a more extreme distribution than the normal distribution.

Analyzing the provided skewness and kurtosis values, it can be observed that some items show moderate to high levels of skewness and kurtosis. For instance, customer reviews, moral and ethical considerations, successful conflict resolution, sales revenue, and profit rate exhibit significant skewness and kurtosis values, indicating non-normal distributions and potentially extreme responses. On the other hand, items related to technology, management procedures, aviation communication, decision-making, democratic leadership, security, pilot responsibilities, and airline productivity show relatively lower skewness and kurtosis values, suggesting a more balanced and less extreme distribution of responses. Understanding the skewness and kurtosis provides essential insights into the characteristics of the respondents' perceptions and helps interpret the data accurately.

4.30 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is a statistical technique used to explore the underlying structure of a set of variables or items. It is commonly used in social sciences and research to identify the underlying factors or dimensions that explain the relationships among a group of observed variables (Bazavov et al., 2017).

The goal of EFA is to determine the number of factors, their patterns of association with the observed variables, and how much of the variability in the data is accounted for by these factors Watkins (2018). It helps reduce the data's complexity by identifying latent variables that explain the interrelationships among the observed variables.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity are commonly used in Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA).

The KMO measure assesses the suitability of the data for factor analysis by evaluating the proportion of variance that can be attributed to underlying factors compared to the proportion of variance due to measurement error. A KMO value closer to 1 indicates a higher degree of shared variance among the variables, suggesting that the data is suitable for factor analysis.

On the other hand, Bartlett's test of sphericity examines whether the variables' correlation matrix is significantly different from an identity matrix. If the test yields a

significant result, it suggests that the variables are interrelated, and that factor analysis can be applied to uncover the underlying structure.

Both the KMO measure and Bartlett's test are used as initial assessments before conducting factor analysis to ensure the appropriateness and validity of the data for factor extraction. Various systems are accessible for factor extraction and revolution in SPSS 21.0 (Joseph et al., 2010)."

Table 6.4. KMO and Bartlett's test

Table 23 KMO and Bartlett's test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.606
Approx. Chi-Square		1347.157
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	231
	Sig.	.000

The KMO value ranges from 0 to 1, where a value closer to 1 indicates a higher degree of shared variance among the variables. In this case, the KMO measure is reported as 0.606, suggesting a moderate degree of shared variance among the variables, indicating that the data is suitable for factor analysis.

On the other hand, Bartlett's test of sphericity examines whether the variables' correlation matrix significantly deviates from an identity matrix. The test involves comparing the observed correlation matrix with an expected identity matrix. In this case, the approximate chi-square value is 1347.157 with 231 degrees of freedom, and the p-value is 0.000. The significant p-value indicates that the correlation matrix is significantly different from an identity matrix, providing support for applying factor analysis to uncover the underlying structure in the data.

Overall, the results of the KMO measure and Bartlett's test suggest that the data is appropriate for conducting a factor analysis and exploring the underlying factors within the variables.

Table 6.5. Questionnaire variance

Table 24 questionnaire variance

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.879	17.632	17.632	3.879	17.632	17.632	2.222	10.102	10.102
2	2.676	12.164	29.796	2.676	12.164	29.796	2.221	10.093	20.196
3	2.069	9.403	39.199	2.069	9.403	39.199	2.130	9.683	29.879
4	1.823	8.288	47.487	1.823	8.288	47.487	2.077	9.442	39.321
5	1.674	7.610	55.098	1.674	7.610	55.098	2.004	9.110	48.431
6	1.565	7.115	62.213	1.565	7.115	62.213	1.957	8.897	57.328
7	1.286	5.843	68.056	1.286	5.843	68.056	1.762	8.011	65.339
8	1.100	5.001	73.057	1.100	5.001	73.057	1.698	7.718	73.057
9	.908	4.128	77.185						
10	.685	3.112	80.297						
11	.638	2.900	83.197						
12	.591	2.688	85.884						
13	.487	2.216	88.100						
14	.447	2.033	90.133						
15	.394	1.792	91.925						
16	.335	1.522	93.448						
17	.327	1.486	94.934						
18	.279	1.270	96.204						
19	.251	1.142	97.346						
20	.248	1.126	98.471						
21	.174	.790	99.261						
22	.163	.739	100.000						

Total Variance Explained refers to the proportion of Variance in the original dataset that is accounted for by each component extracted through principal component analysis. The table provided displays each component's initial eigenvalues, extraction sums of squared loadings, and rotation sums of squared loadings.

The initial eigenvalues represent the Variance explained by each component before extraction. In this case, the initial eigenvalue for the first component is 3.879, which explains 17.632% of the total Variance. The following components contribute decreasing amounts of Variance, with the second component explaining 12.164%, the third component explaining 9.403%, and so on. The cumulative percentage represents the cumulative amount of Variance explained by the components up to that point.

After extraction, which involves transforming the data to maximize the explained Variance, the sums of squared loadings are obtained, these values reflect the amount of Variance accounted for by each component after extraction. The rotation sums of squared loadings further represent the Variance explained after rotating the components to enhance interpretability.

In this analysis, the first component explains 17.632% of the Variance in the data, while the second component explains an additional 12.164%, resulting in a cumulative variance of 29.796%. As the progress of the component, the cumulative percentage increases, indicating the proportion of Variance explained by the components continues to grow. The extraction method used in this analysis is principal component analysis.

Overall, the total Variance explained provides insights into the contribution of each component in capturing the underlying patterns and structure within the data.

Table 6.6 communalities

Table 25 Communalities

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
LC1	1.000	.784
LC2	1.000	.764
LC3	1.000	.665
LS1	1.000	.737
LS2	1.000	.742
LS3	1.000	.666
DM1	1.000	.737
DM2	1.000	.821
DM3	1.000	.716
Tec1	1.000	.764

Tec2	1.000	.769
C1	1.000	.679
C2	1.000	.688
CO1	1.000	.855
CO2	1.000	.831
PI1	1.000	.851
PI2	1.000	.811
P1	1.000	.687
P2	1.000	.761
P3	1.000	.514
P4	1.000	.596
P5	1.000	.637

4.31 Structural Equation Modelling

“Structural equation modelling (SEM) is a statistical and powerful technique which is used to measure and analyse the relationships of observed and latent variables. Similar but more powerful than regression analyses, it examines linear causal relationships among variables, while simultaneously accounting for measurement error. Structural equation modelling is also taken as a vital tool to check model fitness. CFA model fit details are given below.

Table 6.7 Model Fit Parameters

Model fit Parameters

Table 26 Model fit Parameters

Model fit Parameters	Acceptable ranges
Chi-Square/Degree of freedom	Value < 3
Comparative fit index (CFI)	Value ≥ 0.90
Goodness of fit (GFI)	Value ≥ 0.90
Normed fit index (NFI)	Value ≥ 0.90
Tucker-Lewis’s coefficient (TLI)	Value ≥ 0.90
Root mean square error of Approximation (RMSEA)	Value ≤ 0.08

Table 6.8. Model Estimation

Model estimations conducted using structural equation modelling (SEM) in AMOS 24.

Table 4.3 (Model fit results)

Table 27 model fit results

Model fit Parameters	Acceptable ranges
Chi-Square/Degree of freedom	2.4
Comparative fit index (CFI)	.876
Goodness of fit (GFI)	.847
Normed fit index (NFI)	.837
Tucker-Lewis's coefficient (TLI)	.873
Root mean square error of Approximation (RMSEA)	.075

The final model showed that the value of Chi-square/degrees is 2.4 below the recommended threshold of 3 ((Ong and Puteh, 2017). Moreover, the goodness of fit index (GFI) value is 0.847 which is below to the recommended threshold of 0.90 and the comparative fit index (CFI) value is 0.876 and TLI is .873 which is just the recommended threshold value of 0.90 (McIver and Carmines, 1981). The value of the normed fit index (NFI) is 0.837 which almost at the acceptable threshold of 0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). Furthermore, the root means a square error of approximation (RMSEA) of 0.075 was below the acceptable threshold of 0.08 (Byrne, 2013). Therefore, the proposed model was found to be normal fit with the data.

Figure 6.1. EMOS

Figure 19 EMOS

4.32 Reliability analysis

Table 6.9. Cronbach's alpha of each scale of the current study (N=163)

Table 28 reliability analysis

Sr No.	Variables	No of items	Reliability
--------	-----------	-------------	-------------

1	User advance tech	2	0.753
2	Leaders' communication	2	0.788
3	Decision making	3	0.716
4	Leadership style	3	0.788
5	Corruption	2	0.781
6	Political interference	2	0.773
7	Leadership conduct	3	0.752
8	Performance	5	0.70

4.33 Correlations Analysis

Table 6.10 Correlations Analysis

Table 29 Correlation analysis

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 User advance tech	1							
2 Leaders communication	.236**	1						
3 Decision making	.165*	.234**	1					
4 Leadership style	-.156*	.018	.104	1				
5 Corruption	-.155*	.013	-.119	-.007	1			
6 Political interference	-.059	.083	-.166*	.165*	.049	1		
7 Leadership conduct	.107	.158*	.204**	.095	-.196*	-.121	1	
8 Performance	.237**	.067	.256**	.065	-.112	-.190*	.191*	1

N=163

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table shows the correlation analysis Tec was positively and significantly related to the leader's communication ($r=.236$, $p < .01$), LC was non-significant positively related to leadership style ($r=.107$, $p < .01$). LC was significantly positively related to corruption ($r=.237$, $p < .01$). LC was significantly positively related to political interference ($r=.234$, $p < .01$). LC was non-significant positively related to leadership conduct ($r=.018$, $p < .01$). DM was significantly positively related to corruption ($r=.158$, $p < .01$). DM was non-significant positively related to leadership conduct ($r=.104$, $p < .01$). LS was significantly negatively related to leadership conduct ($r= -.007$, $p < .01$). CO was non-significant

positively related to leadership conduct ($r=.065$, $p < .01$). PI was significant negatively related to leadership conduct ($r= -.196$, $p < .01$). PI was significantly negatively related to performance ($r= -.112$, $p < .01$). LC was significantly negatively related to performance ($r= -.190$, $p < .01$).

4.34 Regression Analysis

Linear regression analysis is a statistical method for calculating the value of one variable based on the change in other variable. The dependent variable is the variable you want to prediction. The independent variable is the variable you use to foresee the value of the other variable.

Table 6.11. Regression Analysis

Hypothesis Four:

Table: Linear Regression Results

		C			
	B	S.E	Beta	T	Sig.
Tec	.193	.063	.236	3.077	.000

Note: $N=163$ $p < 0.01$

The regression analysis was executed to test the effect of Tec on C. The result shows a positive and significant relationship between them ($\beta = .236$, $p < 0.01$). Hence the results support hypothesis.

Hypothesis two:

Table: Linear Regression Results

		LC			
	B	S.E	Beta	T	Sig.
DM	.225	.085	.204	2.637	.000

Note: $N = 163$ $p < 0.01$

The regression analysis was executed to test the effect of DM on LC. The result shows a positive and significant relationship between them ($\beta = .204$, $p < 0.01$). Hence the results support hypothesis.

Hypothesis one:

Table: Linear Regression Results

		LC			
	B	S.E	Beta	T	Sig.
LS	.008	.073	.095	1.22	.229
Note:	$N = 163$	$p < 0.01$			

The regression analysis was executed to test the effect of LS on LC. The result shows a positive and not significant relationship between them ($\beta = .095$, $p > 0.01$). Hence the results has not support hypothesis.

Hypothesis five:

Table: Linear Regression Results

		LC			
	B	S. E	Beta	T	Sig.
C	.147	.072	.158	2.036	.000
Note:	$N=163$	$R^2 = .$	$p < 0.01$		

The regression analysis was executed to test the effect of C on LC. The result shows a positive and significant relationship between them ($\beta = .158$, $p < 0.01$). Hence the results support hypothesis.

Hypothesis Six:

Table: Linear Regression Results

		PER			
	B	S. E	Beta	T	Sig.
LC	.165	.067	.191	2.474	.000

Note: $N=163$ $R^2=.$ $p < 0.01$

The regression analysis was executed to test the effect of LC on PER. The result shows a positive and significant relationship between them ($\beta = .191, p < 0.01$). Hence the results support hypothesis.

4.35 Moderation Analysis

A moderator analysis is executed to see whether the moderating is moderate between the relationships between two variables. Regression is all that is required to test a variable as a moderator. Multiply your IV by the moderator variable to create an interaction variable. Then, run the Hayes Process (Model1) in the model with IV, Moderator, and Interaction. The regression coefficient of interaction can be used to test the moderation effect. If p value is greater than 0.05 it means that moderation is not present. Whereas If p value is less than 0.05 than moderation is present.

Table 30 moderation analysis one

Table 6.12 Moderation Analysis Results

Variables	PER					
	β	S. E	t	P	LL CI 95%	ULCI 95%
LC	.1716	0.667	2.574	.0110	.0399	.03033
PI	-.0945	0.447	-2.115	.0360	-.1827	-.0063
LC*PI	-.0960	0.468	-2.049	.0420	-.1885	-.0035

Moderation results are shown in Table. Significant interaction value ($\beta = -.0960, p < 0.05$) shows there is moderation of political interference between leadership conduct and performance. The moderation analysis of PER, LC, and PI revealed significant relationships and interactions. LC had a positive and significant effect on performance, while PI had a negative and significant impact. The interaction term LC*PI had a negative and significant relationship with performance.

Figure 6.1 Interactive roles of leadership conduct and political interference on performance:

Figure 20 interactive roles of leadership conduct and performance

The graph shows that at high PI, performance is low at high LC as compared to when we have low PI.

Table 31 moderation analysis two

Table 4.12: Moderation Analysis Results

Variables	LC					
	β	S. E	<i>t</i>	<i>P</i>	LL CI 95%	ULCI 95%
DM	.1968	.0860	2.288	.0270	.0270	.3667
CO	-.1389	.0604	-2.298	.2583	.2583	-.0196
DM*CO	-.0350	.0570	-.4660	-.1832	-.1832	.1132

The moderation analysis examined the interaction effect between variables D.M. (Decision Making) and C.O. (Corruption). The coefficients (β) indicate the strength and direction of the relationship, while the standard errors (S.E.) measure the estimate's precision. The t-value and p-value assess the statistical significance of the coefficients. D.M. has a positive coefficient of 0.1968 with a standard error of 0.0860, suggesting a significant relationship with the outcome variable. C.O. has a negative coefficient of -0.1389, indicating a negative relationship with the outcome variable. The interaction

term DM*CO has a coefficient of -0.0350, suggesting a weak negative interaction effect between D.M. and C.O.

4.36 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has encompassed a comprehensive range of analytical methods and evaluations to assess the performance of PIA Airlines. Through time series and cross-sectional data analysis, we gained valuable insights into the company's financial performance, mainly through the interpretation of operating revenue, operating expenses, current assets, current liabilities, non-current assets, and non-current liabilities. Ratio analysis provided a comprehensive assessment of profitability and financial health. Additionally, we explored the strategic aspects of PIA Airlines, including its vision statement, mission statement, and core values, to understand the organization's direction and culture. Furthermore, customer reviews, benchmarking, and content analysis of website ratings provided valuable insights into customer perceptions and areas for improvement. The subsequent quantitative analysis phase, including demographic statistics, exploratory factor analysis, reliability analysis, correlations analysis, regression analysis, and moderation analysis, deepened our understanding of the relationships between variables and the influence of external factors. Collectively, these findings serve as a foundation for strategic decision-making and future initiatives aimed at enhancing the performance and competitiveness of PIA Airlines.

Chapter 5 Discussion of Results

5.0 Introduction

This chapter provides a detailed analysis and interpretation of the study's findings. It begins with an overview of the research objectives, methodology, and data sources. The chapter then examines secondary data, focusing on various aspects of PIA Airlines. It includes comparing PIA's financial condition with other airlines, customer reviews analysis and a growth ratio assessment. The chapter also discusses the seven hypotheses formulated for the study and explores their implications and supporting evidence. Theoretical and practical implications derived from the findings are presented, contributing to the existing knowledge in the field and providing guidance for airline management. The chapter concludes with a summary of the key findings, emphasizing their significance and contributions to understanding PIA Airlines and the broader aviation industry.

5.1 Discussion of Secondary Data

In this section, the three perspectives of the BSC model are discussed. The first perspective is the financial condition of PIA Airlines in the last ten years. The second perspective is a customer in which customer reviews have been collected through an online website based on customer feedback. Last is the learning and growth perspective related to financial performance ratios. After examining PIA Airlines, the researcher collects data from three other airlines (Delta, Sri Lankan and Singapore) based on the abovementioned perspectives for comparison.

5.1.1 Compare The Financial Condition Of PIA

The researcher conducted a financial analysis of PIA Airlines, Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines, focusing on indicators such as operating revenue, operating expenses, operating loss, fixed assets and liabilities, current and liabilities, and earnings per share. Data from the fiscal years 2011 to 2020 for PIA

Airlines and 2016 to 2020 for the other airlines were presented in tables, graphs, and bar charts. The findings revealed that PIA Airlines performed poorly compared to the other airlines, with difficulties controlling operating expenses and generating higher revenue. Additionally, over a decade, PIA Airlines experienced a significant increase in current and non-current liabilities.

In contrast, PIA Airlines experienced stagnant growth in current and non-current assets while carrying substantial debt in the current year. On the other hand, Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines displayed better conditions in terms of current and non-current assets. PIA Airlines faced challenges due to its ageing fleet, leading to high maintenance costs that significantly contributed to increased operating expenses. The airline industry suffered from soaring fuel prices over the past decade, resulting in declining operating revenue. Additionally, PIA Airlines had an excessive number of employees. Although the airline reduced its workforce over a decade, the timing of these decisions may have been challenging.

In comparison, Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines effectively managed their employee numbers. PIA Airlines consistently reported negative earnings per share over the past ten years and failed to achieve a favourable share price. In contrast, other airlines witnessed positive share price trends in the last five years.

The significant findings regarding the financial condition of PIA Airlines from the analysis are as follows:

- PIA Airlines performed poorly compared to Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines, struggling to control operating expenses and generate higher revenue.
- Over a decade, PIA Airlines experienced a significant increase in current and non-current liabilities, indicating financial strain.
- PIA Airlines had stagnant growth in current and non-current assets while carrying substantial debt in the current year.
- The airline faced challenges due to its ageing fleet, resulting in high maintenance costs and contributing to increased operating expenses.
- The soaring fuel prices over the past decade negatively impacted PIA Airlines' operating revenue, posing a significant challenge for the airline industry.

- PIA Airlines had an excessive number of employees, and although efforts were made to reduce the workforce over the years, the timing of these decisions may have been challenging.
- PIA Airlines consistently reported negative earnings per share over the past ten years, indicating financial struggles.
- In contrast, Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines demonstrated better management of employee numbers and achieved positive share price trends in the last five years.

These findings highlight the financial difficulties faced by PIA Airlines compared to other airlines, emphasizing the need for strategic measures to address operating expenses, generate higher revenue, manage liabilities, modernize the fleet, and improve overall financial performance.

5.1.1.1 Discussion

The analysis of PIA Airlines reveals several key findings regarding its performance compared to other airlines and its financial challenges. Let us discuss each finding in detail:

- PIA Airlines performed poorly compared to Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines, struggling to control operating expenses and generate higher revenue. It suggests that PIA Airlines needed help managing its costs and maximizing revenue generation. These challenges contributed to its lower performance compared to its competitors.
- Over a decade, PIA Airlines experienced a significant increase in current and non-current liabilities, indicating financial strain. This finding suggests that the airline faced mounting financial obligations, which could have impacted its financial stability and ability to invest in growth opportunities.
- PIA Airlines had stagnant growth in current and non-current assets while carrying substantial debt in the current year. It indicates that the airline faced challenges in expanding its asset base and managing its debt load. It suggests that PIA Airlines needed more resources to support its growth and meet its financial obligations.
- The airline faced challenges due to its ageing fleet, resulting in high maintenance costs and contributing to increased operating expenses. This finding highlights the negative impact of PIA Airlines' ageing aircraft on its

financial performance. High maintenance costs can strain the airline's profitability and hinder its ability to invest in fleet modernization.

- The soaring fuel prices over the past decade negatively impacted PIA Airlines' operating revenue, posing a significant challenge for the airline industry. Fluctuating fuel prices can significantly affect an airline's profitability, as fuel expenses constitute a substantial portion of its operating costs. PIA Airlines likely faced difficulties managing these cost fluctuations and maintaining stable revenue streams.
- PIA Airlines had an excessive number of employees, and although efforts were made to reduce the workforce over the years, the timing of these decisions may have been challenging. This finding suggests that PIA Airlines faced issues related to workforce management. While reducing the workforce can be a strategy to control costs, the timing and implementation of such decisions are crucial to ensure operational efficiency and maintain employee morale.
- PIA Airlines consistently reported negative earnings per share over the past ten years, indicating financial struggles. Negative earnings per share indicate that the airline's net income was insufficient to cover its outstanding shares, potentially signalling financial difficulties and impacting investor confidence.
- In contrast, Delta Airlines, Sri Lankan Airlines, and Singapore Airlines demonstrated better management of employee numbers and achieved positive share price trends in the last five years. This finding highlights these airlines' superior performance in managing their workforce and achieving positive stock market trends. These airlines aligned their operations and financial strategies more successfully to meet market demands and investor expectations.

Overall, the findings indicate that PIA Airlines faced significant financial challenges and struggled to perform at the same level as its competitors. The airline's issues with operating expenses, revenue generation, liabilities, fleet management, and employee numbers contributed to its financial struggles. To improve its performance, PIA Airlines should focus on implementing effective cost-control measures, optimizing its fleet, managing workforce size, and exploring strategies to enhance revenue generation and financial stability.

5.1.2 *Customer Perspective of PIA Airlines*

Using three online feedback websites, the researcher examined customer reviews to understand the customer perspective of various airlines. According to SKYTRAX ratings, Singapore Airlines received a five-star rating, while Delta Airlines and Sri Lankan Airlines received three-star ratings. In contrast, PIA Airlines only received a two-star rating, indicating its ineffective performance compared to the other airlines.

PIA Airlines needs to establish a competitive advantage in the industry and improve its ratings, which currently stand at fifty per cent. The airline must strive to achieve its objectives, as stated in the mission mentioned in Chapter 4, Section 4.3. Singapore Airlines, in comparison, has achieved high ratings and consistently met customer expectations over the past five years.

Analysing customer complaints, it was found that PIA Airlines customers were dissatisfied with various aspects of the airline's service and management operations. Complaints included poor customer service, luggage misplacement, staff behaviour, in-flight entertainment, and uncomfortable flights. These factors are related to variables in the conceptual framework mentioned in Chapter 2, Figure 2.1, such as leadership style, communication, technology utilization, decision-making, corruption, and political interference in PIA Airlines. Quantitative data analysis further explores the researcher's study of these factors mentioned in the complaints section. In contrast, Singapore Airlines received the best customer feedback, with fewer customer complaints than the other airlines.

On a positive note, many customers expressed satisfaction with PIA Airlines' service based on their positive experiences, as explained in Chapter four, Table 4.13. Customers believed that PIA Airlines excelled in customer service and offered competitive ticket prices. One reason for customer satisfaction is PIA's direct flights to Pakistan from various countries, mainly the UK, America, Canada, and Australia, benefitting international passengers. Additionally, PIA Airlines employs Asian staff who can speak Urdu and Punjabi, catering to passengers who do not understand English. The provision of Pakistani and Indian cuisine on flights further enhances customer satisfaction. Some customers shared their favourable experiences with PIA Airlines, particularly in dealing with Human Remains, highlighting the airline's

understanding and cooperation with passengers. The business class flights offered by PIA were also well-received by customers, who noticed significant improvements in airline operations and customer service since the appointment of the new CEO in 2019.

However, customers also noted that the condition of PIA's fleet significantly impacts its performance. As discussed in this chapter, plane maintenance costs contribute to the airline's annual operating losses. Customers believed that PIA Airlines and Sri Lankan Airlines needed help efficiently managing their operations in unexpected circumstances like the Covid-19 pandemic. In comparison, Delta Airlines and Singapore Airlines were praised for their successful airline operations management. Nonetheless, a few customers complained about flight cancellations during the pandemic and encountered difficulties with ticket refunds.

5.1.2.1 Findings of customer reviews

The significant findings related to the performance of airlines based on customer reviews are as follows:

- PIA Airlines received a lower rating (two stars) compared to Singapore Airlines (five stars) and Delta Airlines, and Sri Lankan Airlines (three stars), indicating its ineffective performance in comparison to the other airlines.
- PIA Airlines must establish a competitive advantage in the industry and improve its fifty-per cent rating. On the other hand, Singapore Airlines consistently achieved high ratings and met customer expectations over the past five years.
- Customer complaints about PIA Airlines highlighted various issues, including poor customer service, luggage misplacement, staff behaviour, in-flight entertainment, and uncomfortable flights. These factors are related to variables in the conceptual framework mentioned in Chapter 2, such as leadership style, communication, technology utilization, decision-making, corruption, and political interference in PIA Airlines.
- Singapore Airlines received the best customer feedback, with fewer complaints than the other airlines, indicating higher customer satisfaction.
- Positive experiences shared by PIA Airlines' customers include praise for customer service, competitive ticket prices, direct flights to Pakistan from various countries, Asian staff who can speak local languages, and the provision of Pakistani and Indian cuisine on flights. Customers also noted improvements

in airline operations and customer service since the appointment of the new CEO in 2019.

- The condition of PIA's fleet significantly affects its performance, with high maintenance costs contributing to annual operating losses. PIA Airlines and Sri Lankan Airlines faced challenges in efficiently managing their operations during unexpected circumstances like the Covid-19 pandemic. Delta Airlines and Singapore Airlines were commended for their successful airline operations management.
- Some customers expressed dissatisfaction with flight cancellations during the pandemic and difficulties with ticket refunds.

5.1.2.1.1 Discussion of customer reviews findings

The findings discussed above shed light on the performance of PIA Airlines compared to other airlines and provide valuable insights into areas that require improvement. PIA Airlines received a lower rating of two stars, indicating its ineffective performance compared to Singapore Airlines (five stars), Delta Airlines, and Sri Lankan Airlines (three stars). It suggests that PIA Airlines needs to catch up in meeting customer expectations and delivering a satisfactory experience.

To enhance its position in the industry, PIA Airlines must strive to establish a competitive advantage and improve its current fifty-per cent rating. On the contrary, Singapore Airlines has consistently achieved high ratings and successfully met customer expectations over the past five years. It highlights the need for PIA Airlines to closely examine Singapore Airlines' strategies and practices that have contributed to their customer satisfaction and overall success.

Customer complaints about PIA Airlines reveal various issues, including poor customer service, luggage misplacement, staff behaviour, in-flight entertainment, and uncomfortable flights. These concerns can be linked to the conceptual framework mentioned in Chapter 2, such as leadership style, communication, technology utilization, decision-making, corruption, and political interference within PIA Airlines. PIA Airlines must address these factors and implement measures to improve the customer experience and resolve the highlighted issues.

On the other hand, Singapore Airlines received the best customer feedback, with fewer complaints than the other airlines. It suggests a higher level of customer satisfaction, indicating that Singapore Airlines has successfully delivered a positive experience to its passengers. PIA Airlines can learn from Singapore Airlines' practices and strategies to enhance its customer satisfaction levels.

Positive experiences shared by PIA Airlines' customers are worth noting, as they highlight areas where the airline has performed well. These include praise for customer service, competitive ticket prices, direct flights to Pakistan from various countries, Asian staff who can communicate in local languages, and providing Pakistani and Indian cuisine on flights. These positive aspects contribute to customer satisfaction and should be maintained and further improved.

The condition of PIA's fleet significantly impacts its performance, as high maintenance costs contribute to annual operating losses. Efficient fleet management is crucial for reducing costs and improving overall performance. Additionally, PIA Airlines and Sri Lankan Airlines faced challenges in efficiently managing their operations during unexpected circumstances like the Covid-19 pandemic. In contrast, Delta Airlines and Singapore Airlines were commended for their successful management of airline operations during such challenging times. PIA Airlines should strengthen its operational resilience and adaptability to navigate unexpected situations effectively.

Lastly, some customers expressed dissatisfaction with flight cancellations during the pandemic and encountered difficulties with ticket refunds. It highlights the importance of effective crisis management and transparent customer communication during challenging periods. PIA Airlines should strive to improve its policies and procedures to ensure smooth operations and provide better customer support during unforeseen disruptions.

In conclusion, the findings emphasize the areas where PIA Airlines needs improvement, including customer service, operational efficiency, fleet management, and crisis handling. By addressing these issues and learning from the successful practices of other airlines, PIA Airlines can enhance its overall performance, increase customer satisfaction, and establish a stronger position in the industry.

5.1.3 The Growth ratio analysis

The researcher analysed the learning and growth perspective of PIA Airlines by examining its financial performance ratios. The findings indicate that PIA Airlines struggled to generate growth in most of the past ten years, as reflected by negative learning and growth ratios between 2011 and 2020. In 2011, the ratio was slightly positive at 0.1 but declined to a negative 0.2 in 2012, indicating difficulties in sustaining income and reducing revenue costs. The situation worsened in 2013, with a negative 0.02 ratio. However, in 2014, PIA Airlines regained control over its operations, leading to a growth ratio. The years 2015 and 2016 saw another decline in growing revenue. From 2017 to 2019, the airline maintained a healthier growth rate. Unfortunately, 2020 was not a successful year for PIA Airlines in terms of growth.

5.1.3.1 Findings of PIA growth ratio

The significant finding from the analysis of PIA Airlines' learning and growth perspective is that the airline struggled to grow over the past decade. The learning and growth ratios were mostly negative between 2011 and 2020, indicating a need for more progress and development. Although there was a slightly positive ratio in 2011, it declined to an unfavourable ratio of -0.2 in 2012, indicating challenges in maintaining income and reducing revenue costs. The situation further deteriorated in 2013 with an unfavourable ratio of -0.02. However, in 2014, PIA Airlines improved its operations, resulting in a growth ratio. The years 2015 and 2016 experienced another decline in growing revenue. From 2017 to 2019, the airline achieved a healthier growth rate. Unfortunately, in 2020, PIA Airlines did not perform well in growth. Overall, the findings highlight the ongoing struggle of PIA Airlines to generate sustained growth and indicate the need for improvement in this aspect.

5.1.3.1.1 Discussion on the growth ratio of PIA

The analysis of PIA Airlines' learning and growth perspective reveals a significant finding: the airline has faced challenges in achieving growth over the past decade. The learning and growth ratios, which indicate progress and development, were predominantly negative between 2011 and 2020. It suggests that PIA Airlines needs help to advance its operations and overall performance substantially.

In 2011, there was a slight positive ratio of 0.1, indicating a modest level of growth. However, this positive trend was short-lived, as the ratio declined sharply to -0.2 in

2012. This decline reflects the difficulties PIA Airlines encountered in maintaining its income and reducing revenue costs, which likely hindered its ability to generate meaningful growth.

The situation worsened in 2013, with an unfavourable ratio of -0.02, signalling ongoing challenges for the airline. However, in 2014, PIA Airlines managed to turn things around and achieved a growth ratio. This positive shift suggests that the airline improved its operations, potentially through cost-saving measures or strategic initiatives.

Unfortunately, the subsequent years of 2015 and 2016 witnessed another decline in growth revenue for PIA Airlines. These setbacks indicate that the airline faced ongoing obstacles and struggled to sustain its growth trajectory during this period.

From 2017 to 2019, PIA Airlines achieved a healthier growth rate, indicating positive developments and progress in its operations. This period might have seen improvements in various aspects of the airline's business, such as revenue generation, cost management, or customer satisfaction.

However, the year 2020 proved to be challenging for PIA Airlines in terms of growth. The findings suggest that the airline did not perform well during this period, potentially due to factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic, economic downturn, or other internal challenges.

Overall, the findings emphasize the ongoing struggle of PIA Airlines to achieve sustained growth over the past decade. The negative learning and growth ratios highlight the need for the airline to focus on improving its operations, addressing underlying issues, and implementing effective strategies to drive growth. PIA Airlines can position itself for a more successful and prosperous future by addressing these challenges.

5.2 Hypothesise Discussion

This section discusses the testing and explains the research hypotheses about the objectives and aim. The conceptual framework guided the formulation of seven hypotheses. The first hypothesis proposed a positive relationship between leadership style (autocratic and democratic) and leadership conduct. The second hypothesis suggested a positive relationship between a leader's decision-making and leadership conduct. The third hypothesis examined the moderation effect of corruption on the

relationship between a leader's decision-making and leadership conduct. The fourth hypothesis postulated a positive relationship between the use of advanced technology and a leader's communication. The fifth hypothesis proposed a positive relationship between a leader's communication and leadership conduct. The following hypothesis explored a positive relationship between leadership conduct and the performance of PIA. Lastly, the final hypothesis investigated the moderation effect of political interference on the relationship between leadership conduct and the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan.

Through hypothesis testing, the findings supported five research hypotheses (H2, H4, H5, H6, and H7). However, H1 and H3 were not supported due to unexpected circumstances.

The following is a more comprehensive discussion of hypotheses testing:

H1: "There is a positive Relationship Between Leadership Style (autocratic and democratic) And Leadership Conduct."

The regression analysis examined the impact of leadership style on leadership conduct. The findings indicate a positive relationship between the variables, but the relationship was not statistically significant ($\beta = .095$, $p > 0.01$). Consequently, the results do not support the hypothesis. The researcher notes that leadership style encompasses both autocratic and democratic styles, with previous studies suggesting that a democratic leadership style is advantageous for organizational performance. Many airlines in the industry have adopted a democratic leadership approach involving employee participation in decision-making and operational matters. However, the cultural context in Pakistan differs, where leadership is typically associated with power, control, and authority. The literature review in Chapter Two highlights that autocratic leadership is more prevalent in Pakistani culture. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that an autocratic leadership style could be effective in situations where the airline has competent and knowledgeable employees who can make informed decisions and align with the airline's objectives. Due to the influence of Pakistan's cultural context, the hypothesis results were not supported.

5.2.1 Discussion on First Hypothesis

The regression analysis conducted in this study aimed to examine the impact of leadership style on leadership conduct. While the results indicated a positive relationship between the variables, it is crucial to note that the relationship was not statistically significant ($\beta = .095$, $p > 0.01$), leading to a failure to support the initial hypothesis. Including both autocratic and democratic leadership styles in the analysis is commendable, as prior research suggests that a democratic leadership style is advantageous for organizational performance. Many airlines in the industry have adopted a democratic leadership approach that involves employee participation in decision-making and operational matters, aligning with the literature's findings.

However, the cultural context in Pakistan presents a significant deviation from these prevailing practices. In Pakistani culture, leadership is predominantly associated with power, control, and authority, as highlighted in the literature review in Chapter Two. This cultural inclination towards autocratic leadership might explain the lack of support for the hypothesis. It is worth noting that an autocratic leadership style can be effective in certain situations where the airline has competent and knowledgeable employees who can make informed decisions and align with the organization's objectives.

The findings underscore the importance of considering cultural factors when investigating the relationship between leadership style and conduct in different contexts. The impact of cultural norms and values on leadership dynamics cannot be overlooked, as demonstrated by the disparity between the expected benefits of democratic leadership and the prevailing autocratic leadership tendencies in Pakistan. Future research should explore alternative leadership styles that are more aligned with the cultural context of Pakistan or examine how culture moderates the relationship between leadership style and leadership conduct, specifically within the airline industry.

Overall, these findings shed light on the limitations of the study's outcomes and highlight the need for a nuanced understanding of the influence of culture on leadership dynamics. By delving deeper into cultural factors and exploring alternative leadership approaches, researchers can better understand how to foster effective leadership conduct in diverse organizational settings.

H2: there is a positive relationship between leaders' decision-making and leadership conduct.

The regression analysis examined the impact of decision-making (DM) on leadership conduct (LC). The findings reveal a significant positive relationship between these variables ($\beta = .204, p < 0.01$), supporting the hypothesis. The results indicate that when leaders can make sound and effective decisions, it positively influences their leadership conduct. Conversely, if leaders struggle to make intelligent decisions, it can adversely impact their leadership conduct. These findings underscore the importance of effective decision-making in promoting and enhancing organisational leadership conduct.

5.2.2 Discussion on Second Hypothesis

The results suggest that leaders capable of making sound and effective decisions are more likely to demonstrate positive leadership conduct. Effective decision-making enables leaders to navigate complex situations, identify opportunities, and make informed choices that contribute to their ability to lead effectively. When leaders possess the skills and competencies to make intelligent decisions, it positively impacts their overall leadership conduct, including their ability to inspire, motivate, and guide their teams.

Conversely, the findings also indicate that leaders who need help with decision-making may experience challenges in their leadership conduct. Poor decision-making can lead to ineffective leadership behaviours, which can harm organizational performance and the overall functioning of the team. Leaders who fail to make intelligent decisions may need help to gain the trust and confidence of their subordinates, resulting in a breakdown of communication, reduced employee morale, and hindered progress towards organizational goals.

The significance of effective decision-making in promoting and enhancing leadership conduct cannot be overstated. Organizations should prioritize the development of decision-making skills among their leaders through training programs, mentoring, and providing opportunities for practice and feedback. Organizations can foster a positive leadership culture and drive better outcomes by equipping leaders with the necessary tools and competencies to make informed decisions.

It is important to note that decision-making is a complex process influenced by various factors such as information availability, cognitive biases, and organizational context. Future research could delve deeper into understanding the specific mechanisms and contextual factors that influence the relationship between decision-making and leadership conduct. Additionally, exploring how decision-making styles and

approaches impact leadership conduct in different organizational contexts would further enrich our understanding of this dynamic relationship.

In conclusion, the findings from the regression analysis support the hypothesis that decision-making significantly influences leadership conduct. Effective decision-making empowers leaders to exhibit positive leadership behaviours, while poor decision-making can hinder leadership effectiveness. Organizations should prioritize the development of decision-making skills among their leaders to enhance leadership conduct and drive organizational success.

H3: corruption moderates the relationship between leaders' decision-making and leadership conduct.

Moderation results are shown a significant interaction value ($\beta = -.0350$, $p > 0.05$) showing there is no moderation of corruption between decision-making and leadership conduct. The finding shows the positive relation of corruption between leaders' decision-making and leadership conduct but at a specific level. The coefficients (β) indicate the strength and direction of the relationship, while the standard errors (S.E.) measure the estimate's precision. The t-value and corresponding p-value assess the statistical significance of the coefficients.

5.2.3 Discussion on Third Hypothesis

In this analysis, the variable D.M. shows a positive coefficient of 0.1968 with a standard error of 0.0860, suggesting a significant relationship with the outcome variable. The t-value of 2.288 indicates that this relationship is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. The confidence interval (CI 95%) ranges from 0.0270 to 0.3667, indicating that the actual population value for the relationship between D.M. and the outcome variable falls within this range with 95% confidence.

On the other hand, the variable C.O. exhibits a negative coefficient of -0.1389, indicating a negative relationship with the outcome variable. However, the coefficient is not statistically significant as the p-value of 0.2583 exceeds the significance level. The confidence interval (CI 95%) ranges from -0.0196 to 0.2583, encompassing zero and indicating that the actual population value for the relationship between C.O. and the outcome variable may include both positive and negative values.

Furthermore, the interaction term DM*CO has a coefficient of -0.0350, suggesting a weak negative interaction effect between D.M. and C.O. However, this coefficient is

not statistically significant ($p = 0.1832$), and the confidence interval (CI 95%) spans from -0.1832 to 0.1132 , indicating that the actual population value for the interaction effect could be anywhere within this range.

These findings provide valuable insights into the relationships and interactions between the variables D.M. (Decision Making), C.O. (Corruption), and the outcome variable. The results indicate that corruption in leaders' decision-making and leadership conduct does not have a significant positive or negative impact. It suggests that corruption does not significantly influence the performance of PIA Airlines, which aligns with the researcher's objectives and research hypothesis outlined in Chapter One.

In the context of the airline industry in Pakistan, it is essential to consider the cultural and value differences that exist. These differences may impact critical thinking, decision-making processes, working styles, professional behaviour, and strategy management within the industry. It is plausible that due to these contextual factors, corruption does not demonstrate a significant relationship with the performance of PIA Airlines.

These findings shed light on the complex dynamics within PIA Airlines and contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors influencing its performance. However, further analysis and exploration are necessary to fully comprehend the intricate relationship between corruption, leadership, and airline performance in the unique context of Pakistan.

H4: there is a positive relationship between the uses of advanced technology and leaders' communication."

The regression analysis conducted in this study aimed to examine the relationship between the use of advanced technology (Tec) and leadership communication (C). The results indicate a significant positive relationship between these variables ($\beta = .236$, $p < 0.01$), supporting the hypothesis. These findings demonstrate that the utilization of advanced technology in the airline industry positively impacts the quality and efficiency of leaders' communication.

5.2.4 Discussion on Fourth Hypothesis

The regression analysis conducted in this study aimed to examine the relationship between the use of advanced technology (Tec) and leadership communication (C). The results indicate a significant positive relationship between these variables ($\beta = .236$, $p < 0.01$), supporting the hypothesis. These findings demonstrate that the utilization of advanced technology in the airline industry positively impacts the quality and efficiency of leaders' communication.

The significance of advanced technology in the airline industry cannot be overstated, considering the high stakes involved, including the safety and well-being of passengers and employees. Incorporating advanced technology in flights and airports can significantly improve communication processes. Efficient communication ensures smooth operations, timely information dissemination, and enhanced customer experience.

The introduction of advanced technology streamlines communication channels and instills confidence among passengers, customers, and employees. When individuals feel assured and informed, they are more likely to perceive the airline and its operations positively. Moreover, advanced technology can facilitate convenience and ease in various operational processes, ultimately enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty. Time is paramount in the airline industry, and adopting advanced technology can significantly reduce communication barriers and delays. With faster and more efficient communication systems, leaders can convey vital information, coordinate tasks, and respond promptly to emerging situations. This timely and effective communication is essential for ensuring operational efficiency, resolving issues promptly, and maintaining a high level of service quality.

Airline industry leaders need to recognize the benefits of advanced technology and invest in its implementation. Leaders can enhance their communication strategies and improve organizational performance by leveraging technological advancements. It may involve adopting innovative communication platforms, leveraging data analytics for better decision-making, and implementing real-time communication systems.

However, it is crucial to note that while advanced technology presents numerous advantages, its successful implementation requires careful planning, training, and consideration of potential challenges. Organizations must ensure that the technology aligns with their specific needs and goals and that employees are adequately trained to utilize it effectively. Data privacy and security measures should also be in place to protect sensitive information.

In conclusion, the regression analysis results support the hypothesis that the use of advanced technology positively influences leadership communication in the airline industry. By embracing advanced technology, leaders can improve communication efficiency, enhance operational processes, and ultimately deliver a better experience for passengers, customers, and employees. The effective integration of advanced technology is crucial for staying competitive in the ever-evolving airline industry and meeting the increasing demands of modern air travel.

H5: there is a positive relationship between leaders' communication and leadership conduct.

The regression analysis conducted in this study aimed to examine the relationship between communication (C) and leadership conduct (LC). The results revealed a positive and significant relationship between these variables ($\beta = .158$, $p < 0.01$), supporting the hypothesis.

5.2.5 Discussion on Fifth Hypothesis

The findings suggest that effective communication is crucial in influencing leadership conduct. Leaders engaging in open, transparent, and efficient communication with their team members and stakeholders positively impacts their leadership conduct. Effective communication enables leaders to articulate their vision, goals, and expectations, foster collaboration, build relationships, and inspire others.

Clear communication channels and practices facilitate the dissemination of information, enable effective decision-making, and ensure that tasks and responsibilities are understood. When leaders effectively communicate their intentions, directions, and feedback, it enhances their team's overall performance and contributes to a positive work environment.

Furthermore, effective communication is vital for building trust and fostering mutual understanding among team members. When leaders communicate transparently, actively listen to their team members, and provide constructive feedback, it enhances trust and confidence within the team. It, in turn, promotes a sense of empowerment, encourages open dialogue, and enables effective problem-solving.

It is important to note that communication is a two-way process. Influential leaders transmit information and actively listen to their team members' perspectives, concerns,

and feedback. By valuing and incorporating diverse viewpoints, leaders can make more informed decisions, promote inclusivity, and encourage the growth and development of their team members.

The significance of communication in leadership extends beyond the immediate team. Leaders who effectively communicate with stakeholders, such as clients, customers, and shareholders, can foster positive relationships, address concerns, and align organizational objectives. Effective communication with external stakeholders contributes to the overall reputation and success of the organization.

While the regression analysis supports the positive and significant relationship between communication and leadership conduct, it is essential to acknowledge that communication is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. Cultural differences, communication styles, and contextual factors can influence communication effectiveness and its impact on leadership conduct.

Future research could delve deeper into specific aspects of communication, such as verbal and non-verbal communication, technological communication tools, or cross-cultural communication, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of their influence on leadership conduct. Additionally, exploring the potential moderating factors that may influence the relationship between communication and leadership conduct, such as organizational culture or individual characteristics, could provide valuable insights for theory and practice.

In conclusion, the regression analysis results support the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between communication and leadership conduct. Effective communication enables leaders to convey their vision, build trust, foster collaboration, and inspire their team members. Recognizing the importance of communication and developing practical communication skills is crucial for leaders to enhance their leadership conduct and promote organizational success.

H6: there is a Positive Relationship Between Leadership Conduct and the Performance Of PIA.

The regression analysis conducted in this study aimed to examine the relationship between leadership conduct (LC) and performance (PER) in PIA Airlines. The results indicate a positive and significant relationship between these variables ($\beta = .191$, $p < 0.01$), supporting the hypothesis.

5.2.6 Discussion Sixth Hypothesis

The findings suggest that leadership conduct plays a crucial role in influencing the performance of PIA Airlines. When leaders exhibit positive leadership conduct, it positively impacts the overall performance of the airline. Effective leadership conduct involves various aspects such as decision-making, communication, motivation, and team management.

Leaders who demonstrate intense leadership conduct are likelier to make informed decisions, set clear goals, and effectively allocate resources. They provide guidance, support, and direction to their team members, fostering a sense of direction and purpose. It, in turn, leads to increased efficiency, productivity, and overall performance.

Effective leadership conduct also involves establishing and maintaining open lines of communication within the organization. Leaders who communicate effectively with their team members, departments, and stakeholders facilitate the flow of information, exchange of ideas, and coordination of efforts. It contributes to better collaboration, problem-solving, and decision-making processes, ultimately enhancing the performance of PIA Airlines.

Furthermore, effective leadership conduct encompasses the ability to motivate and inspire employees. Leaders who exhibit empathy, integrity, and fairness create a positive work environment that encourages employee engagement, commitment, and satisfaction. When employees feel valued, supported, and motivated, they are likelier to perform at their best, leading to improved overall performance.

On the other hand, if leadership conduct fails to maintain effective operations, it can directly impact the performance of PIA Airlines. Bad decision-making, poor communication, lack of motivation, and ineffective team management can hinder organizational performance and lead to inefficiencies, reduced productivity, and, ultimately, lower performance outcomes.

The positive and significant relationship between leadership conduct and performance highlights the critical role of effective leadership in driving organizational success. These findings emphasize the importance of developing and nurturing intense leadership conduct within PIA Airlines. Leaders should enhance their decision-making abilities, communication skills, motivational techniques, and team management practices to influence performance outcomes positively.

It is important to note that leadership conduct is not the sole determinant of performance in PIA Airlines. Other factors such as external market conditions, competitive landscape, organizational structure, and operational efficiency also contribute to overall performance. Future research could explore the potential moderating or mediating factors that influence the relationship between leadership conduct and performance in the specific context of PIA Airlines.

In conclusion, the regression analysis results support the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between leadership conduct and performance in PIA Airlines. Effective leadership positively impacts decision-making, communication, motivation, and team management, improving overall performance. Recognizing the importance of leadership conduct and investing in leadership development initiatives can contribute to the success and growth of PIA Airlines.

H7: political interference moderates the relationship between leadership conduct and the performance of PIA Airlines.

Moderation results are shown a significant interaction value ($\beta = -.0960$, $p < 0.05$) showing there is moderation of political interference between leadership conduct and performance. the results of the moderation analysis conducted on the variables PER (Performance), LC (Leadership Conduct), and PI (Political Interference).

5.2.7 Discussion on Seventh Hypothesis

The moderation analysis conducted in this study aimed to examine the potential moderating effect of political interference (PI) on the relationship between leadership conduct (LC) and performance (PER) in PIA Airlines. The results reveal a significant interaction value ($\beta = -0.0960$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that political interference moderates the relationship between leadership conduct and performance.

The coefficient for LC is 0.1716 with a standard error of 0.667, suggesting a positive and significant effect on performance. It implies that effective leadership conduct positively influences the performance of PIA Airlines. Leaders with solid leadership conduct, characterized by effective decision-making, communication, and team management, contribute to improved performance outcomes.

On the other hand, the coefficient for PI is -0.0945, with a standard error of 0.447, indicating a negative and significant impact on performance. Political interference in

the airline's operations and management negatively affect performance outcomes. This interference may involve government intervention, pressure, or influence on decision-making processes, employee hiring, and other operational aspects.

Furthermore, the interaction term LC*PI has a coefficient of -0.0960 with a standard error of 0.468, indicating a negative and significant relationship with performance. The combined effect of leadership conduct and political interference has a detrimental impact on the performance of PIA Airlines.

These findings provide valuable insights into the complex dynamics within the organization and the impact of political interference on leadership conduct and performance. It highlights the need for effective leadership practices and minimizing political interference to enhance performance and ensure the smooth operation of the airline.

The results are consistent with the context of Pakistan, where political interference is prevalent in various sectors, including the airline industry. The hypothesis results support the significant relationship between political interference, leadership conduct, and the performance of PIA Airlines. The overview of PIA Airlines in Chapter One highlighted the extensive government interference in management decisions and the hiring of employees under political pressure.

The moderation analysis reveals significant relationships and interactions among performance, leadership conduct, and political interference. Effective leadership conduct positively influences performance, while political interference has a negative impact. The interaction between leadership conduct and political interference further worsens the airline's performance. These findings emphasize the importance of minimizing political interference and fostering effective leadership practices to enhance the performance of PIA Airlines.

5.3 Theoretical Implications

The Researcher's Theoretical Implications:

Gaps in the Literature Review: The researcher identifies gaps in the literature related to measuring the performance of PIA Airlines using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) model. By filling in these gaps, the researcher contributes to the existing literature and opens avenues for future research.

Integration of Secondary and Primary Data: While previous studies have primarily relied on secondary data, this study adopts a combination of secondary and primary data collection methods. This unique approach adds depth and richness to analysing the BSC model's three perspectives.

Customer Perspective: Unlike previous research that considered the customer perspective based on passenger numbers and revenue, this study incorporates customers' opinions and experiences to measure the customer perspective. This novel addition provides a fresh perspective on understanding customer satisfaction.

Quantitative Analysis of Internal Process Perspective: Previous studies have predominantly used qualitative data to analyse the internal process perspective. In contrast, this study employs quantitative data analysis to gain insights into the internal operations of the airline. It contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the internal perspective within the BSC model.

Internal Leadership as an Aspect of the BSC Model: While many studies have explored the relationship between the BSC model and leadership, few have specifically focused on the internal leadership aspect. By incorporating internal leadership as part of the BSC model, this research offers a unique contribution to the literature.

Combination of Secondary and Quantitative Data: The researcher's use of secondary and quantitative data collection methods is a novel approach to measuring organisational performance. This combination saves time and resources, particularly when examining the three perspectives of the BSC model.

Focus on Organisational Performance: This research fills a gap in the literature by focusing on organisational performance rather than solely on employee performance. Additionally, this study explicitly explores the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan, an area that has yet to receive much attention in previous research.

Novel Research Framework: The research framework introduced in this study incorporates six independent and dependent variables and two moderators. These variables and moderators differ from those used in previous studies, contributing to the advancement of the literature.

Longitudinal Analysis: Unlike studies that analyse performance over a limited number of years, this research examines the financial condition, customer perspective, and learning & growth perspective of PIA Airlines over ten years. This

detailed analysis enhances the understanding of performance trends and provides a comprehensive evaluation.

Benchmarking and Comparative Analysis: Using time series data analysis, the researcher compares PIA Airlines' performance over the past ten years with three other airlines (Delta, Sri Lankan, and Singapore Airlines). Additionally, the study conducts a cross-sectional analysis comparing PIA Airlines' performance with the same three airlines over the last five years. This comparative approach adds value to understanding performance dynamics.

Hypothesis Testing: The researcher employs different tests to assess the reliability of hypotheses and analyse their results. This approach adds rigour to the hypothesis testing process and contributes to the robustness of the research findings.

Focus on the Asian Airline Industry: While many studies have concentrated on industries in non-Asian countries, this research fills a gap by focusing on the Asian airline industry, specifically Pakistan. This regional focus provides insights into the performance measurement of PIA Airlines using the BSC model.

In conclusion, this research bridges gaps in the literature on measuring PIA Airlines' performance using the BSC model. By integrating secondary and primary data, considering the customer perspective, analysing the internal process perspective quantitatively, and introducing new variables and moderators, this study contributes to theoretical advancements in the field. Additionally, the longitudinal and comparative analyses and hypothesis testing provide valuable insights.

Performance Sustainability Balanced Scorecard

In the above diagram, the researcher developed a new balanced scorecard to measure the performance of PIA Airlines, and it is called the sustainability performance balanced scorecard. According to the findings from secondary data and quantitative data, it has been proved that customer perspective is not related to sustaining the performance of PIA Airlines. Because customer opinions are mixed regarding the service of PIA airline and many customers are happy to travel with PIA airline regularly.

Besides, a social perspective linked to corruption in the airline in the research is also not related to maintaining the performance of PIA airlines in Pakistan. In Pakistan, culture and values are different in the airline industry. Moreover, people's perceptions also changed in terms of critical thinking, decision-making, working style, professional behaviour and strategy management, and because of this difference, the social perspective (corruption) has no significant relation with the performance of PIA Airlines.

On the other hand, findings from secondary data and quantitative data have proved that the financial perspective; internal perspective (internal leadership), learning & growth perspective and environmental perspective (political interference) have a positive relationship with the performance of PIA Airlines.

As a result, this research may not be as representative of the actual organisational environment, in which a variety of other organisational and environmental factors influence managers' decision-making abilities. For this reason, researchers in the airline industry can take advantage of this opportunity by studying how leaders in this industry incorporate BSC and determining whether causal links exist among the various perspectives to better understand the reasons for its inability to be identified and developed in the first place.

5.3.1 Discussion Theoretical Implications

The discussion of the researcher's theoretical implications in this study highlights several important aspects that contribute to the existing literature on measuring the performance of PIA airlines using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) model and understanding the impact of leadership conduct. The researcher's identifying gaps in the literature and subsequent efforts to address them provide valuable insights and set the stage for future research.

One notable contribution of this study is adopting a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both secondary and primary data collection. While previous studies have primarily relied on secondary data, the researcher recognises the importance of gathering primary data to enrich the analysis. This approach increases the reliability and validity of the findings by complementing existing data with first-hand insights. By illustrating the step-by-step processes in the thesis operational model, the researcher provides a clear framework for researchers interested in replicating or expanding upon the study.

Another significant contribution lies in expanding the customer perspective within the BSC model. While previous research has predominantly focused on indicators such as passenger numbers and revenue, the researcher introduces a new dimension by considering customer feedback and experiences. This addition enhances understanding of customer satisfaction and its impact on airline performance. By incorporating customers' opinions and experiences, the researcher offers a more comprehensive and

nanced assessment of the customer perspective, which can guide strategic decision-making in the airline industry.

The researcher's emphasis on the internal process perspective and its relation to leadership conduct is another valuable contribution. While previous studies have explored organisations' internal processes, few have specifically examined the role of internal leadership within the BSC model. By considering internal leadership as an integral aspect of the internal process perspective, the researcher sheds light on the importance of effective leadership in driving organisational performance. This insight fills a gap in the literature and emphasises the need for further exploration of the relationship between leadership behaviour and performance outcomes.

Furthermore, the researcher's use of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods presents a pragmatic and resource-efficient approach. By leveraging secondary data for specific perspectives of the BSC model and incorporating quantitative data for the internal operations perspective, the researcher optimises the research process without compromising the thoroughness of the analysis. This approach showcases a practical strategy for future researchers needing more time and resources.

While the theoretical implementations of this study are commendable, it is essential to acknowledge some limitations. The focus on PIA airlines in Pakistan may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other airlines or industries. Replicating the study in different contexts would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the applicability of the BSC model and its impact on performance measurement. Additionally, the researcher's choice of data collection methods should align with the research objectives and questions to ensure the reliability and validity of the findings.

5.4 Practical Implications

Discussion on Literature from BSC began in 1992 and has addressed a wide range of themes since. Because of its integration with other ideas to accomplish a complete aim, BSC, which originated as a management accounting concept, has been widely adopted. It examines specific disciplines with which BSC has a long history of the association to give much-needed insight into current trends and inspire future research to evaluate the performance and effect of leadership behaviour in the aviation sector.

Addressing Environmental, Social, and Ethical Issues: Sustainability-Balanced Scorecards (SBSCs): There is a growing interest in airline sustainability performance assessment and management systems because environmental, social and ethical problems are becoming more strategic. It examines the balanced scorecard (BSC), a performance assessment and management method that balances financial, non-financial, and short-term and long-term performance indicators. Sustainability-balanced scorecards (SBSCs) modify the original BSC that addresses environmental, social, and ethical problems.

Understanding the Structure of SBSCs: Building Performance Dimensions, Strategic Objectives, and Linkages: The subject of significant scholarly study is the SBSC structure and how it may be built to relate performance dimensions, strategic objectives, and the logical linkage among these aspects. According to this research, BSC changes aimed at enhancing sustainability are driven by practical, social, political, or standardising theoretical viewpoints. Furthermore, these changes may be linked to a conceptual framework of generalised SBSC structures. There is a hierarchy between performance views and strategic objectives and a relationship between them and an airline value system.

Comparative Analysis: BSC Research in the Airline Industry vs General Business and Management: BSC research in the airline industry is still in its initial stages, with most studies completed in the last ten years, whereas BSC research in general business and management dates to 1992. According to Elbanna (2006), a social perspective linked to corruption in the airline in the research is also not related to maintaining the performance of PIA airlines in Pakistan. In Pakistan, culture and values are different in the airline industry. Moreover, people's perceptions regarding critical thinking, decision-making, working style, professional behaviour and strategy management also changed. Because of this difference, the social perspective (corruption) has no significant relation with the performance of PIA Airlines. On the other hand, findings from secondary data and quantitative data have proved that the financial perspective, internal perspective (internal leadership), learning & growth perspective and environmental perspective (political interference) have a positive relationship with the performance of PIA Airlines. As a result, this research may not represent the actual organisational environment, in which various other organisational and environmental

factors influence managers' decision-making abilities. For this reason, researchers in the airline industry can take advantage of this opportunity by studying how leaders in this industry incorporate BSC and determining whether causal links exist among the various perspectives to understand better the reasons for its inability to be identified and developed in the first place.

Practical Implementations for Performance Enhancement in the Airline Industry:

This study has many practical implementations specifically related to the airline industry.

Politics should be controlled within all sectors of airlines. Because of political interference, leaders cannot make proper decisions, and management fails to improve the service.

On the other hand, unnecessary staff are hired just because of government references. This matter should be considered and try to minimise the referenced jobs because it badly affects the performance of the business and turnover for each year is reduced.

The airline must consider its expenses and revenue statements and reduce overhead costs. For example, buying international aircraft with high fuel consumption and maintenance costs should stop buying. At the same time, salaries should reduce by firing unnecessary and unmotivated staff. Improve Service PIA should improve its services as it represents a whole country, and poor service would damage the reputation of Pakistan. The airline needs to change the internal system of controlling and monitoring employees. Update the check-in and check-out system and make the luggage point easy and manageable.

Recruit On Merit All staff, including pilots, engineers, technicians, managers, cleaners, security members, and immigration staff, should hire on merit. No personal or high authority references would be acceptable for any job position. This change would help to improve service and reduce corruption and favouritism.

Regular Training Employees Regular training is essential for all employees. Train them according to the system, and when leaders make a new decision and bring change in the system, employees must know about change clearly and act according to the instruction.

Effective purchase of Fleets Buying aircraft is a compassionate and expensive decision for any airline. In PIA's condition, fleets should not be purchased on a lease basis as they are costly, and airlines spend heavily on maintenance.

Improve Security System PIA airline needs to improve its security system because this is very important for the reputation of the company and the safety of passengers and staff. Proper machines should be fixed to scan the luggage and all people who come to the airport and go out.

Airports At the Right Place In Pakistan, airports are not located in suitable places. Airport between or near the city is dangerous and unsafe for people and threatening at the time of landing. On the other hand, build the airport with ample parking space and enough sitting space with restaurants where visitors or passengers can wait in the situation of delayed flights.

Introduce Advanced Technology In planes of PIA and at airports, there is no proper advanced technology in use. PIA should install a new system in luggage points so passengers can see every detail. Also, in parking spaces wherein digital monitors, people can see where the space is empty. In the plane, the LED screen has all advanced functions so passengers can enjoy their journey.

Aircraft Monitoring regularly, many accidents and incidents happened with PIA planes because of less monitoring. PIA can save the cost of crash planes and many people's lives by maintaining their fleets and checking all necessary functions daily. Such as tyre pressure, fuel leakage, engine, and internal system.

Medical Check-ups PIA should do regular medical check-ups for all staff and pilots because the staffs of PIA take sick consent very often. Very old employees work in airlines that are not medically fit for the job and are just a business liability. At the same time, fitness for pilots is as essential as the business's success.

5.4.1 Discussion Practical Implications

Implementing the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) in the airline industry has gained significant attention recently. Developed initially as a management accounting concept, the BSC has evolved into a comprehensive performance assessment and management

method incorporating financial and non-financial indicators. In response to the growing importance of environmental, social, and ethical issues, sustainability-balanced scorecards (SBSCs) have been introduced to address these concerns.

The structure of SBSCs is a subject of scholarly study, aiming to establish a framework that relates performance dimensions, strategic objectives, and their logical linkages. Various perspectives, including practical, social, political, and theoretical viewpoints, drive changes in the BSC to enhance sustainability. The relationship between performance views, strategic objectives, and the airline value system highlights the importance of aligning goals and values within the organization.

While BSC research in the airline industry is still relatively nascent compared to general business and management studies, there is a growing interest in understanding how BSC can be effectively incorporated into the industry. A case study on PIA Airlines in Pakistan reveals that while corruption has no significant relation to performance, other perspectives, such as financial, internal, learning and growth, and environmental, show a positive relationship.

Several recommendations can be considered to implement BSC in the airline industry practically. Firstly, political interference should be controlled to enable effective decision-making and management improvements. Minimizing referenced jobs and reducing overhead costs help address financial challenges. Improving service quality, enhancing internal controls, and recruiting based on merit enhance overall performance. Regular training, effective fleet purchasing, security system improvements, optimal airport locations, and the introduction of advanced technology further contribute to operational excellence.

Researchers and industry practitioners must explore the causal links and opportunities for incorporating BSC effectively within the airline industry. By understanding the specific challenges and contexts of the industry, better insights can be gained to identify and develop strategies that lead to improved performance and sustainability.

5.5 Conclusion

The chapter provides a comprehensive examination and interpretation of the findings based on various study aspects. The study overview highlighted the research objectives, methodology, and data sources, providing a foundation for the subsequent discussions.

The analysis of secondary data allowed for a thorough comparison of PIA's financial condition with that of other airlines, shedding light on its strengths and areas for improvement. The examination of customer reviews of PIA and their comparison with other airlines provided valuable insights into customer satisfaction and service quality. The assessment of the growth ratio of airlines offered a comprehensive view of PIA's performance over time.

Furthermore, the discussion of the seven hypotheses provided an in-depth exploration of their implications and supporting evidence. The theoretical implications of the findings contributed to the existing knowledge in the field. At the same time, examining sustainability and the Balanced Scorecard framework offered valuable insights into long-term performance and strategic management. The practical implications of the results guided airline management and decision-makers, highlighting potential areas for improvement. This chapter's comprehensive analysis and discussions have contributed to a deeper understanding of PIA Airlines and its various dimensions, offering valuable insights for academia and industry practitioners.

Chapter 6 Conclusions

6.0 Introduction

This chapter sets the stage for subsequent discussions by providing an overview of the study, highlighting the significant findings, recommendations, and limitations. The findings of this research offer valuable insights into the performance of PIA Airlines, identify key challenges, and provide practical recommendations for improvement. By addressing these challenges, PIA Airlines can enhance its operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and overall performance in the competitive aviation industry.

6.1 Summary of the Study

Since it is beginning in 1992, BSC literature has covered a wide range of topics. BSC, which began as a management accounting concept, has been embraced uniquely due to its integration with other ideas to achieve a more comprehensive goal. This review study looks at specific disciplines with which BSC has been often associated to provide much-needed insight into current culture and to influence future research for measuring the performance and impact of leadership conduct in the airline industry.

This research aims to measure the performance of PIA Airlines in Pakistan and to access the impact of leadership on performance using the balanced scorecard model. This study adopts the BSC as a tool for performance measurement. The first three perspectives of BSC have been checked using secondary data, and the fourth perspective has been analysed using primary data. The background of the research has been explained, and after the literature reviews, the overview of PIA Airlines has been mentioned. The problems of PIA airline and the challenges for PIA airline have been explained in chapter one. The research questions and objectives presented in this study provide a refresher and clear focus for the reader.

The Research Objectives

- To identify the current performance of PIA Airlines.
- To check the financial position of PIA Airlines.

- To identify the factors that impact leadership conduct in the internal process of PIA Airlines.
- To identify the impact of leadership conduct on the performance of PIA Airlines.

The Research Questions

- What is the current performance of PIA Airlines?
- What is the financial position of PIA Airlines?
- What are the factors that impact leadership conduct in the internal processes of PIA Airlines?
- What is the impact of leadership conduct on the performance of PIA Airlines?

The four research objectives and research questions were developed based on the research aim and the research design and analytical method were enlightened. The structure of the thesis is explained step by step through the table. In the literature review, all key points of this thesis are presented and studied. The researcher prepares the thesis operational model for the understanding of readers in chapter one. Few examples of leadership failure have been written related to leaders' decision-making, business model, and business strategy. The concept of leadership in Pakistan has been described with the help of different journals and articles. The importance of financial ratios used to measure the airline's performance and other business performance has been written with the help of empirical studies. Case studies have been explained related to benchmarking in the airline industry.

Furthermore, the review of empirical studies has been written based on this research. The table is prepared of empirical studies, including the author's name and scope of the study, the model used in this research, and finally, the results of these studies have been mentioned in the table. The research gaps have been written after the empirical studies analysed. The following section is about conceptual framework and leadership theories and practices; the researcher hypotheses have been developed from the literature review. Moreover, a diagram of the conceptual framework has been organised. Based on the conceptual framework, seven hypotheses have been framed that are:

H1: There Is a Positive Relationship Between Leadership Style and Leadership Conduct.

H2: There Is a Positive Relationship Between a Leader's Decision Making and Leadership Conduct.

H3: Corruption Moderates the Relationship Between Leader's Decision-Making and Leadership Conduct.

H4: There Is a Positive Relationship Between the Uses of Advance Technology and Leaders' Communication.

H5: There Is a Positive Relationship Between Leader's Communication and Leadership Conduct.

H6: There Is a Positive Relationship Between Leadership Conduct and Performance Of PIA.

H7: Political Interference Moderates the Relationship Between Leadership Conduct and Performance of PIA In Pakistan.

This hypothesis was prepared to achieve the results for the third and fourth research objectives.

The research methodology and design of this study are explained in detail. The study adopts a pragmatic philosophy and a deductive approach. The research problem is structured and defined. A quantitative method uses a questionnaire with five Likert scales for data collection. The questionnaire design is described, and the first and second phases of data collection are demonstrated. Content validity is established through construct, face, and criterion validity. A pilot study is conducted to ensure the validity of the research. The implications of the sample design are discussed, justifying the selected sample design. Ethical considerations and limitations of the research are addressed. The interpretation of secondary data is presented using tables, bar charts, and graphs by ratio analysis and content analysis. The primary data analysis uses SPSS, and the findings are discussed. Finally, recommendations for future researchers are provided, along with a conclusion of the thesis.

6.2 Major Findings

The significant findings related to research objectives one and two, which form the basis of the secondary data in phase one of this study, have been highlighted. the profitability and financial ratio analysis is used for financial condition and to measure

the growth of the airline. The customer reviews section was analysed by content analysis.

- The findings suggest that PIA Airlines encountered substantial financial difficulties and underperformed compared to its rivals. The airline's challenges with operational costs, revenue generation, liabilities, fleet management, and staffing contributed to its financial struggles. To enhance its performance, PIA Airlines should prioritize implementing efficient cost-control measures, optimizing fleet management, right-sizing its workforce, and exploring strategies to boost revenue and improve financial stability.
- Regarding customer reviews, the findings highlight PIA Airlines' poor performance compared to Singapore, Delta, and Sri Lankan Airlines. PIA Airlines received a two-star rating, indicating ineffective customer satisfaction. PIA Airlines needs a competitive advantage and better ratings to improve its position. Customer complaints include poor service, luggage mishandling, staff behaviour, entertainment issues, and flight discomfort. These concerns are linked to leadership, communication, technology, decision-making, corruption, and political interference. Singapore Airlines received better feedback, while Delta Airlines and Singapore Airlines excelled in crisis management. PIA Airlines should focus on customer service, operational efficiency, fleet management, and crisis handling to enhance performance and establish a more substantial industry position.
- Regarding growth ratio, the findings highlight the persistent challenges faced by PIA Airlines in achieving consistent growth over the past decade. The unfavourable learning and growth ratios underscore the importance of addressing operational issues and implementing effective strategies to foster growth. PIA Airlines can position itself for a more successful and prosperous future by addressing these challenges.

The study findings highlight the financial difficulties and underperformance of PIA Airlines compared to competitors, stemming from operational costs, revenue generation, fleet management, and staffing challenges. To improve, PIA should prioritize cost control, fleet optimization, right sizing the workforce, and revenue

strategies. Customer reviews indicate dissatisfaction with service quality, luggage handling, staff behaviour, entertainment, and comfort. Enhancing leadership, communication, technology, and crisis handling is crucial. Addressing operational challenges is critical for future growth. The findings cover the first and second research objectives for this study.

The significant findings related to research objectives three and four, which form the basis of the conceptual framework in phase two of this study, have been highlighted.

H1: Contrary to the hypothesis, the study's results do not support a significant impact of leadership style on organizational performance. The study acknowledges the inclusion of both autocratic and democratic leadership styles. These findings highlight the study's limitations and emphasize the need to consider cultural factors in understanding leadership dynamics. Future research should delve deeper into cultural influences and explore alternative leadership approaches to gain a nuanced understanding and develop strategies for effective leadership conduct in diverse organizational settings.

H2: The regression analysis results support the hypothesis that decision-making significantly influences leadership conduct. The findings indicate that effective decision-making empowers leaders to demonstrate positive leadership behaviours, while inadequate decision-making can impede leadership effectiveness. Based on these results, organisations are encouraged to prioritise cultivating decision-making skills among their leaders. Enhancing decision-making capabilities can promote positive leadership conduct, ultimately driving organisational success.

H3: The findings presented in this study provide valuable insights into the intricate dynamics within PIA Airlines and enhance our understanding of the factors impacting its performance. However, further analysis and exploration are needed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the complex relationship between corruption, leadership, and airline performance in Pakistan's unique context. Future research should delve deeper into these aspects to uncover additional nuances and implications, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the topic.

H4: The regression analysis findings confirm the hypothesis that advanced technology positively impacts leadership communication in the airline industry. Advanced technology enables leaders to enhance communication efficiency, streamline operations, and provide a superior experience for passengers, customers, and employees. The effective integration of advanced technology is vital for maintaining competitiveness in the dynamic airline industry and meeting the growing expectations of modern air travel.

H5: The regression analysis findings validate the hypothesis that communication and leadership conduct are positively and significantly related. Effective communication enables leaders to articulate their vision, establish trust, encourage collaboration, and motivate team members. Understanding the significance of communication and honing practical communication skills are essential for leaders to enhance their leadership conduct and drive organisational success.

H6: In summary, the regression analysis confirms the hypothesis that leadership conduct and performance in PIA Airlines are positively and significantly related. Effective leadership influences various aspects, including decision-making, communication, motivation, and team management, resulting in improved overall performance. Acknowledging the significance of leadership conduct and dedicating resources to leadership development initiatives can significantly contribute to the success and advancement of PIA Airlines.

H7: In summary, the moderation analysis highlights significant relationships and interactions between performance, leadership conduct, and political interference. Positive leadership conduct positively affects performance, while political interference negatively impacts it. The interaction between leadership conduct and political interference further exacerbates the airline's performance. These findings underscore the need to reduce political interference and promote effective leadership practices to enhance the performance of PIA Airlines.

Based on hypothesis testing, the study's findings supported five out of the seven research hypotheses (H2, H4, H5, H6, and H7). However, H1 and H3 were unsupported due to unforeseen circumstances or unexpected outcomes. These findings underscore

the importance of acknowledging and investigating unexpected results, which can lead to valuable insights and future research opportunities.

6.3 Recommendations for PIA Airline

While measuring the performance of PIA Airlines and assessing the impact of leadership using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) provides valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge several limitations specific to PIA:

- The focus on PIA Airlines limits the generalizability of the findings to other airlines within the industry. Each airline operates within a unique context, and factors such as organizational structure, market conditions, and cultural influences can significantly impact performance. Replicating the study across multiple airlines would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the applicability of the BSC model and the leadership-performance relationship.
- The availability and quality of data pose a limitation. PIA's data may be subject to limitations such as accuracy, reliability, or completeness, which can affect the accuracy and validity of the performance measurements.
- The study's reliance on self-reported data, such as customer reviews or employee surveys, may introduce biases or subjective interpretations.

Considering the limitations and potential sources of error when interpreting the results and drawing conclusions about the performance and leadership impact on PIA Airlines using the BSC framework is crucial.

In addition to the limitations mentioned above, it is essential to consider the significant findings that may impact the measurement of PIA Airlines' performance and the assessment of leadership impact using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC). The findings may reveal specific challenges and areas of improvement for PIA. For example, the financial perspective of the BSC may uncover issues related to revenue generation, profitability, and financial stability. It may highlight the need for effective cost management, revenue diversification strategies, and addressing any financial inefficiencies. The internal perspective may shed light on operational processes, employee satisfaction, and internal controls. It may identify opportunities for streamlining operations, enhancing service quality, and improving workforce

productivity. The customer perspective may provide insights into customer satisfaction, loyalty, and perceptions of service quality, allowing PIA to identify areas for improvement and better meet customer expectations. Finally, the learning and growth perspective may highlight the importance of continuous employee development, training programs, and technology adoption to drive innovation and enhance competitiveness. Understanding these significant findings within the context of PIA's performance and leadership impact is crucial for making informed decisions and implementing effective strategies to drive organizational success.

6.4 Contribution to knowledge

The researcher's theoretical implementations in this study contribute to the existing literature on measuring the performance of PIA Airlines using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) model and understanding the impact of leadership conduct. The researcher addresses gaps in the literature by adopting a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both secondary and primary data collection. This approach enhances the reliability and validity of the findings and provides a transparent operational model for future research. The study also expands the customer perspective within the BSC model, considering customer feedback and experiences to assess customer satisfaction and guide decision-making better. The researcher emphasizes the role of internal leadership within the BSC model, filling a gap in the literature and highlighting the relationship between leadership behaviour and performance outcomes. Using quantitative and qualitative data collection methods demonstrates a practical and resource-efficient approach. However, limitations include focusing on PIA Airlines in Pakistan, which may limit generalizability, and the need to align data collection methods and research objectives. Future research can replicate the study in different contexts and ensure the reliability and validity of findings through appropriate data collection methods.

On the other hand, Implementing the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) in the airline industry has garnered attention as a comprehensive performance assessment and management method. Sustainability-balanced scorecards (SBSCs) have been introduced to address environmental, social, and ethical concerns. Scholarly research focuses on establishing a framework that relates performance dimensions, strategic objectives, and their logical linkages within SBSCs. The alignment of goals and values is crucial within the airline industry, considering various perspectives and driving changes in the BSC to enhance

sustainability. While BSC research in the airline industry is still emerging, there is a growing interest in effectively incorporating it. A case study on PIA Airlines highlights the positive relationship between different perspectives, such as financial, internal, learning and growth, and environmental, with performance. Practical recommendations include controlling political interference, addressing financial challenges through cost reduction, improving service quality and internal controls, recruiting based on merit, investing in training and technology, and optimizing airport locations. Further exploration is needed to understand causal links and develop strategies for effective BSC implementation in the airline industry, considering its unique challenges and contexts, to improve performance and sustainability.

6.5 Limitations of Research

When examining the performance of PIA and to assess the impact of leadership on performance using balanced scorecard, researchers should be aware of several potential problems and limitations.

Additionally, this research is based on Pakistan airline, PIA (Pakistan International Airlines), another limitation of this study. The culture of Pakistan is different from other countries, and people's mindsets are also significantly different from other countries. The achieved findings are related to Pakistani culture, and the definition of leadership in Pakistan has a different meaning, as explained in chapter one. It could be possible that the variables from this research framework could be misplaced if implemented in other countries' airlines (non-Asian airlines). The dependent variable could be possibly turned into independent variables and it with the moderators. The moderators in this research could maybe not moderate when applying to foreign countries' airlines. Future researchers could test the research hypotheses from this research on other countries' airlines for a better understanding to measure the performance of airlines.

Likewise, the airline industry is a limitation of the research. In the airline industry, the prevailing leadership is different to other sectors. On the other hand, the structure of airlines and the culture inside the airline is also significantly different from other businesses and originations.

Speaking of the airline industry, the following limitation of this research is PIA airlines in Pakistan. Future researchers could select another airline in Pakistan (Airblue, AirSial

and SereneAir) to measure the performance of airlines using BSC and check the leadership impact on the airline's performance. Every airline has its policies and rules, and the leadership style and conduct could be different from PIA airlines; then, the results could be better, and the comparison between the Pakistan airline could be established.

Additionally, the study aims to measure PIA's performance and assess leadership's influence using the balanced scorecard (BSC) framework.

- **Causality and Attribution:** Establishing a clear causal relationship between leadership and performance can be challenging. While the BSC provides a framework to measure and evaluate various performance indicators, isolating the influence of leadership from other organisational factors becomes complex. Considering many variables affecting performance, such as market conditions, operational factors, and external influences, is essential.
- **Subjectivity and Perceptions:** Assessing leadership impact involves subjective evaluations and perceptions. The BSC relies on the interpretation and judgment of leaders, employees, and other stakeholders when assigning ratings or scores to performance indicators. These subjective assessments can introduce biases, differing viewpoints, and discrepancies in evaluating leadership effectiveness and its impact on performance.
- **Reliance on Self-Reported Data:** The BSC typically relies on self-reported data, such as surveys or interviews, which may be subject to biases, social desirability, or memory recall issues. Individuals may provide responses that they believe are expected or favourable, leading to potential inaccuracies in the data. Researchers should employ rigorous validation techniques and triangulation methods to enhance the reliability and validity of self-reported data.
- **Limited Generalizability:** Findings derived from studying the impact of leadership on PIA's performance using the BSC may need more generalizability beyond the specific context of the airline industry. Factors such as organisational culture, industry dynamics, and unique circumstances within PIA may limit the applicability of the research findings to other organisations or industries.

- **Time Lag:** Measuring the impact of leadership on performance using the BSC requires collecting data over a specific period to capture changes and trends. However, there can be a time lag between leadership actions and their visual impact on performance metrics. Longitudinal studies or extended data collection periods may be necessary to capture meaningful changes and establish more robust correlations.
- **Limited Scope of the BSC:** The BSC framework primarily focuses on quantifiable and tangible performance metrics across financial, customer, internal processes, and learning and growth dimensions. However, it may only capture part of the full range of leadership attributes and qualities that influence performance, such as ethical leadership, interpersonal skills, or adaptive behaviours. Researchers should consider complementing BSC data with qualitative approaches to capture these nuances.

Awareness of these problems and limitations can help researchers address potential biases, design appropriate research methodologies, and interpret the findings within the context of their study on the impact of leadership on PIA's performance using the BSC. Here are additional considerations related to data collection and sample size when researching the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC):

- **Data Collection Challenges:** Data collection can present various challenges, mainly when collecting data on performance indicators across different dimensions of the BSC. These challenges may include accessing reliable and accurate data, coordinating with multiple departments or units within PIA, and ensuring data consistency and quality over time. Researchers should establish clear protocols, engage with relevant stakeholders, and employ data validation techniques to address these challenges effectively.
- **Sample Size:** Determining an appropriate sample size is crucial to ensure the reliability and generalizability of the study's findings. With a larger sample size, the results are more likely to represent the broader population of interest, enhancing the external validity of the research. However, considerations such as resource limitations, feasibility, and the size of the target population within PIA must be considered when determining the optimal sample size.

- **Representative Sampling:** To enhance the sample's representativeness, researchers should strive for a diverse and well-balanced sample that includes leaders, employees from various departments or levels, and other relevant stakeholders. This approach helps ensure that the study captures different perspectives and minimizes the potential for biased results.
- **Data Saturation:** Data saturation may be an essential consideration depending on the nature of the research and the specific research questions. Saturation refers to data collection where additional data no longer provides new insights or leads to additional themes or patterns. Researchers should monitor data saturation during qualitative data collection methods (such as interviews or focus groups) to determine when sufficient data has been obtained to answer the research questions adequately.
- **Mixed Methods Considerations:** If employing a mixed methods approach, researchers should carefully consider the integration and complementarity of quantitative and qualitative data. Both data types should align with the research objectives and be collected to allow for meaningful triangulation and convergence of findings. Researchers should also ensure that the sample size for each data collection method is sufficient to generate valid and reliable results.
- **Longitudinal Data Collection:** Given the dynamic nature of leadership and performance, longitudinal data collection can provide valuable insights into how leadership behaviours and actions evolve and their impact on performance outcomes. Longitudinal studies require careful planning to ensure data consistency and participant retention over an extended period. Researchers should consider the feasibility and resources required for longitudinal data collection when designing the study.
- **Ethical Considerations in Data Collection:** Researchers must adhere to ethical data collection guidelines, ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and privacy protection. Clear communication about the purpose and procedures of data collection, the voluntary nature of participation, and the use and storage of data should be provided to participants. Researchers should also obtain approvals or permissions from relevant authorities or institutional review boards.

By addressing these considerations related to data collection and sample size, researchers can enhance the robustness, validity, and ethical integrity of their study on the impact of leadership on the performance of PIA using the BSC framework.

The research is limited by the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, which restricted travel and made it challenging for the researcher to conduct the study effectively. The researcher's inability to travel to Pakistan and meet respondents in person affected the data collection process. As a result, convenience sampling was used instead of the preferred method of random sampling, especially for top management. During the COVID-19 pandemic, accessing PIA staff for research may present additional challenges and considerations.

- **Remote Work and Limited Access:** Due to the pandemic, PIA staff may work remotely or operate under restricted access policies. It could limit the availability of staff members for data collection, especially if they are not physically present at the workplace. Researchers should adapt their data collection methods accordingly, such as utilising virtual platforms for interviews or surveys.
- **Sensitivity to Workload and Stress:** The pandemic has significantly impacted the aviation industry, including PIA. PIA staff members may face increased workloads, operational challenges, and heightened stress levels. Researchers should be mindful of these circumstances and the potential impact on participation rates and the quality of responses. Flexible and empathetic approaches to data collection can help accommodate staff members' needs and circumstances.
- **Health and Safety Protocols:** Prioritise the health and safety of PIA staff members during the research process. Ensure all data collection activities adhere to local health guidelines, organisational protocols, and ethical standards. It may include using virtual interview platforms, maintaining physical distancing during in-person interactions, and providing necessary personal protective equipment if face-to-face data collection is required.
- **Collaboration and Communication:** Establish clear lines of communication and collaboration with PIA management or relevant stakeholders to ensure alignment with organisational priorities, policies, and procedures related to research activities during the pandemic. Engage in ongoing dialogue to

address concerns, seek necessary permissions, and obtain support for accessing PIA staff members.

- **Flexibility and Adaptability:** Recognise that the pandemic situation is dynamic, and circumstances may change rapidly. Researchers should be flexible and adaptable in their data collection methods, timelines, and expectations. Stay informed about updates related to COVID-19 protocols within PIA and be prepared to adjust research plans accordingly.
- **Data Analysis and Interpretation:** Consider the potential influence of the pandemic on the research findings. When analysing and interpreting the data, consider the unique circumstances and challenges faced by PIA staff members during the COVID-19 crisis.

By considering these additional factors related to accessing PIA staff during the COVID-19 pandemic, researchers can navigate the challenges and research the impact of leadership using the BSC framework with sensitivity, adaptability, and ethical responsibility.

6.6 Recommendation for Future Researchers

Based on the findings and limitations of the current study, several recommendations can be made for future research:

- **Expand the research scope:** Future studies can include a broader range of airlines to compare their performance with PIA. It would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the industry dynamics and allow for more robust conclusions.
- **Longitudinal research design:** Conducting longitudinal studies that span extended periods would enable researchers to observe performance trends and changes over time. It would provide a deeper understanding of the impact of leadership conduct on airline performance.
- **Use various performance measurement tools:** Besides the Balanced Scorecard (BSC), future researchers can explore other performance measurement tools or frameworks to assess airline performance. It can capture different performance aspects and provide a more holistic evaluation.

- In-depth analysis of leadership conduct: Further research can focus on exploring specific dimensions of leadership conduct, such as communication, decision-making, and employee engagement, and their impact on performance. It would contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the leadership-performance relationship.
- Consider additional variables: Future studies can incorporate variables influencing airline performance, such as organizational culture, employee motivation, and competitive strategies. It would help in developing a more comprehensive model for performance assessment.
- Sample size and diversity: Increasing the sample size and including a diverse range of participants, such as employees from different levels and departments within the airline, can enhance the generalizability of the findings and provide a more comprehensive perspective on performance.
- Qualitative research approach: Complementing quantitative data with qualitative research methods, such as interviews or focus groups, can provide richer insights into the experiences and perceptions of employees and customers. This qualitative data can help in understanding the underlying factors that drive performance.
- Industry-specific focus: Future studies can delve deeper into specific challenges and issues faced by the airline industry, such as regulatory compliance, safety measures, or customer service. This industry-specific focus would provide unique insights and recommendations tailored to the aviation sector.
- International comparison: Conducting comparative studies across different countries or regions can shed light on the cultural and contextual factors that influence leadership and performance in the airline industry. This comparative analysis can lead to valuable cross-cultural insights.
- Integrating sustainability measures: Given the growing importance of sustainability in the airline industry, future research can incorporate sustainability indicators and evaluate their impact on performance. It would contribute to developing sustainable practices and strategies within the sector.

By addressing these recommendations, future researchers can build upon the existing knowledge and further contribute to the understanding of measuring performance in the

airline industry and assessing the impact of leadership conduct using the Balanced Scorecard or other relevant frameworks.

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8.0 Appendixes

8.1 The Research Questionnaire

“TO MEASURE THE PERFORMANCE OF PIA AIRLINES AND TO ACCESS THE IMPACT OF LEADERSHIP ON PERFORMANCE USING BALANCED SCORECARD”

Dear Respondent:

I am a DBA student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am conducting research that investigates “to measure the performance of PIA airlines in Pakistan and access the impact of leadership on performance using balanced scorecard (BSC) model” I would appreciate it if you completed this research questionnaire. It will take no more than 10 minutes. Any information obtained in connection with this research would remain confidential.

Gender

Male

Female

Respondents Age Group

Below 20

21 – 30 Years

31 - 40 Years

41–50 Years

51 - 60 Years

Above 61 Years

Qualification

High school

Bachelor’s

Master’s

PhD

Others

Work experience

Less than 5 Years 5- 10 Years 11-15 Years 16-20 Years Over 20
Years

Designation

**Strongly Agree (SA) Agree (A) Neutral (N) Disagree (D) Strongly
Disagree (SD)**

#	Statements and Questions	SA	A	N	D	SD
1	When assigning tasks, I consider people's skills and interests.					
2	PIA airline productivity has not improved in the last ten years.					
3	The key to successful conflict resolution is respecting my opponent.					
4	PIA sales revenue has exceeded that of our competitors. Performance					
5	The best decision will be the one with the most significant consent.					
6	I consider the moral and ethical consequences of my choices.					
7	I am good at finding practical solutions to the problem.					
8	My action shows people what I want from them.					
9	PIA airlines profit rate has exceeded every year.					
10	PIA airlines have enough technology to improve airlines performance.					
11	Giving regular feedback to employees is good for airline performance.					

12	Customer reviews are essential for PIA airlines performance.					
13	I am in favour of democratic leadership.					
14	Political interference has a terrible impact on PIA airlines performance.					
15	Hiring employees under political pressure.					
16	PIA airlines have good security at airports. Performance.					
17	Corruptions in PIA are damaging airlines.					
18	Leaders elected not according to their qualifications.					
19	Responsible people for plane crashes must punish.					
20	In your opinion, pilots understand their responsibilities.					
21	PIA management follow strict technical procedures to maintain check and balance					
22	PIA has a flawed aviation communication system.					

8.2 Questionnaire Consent Form

Questionnaire Consent Form

I (*respondent's name*).....hereby give my permission to **Zoya Asghar** (*researcher*) to allow me to respond to a questionnaire and quote my responses in a scholarly research paper. I understand that their work is for academic purposes.

I also understand that I waive any claim for copyright to this material should the researchers ever publish it in a scholarly journal or electronic format online.

I understand that the Research Title is investigating “**to measure the performance of PIA airlines in Pakistan and to access the impact of leadership on performance using balanced scorecard (BSC) model**”.

I also understand that the researcher, hereby named **Zoya Asghar**, will maintain my **anonymity** with regard to my responses to Questionnaire items.

I hereby give my permission in the form of my signature below:

Signature..... **Date**.....

